

Deliverable No. 4.3

Project acronym:

FarFish

Project title:

Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

Grant agreement No: **727891**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme

Start date of project: **1st June 2017**

Duration: **48 months**

Due date of deliverable:	31/01/2019
Submission date:	23/09/2020
File Name:	FarFish D4.3_MR1 for each CS_2.0
Revision number:	02
Document status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	PU

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Deliverable D4.3

Management Recommendation 1 for each case study

23/09/2020

Foreword

More than 20% of the European fishing fleets catches are taken from non-European waters. Access to these waters is often based on agreements with coastal states that allow the EU fleet to fish from surplus stocks in return for financial support. These agreements have been subjected to criticism, as these fisheries are sometimes poorly regulated and management decisions are often based on limited knowledge, compliance, and enforcement capabilities. It is also too often the case that trust between stakeholders is lacking. The aim of the FarFish project is to overcome these hurdles. The FarFish project is designed around six case study areas in which the European fleet is actively engaged in fishing activities, including Cape Verde, Mauritania, Senegal and Seychelles, as well as the international high-seas areas in the southeast and southwest Atlantic.

This document serves as the first proposal for management recommendations (MR1) for each of the FarFish case studies. MRs are formal arrangements between a management authority and the operators in the respective case studies. It specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery. This approach is based on the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS), which is a management approach developed within the FP7 project [EcoFishMan](#). The RFMS is an adaptive management approach that is results-based and ecosystem-based. The RFMS attempts to reduce micromanagement by involving stakeholders and increase the degree of co-management by delegating management responsibilities to resource users. According to this approach, the formal responsibility for developing the MRs is largely delegated to the resource users e.g. EU fishing fleet.

These MR1 are developed following the “draft General Guidelines for making MRs” presented in FarFish ([D3.1](#)) and is based on the Management Recommendation Invitation ([D3.2](#)), where the outcome targets (OTs) for each case study are proposed. The proposed OTs area based on input from Management Plan Zero ([D4.1](#)), input from operators at the MR Kick-off meeting ([D4.2](#)) and additional stakeholder meetings facilitated by FarFish stakeholder interaction (WP1), and input from FarFish Work package (WP)/Case study (CS) leader meeting in Mindelo (Cape Verde, Nov. 2018).

It is not the intention of the FarFish project to replicate measures that are already being worked on within the contexts of the SFPAs agreements, national management authorities or RFMOs; but rather to address issues that can potentially support those and be therefore of added benefit to all stakeholders. FarFish has therefore been in good contact with the respective case study authorities, RFMOs and other stakeholders to decide on where it can be of greatest benefit to support ongoing measures.

This report (Deliverable 4.3) is a collation of six “stand-alone” MRs i.e. for each of the FarFish case studies. They are all developed according to the same guidelines and are therefore with the same structure, which means that there is significant repetition between each MR.

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MAURITANIAN CASE STUDY

SEYCHELLES CASE STUDY

SOUTHWEST ATLANTIC CASE STUDY

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File Name:	FarFish D4.3_MR1 Southwest Atlantic
Revision number:	02
Document status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public

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Deliverable D4.3

Management Recommendation 1

Southwest Atlantic

23/09/2020

Executive Summary

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) for The international mixed fishery in FAO Area 41, mainly in the subareas 41.3.1 and 41.3.2, at the part of the Patagonian shelf and slope (< 300m) that extends beyond the Argentina EEZ and the Falkland Islands Outer Conservation Zone. The fact there is no Regional Fisheries Organization Organisations as key body responsible for managing fisheries, makes the coexistence of international fleets within the area difficult, especially due to the different levels of compliance and enforcement of the flag states.

The MR1 follows the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, D3.1) and is based on the Management Recommendation Invitation (FarFish, D3.2), where the outcome targets (OTs) were proposed. Only the obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version of the MR. This is because they are considered important to reach the main objectives of the MR which were identified by authorities in Management Recommendation Zero (MRO) (FarFish, D4.1), taking into account input from operators at the MR Kick-off meeting (FarFish, D4.2). The recommended OTs are not considered vital to the MR progress aiming to reach the management objectives, but FarFish will address these in the next iteration and in the following version of the MR (MR2).

The aim of this MR is to establish a level-playing field and improve monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) in this area beyond national jurisdiction where no RFMO is present. The MR1 includes the development a soft-law mechanism [International Conference] to initiate dialogue between stakeholders and support international cooperation for improved MCS. FarFish also aims to contribute to increase knowledge on monitoring in the Southwest Atlantic looking at available AIS data using the Global Fishing Watch. Subject to data availability and collaboration and engagement from relevant national and/or international control authorities in the area, it might be possible to explore the idea of developing with EFCA a regional pilot project for operational coordination through the development of a specific control and Inspection Programme.

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Abbreviations

ABNJ	Areas Beyond National jurisdiction
AIS	Automatic Identification System
ASW	Atlantic Southwest
CAFS	Chinese Academy of Fishery Sciences (China)
CCMAR	Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal)
CCSBT	Commission for the Conservation of Southern Bluefin Tuna
CETMAR	Centro Tecnológico del mar Fundacion (Spain)
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CGPOP	General Coordination of Fisheries Planning and Management (Brazil)
CPUE	Catch per Unit Effort
CS	Case Study
CSIC	Spanish National Research Council (Spain)
CTMFM	Joint Argentinean-Uruguay Technical Commission of the Maritime Front
DFO	Fisheries and Oceans Canada (Canada)
DG MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (EU)
DLM	Data Limited Method
EBA	Ecosystem Based Approach
EBAFM	Ecosystem Based Approach to Fisheries Management
EC	European commission
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EJF	Environmental Justice Foundation
ERS	Electronic Recording Systems
EFCA	European Fisheries Control Agency
FAD	Fish Aggregation Device
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FarFish RG	FarFish Reference Group
FICZ	Falkland Islands Interim Conservation and Management Zone
FIG	Falkland Islands Government
FIP	Fisheries Improvement Project
FitI	Fisheries Transparency Initiative
FMC	Fisheries Monitoring Centre
FOCZ	Falkland Islands Outer Conservation Zone
GES	Good Environmental Status
GFW	Global Fishing Watch
HS	High seas
HSBFC	High Seas Bottom fishery closure
HSBG	High Seas Bottom Gear
ICCAT	International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas
ICMAN-CSIC	Institute for Marine Sciences of Andalucía (ICMAN)-Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) (Spain)

IEO	The Spanish Institute of Oceanography (Spain)
IMO	International Maritime Organization
INIDEP	The National Institute of Fisheries Research and Development (Argentina)
ITLOS	International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea
IUU	Illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing
JDP	Joint Deployment Plans
LDAC	EU Long Distance Fleet Advisory Council
MATIS OHF	Icelandic Food and Biotech R & D Institute (Iceland)
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MR	Management Recommendation
NOFIMA	The Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture research (Norway)
OCEANA	International organization focused solely on ocean conservation (NGO)
OFCF	Overseas Fishery Cooperation Foundation, (Japanese NGO)
OPROMAR	Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín (Spain)
OT	Outcome Target
RPOG	Regional Ocean Governance
RBM	Results-Based Management
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
RFMS	Responsible Fisheries Management System
SCIP	Specific Control and Inspection Programme
STECF	Scientific, Technical and economic Committee for Fisheries (EU)
SYN	SP/F SYNTESA (Faroe Islands)
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
UIT	The Arctic University of Norway (Norway)
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNFSA	Straddling and highly migratory stocks agreement in ABNJ
UNGA	United Nations General Assembly
USP	University of São Paulo (Brazil)
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System
WWF	Worldwide fund for nature

Concepts/definitions

Indicator	A variable, pointer or index related to a criterion. Indicators are selected such that their variations reflect variations in key elements of the fishery resource, the social and economic well-being of the sector and the sustainability of the ecosystem. The position and trend of an indicator in relation to reference points or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. Indicators provide a bridge between objectives and actions (source: FAO 1999).
Management goals	The higher-order objective to which a management intervention is intended to contribute (OECD 2011). A management goal is derived from a management principle (constitutional-order) and is specified into a set of more operational management objectives (collective-order).
Management intervention	Strategies or instruments aimed to impact the state of a fishery with reference to authorized objectives. Examples are input and output controls and economic measures.
Management measures	Can be technical (e.g. gear selectivity etc.), input (effort)/output (catch) control, right based.
Management objectives	Fisheries management objectives are typically framed within the overall concept of sustainable development and may reflect one or more of the various dimensions and criteria that relate to it (FAO 1999). Operators through setting and implementing management measures control OTs.
Management Plan (MP)	A fisheries management plan is a formal arrangement between a fishery management authority and interested parties which identifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, details the agreed objectives for the fishery and specifies the management rules and regulations which apply to it and provides other details about the fishery which are relevant to the task of the management authority (Source: FAO 2002).
Management Recommendation (MR)	In RFMS, the management recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority and operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery. In RFMS, the formal responsibility for developing the management plan is delegated to an operator.
Management strategies	In FarFish context, it means the strategies applied to achieve OTs
Outcome Target (OT)	Outcome targets (OTs) are specific and measurable requirements that are set by an authority to make management goals operational. An OT is a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B') or a statement of presence or absence of some entity. On the basis of relevant information, this statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time ⁵⁴ . For instance, the management objective that "the fishery should be biologically sustainable" could be expressed in terms of one or more OTs such as 'Catch < 20 000t; 'bycatch < 20%'; SSB > 30 000t; 'a catch reporting system is present', etc.
Reference point	A classification device, defined in relation to the measure of an indicator, for distinguishing different management relevant states of the system under management. A Biological Reference Point is a metric of stock status. A Target Reference Point indicates a state of a system which is considered desirable and at which management action should aim. A Limit Reference Point indicates a state of a system, which is considered to be undesirable, that one therefore should seek to avoid through relevant management action.
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) is a fisheries management approach developed within the FP7 project EcoFishMan . The RFMS is an adaptive management approach that is results-based and ecosystem-based. The RFMS attempts to reduce micromanagement by involving stakeholders and increase the degree of co-management by delegating management responsibilities to resource users.

1 Introduction

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) from European operators active in the international mixed fishery in the Southwest Atlantic (ASW), FAO Area 41, mainly in the subareas 41.3.1 and 41.3.2. These areas are located at the part of the Patagonian shelf and slope (< 300m) that extends beyond the Argentina EEZ and the Falkland Islands Outer Conservation Zone (FOCZ). The operators are represented by EUs Long Distance Advisory Council (LDAC). The proposal defines the strategies and measures suggested in order to achieve the obligatory outcome targets (OT) suggested by authorities in the first MR Invitation (FarFish, 2018d) and how these strategies could be implemented in the given setting. The development of this MR1 follows the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2018c) and will address the obligatory OTs.

A Management Recommendation (MR) is basically an agreement between competent authorities, relevant operators and potentially other stakeholders, in a given fishery, that identifies measures to reach key objectives or outcome targets (OT) established by the authority in order to support sustainable fisheries.

This MR is founded on Results-Based Management (RBM) principles based on the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) approach (Figure 1), which was developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan (Silva et al., 2014, Santiago et al., 2015, Nielsen et al., 2017). The MR is arrangement between a management authority¹ and operators². The partners in the fishery and their respective roles and responsibilities are identified in the MR, which also a detailed overview of the fishery and the geographical boundaries for the MR. The MR contains the management objectives emphasized by the authorities in the Management Recommendation Zero (FarFish 2018a) and OTs which are defined in the Management Recommendation Invitation (FarFish 2018d). In line with the RFMS approach, the engagement of stakeholders is highly prioritized in FarFish. At the successful MR kick-off meeting in Vigo (Spain, June 2018), several operators representing the distant water fleet (DWF) from the European Union expressed their interests and needs, which were relevant for the development of the MR Invitation and defining the OTs (FarFish, 2018e).

¹ Authority: Organizational entity acting authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission

² Operator: Organizational unit with delegated authority to develop management recommendations and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority

1.1 Partners involved in MR1

The authority is the organizational entity acting as the authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission. They oversee the RFMS process and issue the “MR invitation”, which includes a clear specification of OTs, set in order to operationalize the goals of existing policies and the local management objectives. In the absence of a Regional Fisheries Management Organisation (RFMO) in ASW international waters of the Patagonian shelf, there is no competent fisheries management authority in this area to take the lead in the RFMS process. Following, FarFish Work Package 3 representatives will act as the leading authority, whilst considering input from relevant authorities, e.g. FAO, DG MARE and CAFS (Figure 1).

Figure 1: General description of the process of making Management Recommendations in FarFish. The responsibilities of each of the three entities are demonstrated with different colours. Authority: red/Operators: blue/ Auditors: yellow (FarFish, D3.1).

The operator is defined as an organized group of resource users, e.g. an association of fishermen or stakeholders with rights in a given fishery. They develop, propose and implement an MR which they develop based on the OTs set by the authority. The European operators qualified to respond to the MPR Invitation will provide feedback through the LDAC, represented by its Executive Secretary Alexandre Rodríguez. In addition to LDAC, two members from ARVI participated in MR1 meetings. LDAC developed this MR draft aided by CETMAR and FarFish Work Package 4 lead by UiT, aiming to demonstrate how to meet the OTs listed in the MR Invitation (FarFish, 2018d). The OTs have been revised during this process, illustrating the iterative dialogue between authority and operators that characterizes the RFMS (see Nielsen et al., 2018). Work Package 5 lead by SYN, will evaluate MR1 and provide the audit of the MR1 once approved by both operators and authorities.

Table 1: MR1 South West Atlantic entities, area, target species, fleets, main aims and time frame

MR basis	MPR1 SW Atlantic		
RFMS entities	Authorities: WP3, DG Mare, CAFS, FAO		
	Operators: WP4, LDAC		
	Auditor: WP5		
Target species	Common name	Scientific name	FAO code
	Argentine hake	<i>Merluccius hubbsi</i>	HKP
	Argentine shortfin squid	<i>Illex Argentinus</i>	SQA
	Longtail southern cod	<i>Patagonotothen ramsayi</i>	PAT
	Antarctic rockcods	<i>Nototheniidae</i>	NOX
	Patagonian squid	<i>Loligo gahi</i>	SQP
	Patagonian grenadier	<i>Macruronus magellanicus</i>	GRM
	Southern blue whiting	<i>Micromesistius australis</i>	POS
Geographical range	High seas FAO area 41 (41.3.1 and 41.3.2), depths <300 m		
Fleets	EU fleet: Spain, Portugal, Other fleets; China		
Main aims of MR	Initiate dialogue between stakeholders involved in fishery in FAO area 41, improve data collection, contribute to improved monitoring and improved level playing field		
RFMS planning period	Lifetime of FarFish project 2017-2021		

1.2 Aims of the MR1 for the Southwest Atlantic (ASW)

The main aims of the MR for (ASW) are to improve the sustainability of high seas mixed fisheries at Patagonian shelf (Figure 2), by (1) the inclusion of soft-law mechanisms, (2) improve the quality and quantity of data collection, (3) contribute to improved fishing and conservation through monitoring, control and surveillance mechanisms and thereby (4) contribute to a level playing field for international fleets involved.

Figure 2: Left: FAO Fishing Area 41 and its subareas Right: Locations of Spanish fishing effort in Southwest Atlantic. Sources: Left: www.FAO.org, Right: [Bench et al., 2009](#).

1.3 Current legislative situation in high seas fisheries in Southwest Atlantic high seas

The scope of the MR comprises Marine Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ). There is no RFMO in place for the area with the legal competence to regulate demersal or deep-water fisheries, although the area falls under the convention area of ICCAT and CCBT (Commission for the Conservation of Southern Bluefin Tuna (FarFish 2017)). With the lack of an RFMO, the background for policy objectives and jurisdiction of authorities within the RFMS process is largely absent. Nevertheless, since 2004 the international community has made significant progresses to promote the sustainable management of fisheries resources in the ABNJ mainly through both hard and soft law instruments. For instance, UN resolutions 59/25 and 61/105, which are binding for CPCs to implement, but difficult to enforce, or the set of FAO (non-binding) International Guidelines for the Management of Deep-Sea Fisheries in the High Seas. Soft law refers to quasi-legal instruments that include hortatory, rather than legally binding, obligations (Guzman and Meyer, 2010). Soft law instruments are considered as a flexible tool of compromise that can ease bargaining problems and open up mutually preferred compromises (Abbott and Snidal, 2000).

The UNGA Resolutions 61/105³ and the FAO International Guidelines for the Management of Deep-Sea Fisheries in the High Seas (FAO, 2009)⁴ were implemented by (EC) Council Regulation 734/2008⁵. To follow up on this, the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO) conducted a series of multidisciplinary research (ATLANTIS-3 Project) on international waters of the ASW from October 2007 to April 2010. The aim of the surveys was to identify VMEs and to assess the potential interactions with fishing activities (Del Rio et al, 2012; Portela et al., 2015). The research undertaken and its main findings led to the delineating of several areas to be protected, with a total area of 41,000 km², according to presence of organisms classified as vulnerable.

The European Union has also established a system concerning fishing activities of Union fishing vessels fishing outside Union waters on the high seas⁶. EU's reformed Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), which came into effect in January 2014, state that all EU fishing activities, inside and outside EU waters, are subject to the same environmental and other standards (EC 2013). Thus, the EU must conduct its external fleet in accordance with the objectives and principles set out in Articles 2 and 3 of the CFP. According to Article 2, those objectives include the application and promotion of the precautionary approach to ensure that the stocks targeted are higher levels that deliver MSY by 2020 at the latest, the application of the ecosystem principle, the promotion of the collection of scientific data and the gradual elimination of discards (FarFish, 2018g).

The main objective of the CFP is to ensure that fishing activities are environmentally, economically and socially sustainable and are managed consistently with the objectives of achieving economic, social and employment benefits, and of restoring and maintaining fish stocks above levels which can produce maximum sustainable yield and that they are contributing to the availability of food supplies. Additionally, the union has committed itself to Sustainable Development Goal 14⁷ (SDG 14) and Sustainable Development Goal 12⁸ (SDG 12). EU vessels operating under the SFPA agreement shall comply with all technical conservation measures as set out in the SFPA protocol. The CFP stresses the need to promote the objectives of CFP internationally, ensuring that Union-fishing activities outside Union waters area based on the same principles and standards as those applicable under Union law, while promoting a level playing field for Union operators and third-country operators.

³ https://www.un.org/Depts/los/general_assembly/general_assembly_resolutions.htm

⁴ <http://www.fao.org/3/i0816t/i0816t00.htm>

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32008R0734>

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32017R2403>

⁷ SDG14: conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

⁸ SDG12: ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns and their targets

1.4 Identity of the fishery in Southwest Atlantic (ASW) high seas

The European fleet take part in the mixed fisheries in FAO Area 41 in the South West Atlantic (ASW), mainly in the sub-areas 41.3.1 and 41.3.2 between 44° and 48°S (Figure 2), within areas without evidence of seamounts or Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs). Other important DWF from non-European fleets fishing in ABNJ come from China, Taiwan and Korea (FarFish, 2019). The main fishing areas are at the part of Patagonian shelf and southern slope between 110 and 250 m depth (Vilela et al., 2018), extending beyond the Argentinian EEZ and the Falkland Islands Outer Conservation Zone (FOCZ).

2 Fishery overview

The EU fleet operating in this area is almost exclusively represented by Spanish trawlers over 40 m and is the most important DWF in the area. The Spanish fleet consists of up to 19 vessels, ranging from 696 to 1,819 GT, with an average of about 1,190 GT. The Spanish long-distance freezer trawler fleet and long liners are based in Galician ports, mainly in Vigo (FarFish, 2017).

The target species are mainly represented by Argentine Hake (*Merluccius hubbsi*), Argentine shortfin squid (*Illex argentinus*), Patagonian squid (*Loligo gahi*), Antarctic rockcod (Nototheniidae), Longtail southern cod (*Patagonotothen ramsayi*) and southern blue whiting (*Micromesistius australis*) (Fig 3.1, STECF, 2018). The main by-catch species in this fishery is Patagonian grenadier (*Macruronus magellanicus*) and Patagonian toothfish (*Dissostichus eleginoides*), but also Rays mantas nei (*Raiiformes*), Stingrays (*Dasyatis spp.*), Longtail southern cod (*Patagonotothen ramsayi*) and Forkbeard (*Phycis phycis*) occurs.

Argentine hake is the main target species for demersal trawl, but also Patagonian grenadier, Patagonian squid, cod, croaker and blue whiting are caught by bottom trawl (FAO, FishStat J, 2018). Other important gears applied in the area are longline and purse seiners.

2.1 Recent catch trends in ASW

The ASW is one of the main fishing areas for the EU Distant Water Fleet (DWF) and catches in FAO 41 constituted for 14% of the catches in weight in other fishing regions (OFR) in 2016 (STECF, 2018). Although catches by DWF from China and Taiwan are considerable, they fluctuate significantly between years (FarFish, 2019). The Spanish demersal trawlers take 87% of the landed weight reported for FAO 41 and 66% of the value (STECF 2018). The total average catch volume by EU Fleets (including Russia and other former Soviet-Union countries) in ASW has decreased substantially over the last four decades and in the last decade (2007-2016) it has been about 135 tons per year, of which Spain accounts for over 70% of the catch (FAO, FishStat J 2018). Argentine hake, longtail southern cod, Antarctic rockcod and Argentine shortfin squid are the major species caught by EU fleets in the SW-Atlantic, accounting for around 63% of total catch over the last decade (FarFish, 2019)

Argentine hake is the most important in target species in weight taken by the EU fleet in these waters and the catches has been ranging between 36.4 and 24.6 thousand tons in the period from 2013-2016 (STECF, 2018). Argentina catch about 90% of all hake catches taken by demersal trawl in ASW representing 80% of all hake landings (FAO, FishStat J 2018). Catches are dominated by Argentine hake (97%) and minor catches of Southern hake (*Merluccius australis*) (Arkhipkin et al., 2015). Swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*) and Patagonian squid are not very important in terms of landed weight, by in terms of value, they were almost as important as Argentine hake in 2016 (STECF, 2018).

The squid *Illex argentinus* is the most important cephalopod species in the area and it is the target of major fisheries by both bottom trawlers and jigging vessels during the first half of the year. Bottom trawlers are mainly from Spain, whereas jiggers belong to several Asian countries such as Japan, Korea and Taiwan. The main fishing area on the high seas is between parallels 44°- 47°S. The catches of squid are highly variable and the EU catches of argentine shortfin in FAO area 41.3.1 and 41.3.2, ranged from 2.4 to 24.6 thousand tons in the period from 2013 to 2016 (STECF, 2018). A high level of IUU fishing is known or noticed to exist by the foreign fleet in the Argentinean EEZ reaching 40% of the total catches in last years (2012-2015). 2016 estimates are uncertain⁹. There is one unique population in Argentinean EEZ waters.¹⁰ In 2016, the Argentinean jiggers caught 53,869 t and trawlers 2,976 t. Estimated catches by the foreign fleet were at 2, 4 t within the Argentinean EEZ and around 40,000 t in the high seas (Fishsource.org). The amount of Southern blue whiting in EU catch has been increasing during the period from 2013 to 2016 and is mainly taken as by-catch during squid and hake fisheries by bottom trawlers from several countries, mainly from Spain. Yet, it is target fishery in Falkland waters in subarea 41.3.2. The landings of Longtail southern cod has been decreasing in the same period, but was still the second most important in landings measured by weight in 2016.

Figure 3: EU fleet activity in FAO subareas 41.3.1 and 41.3.2 by landings in weight (tons) in the period from 2013 to 2016. Source data: STECF 2018

⁹ https://www.fishsource.org/stock_page/1626

2.2 Stock status of major target species in ASW

Due to the involvement of fleets from a number of nations, the wide distribution of some of the main target species (straddling stocks), and the absence of an RFMO or any other kind of competent authority, stock assessment in FAO 41 is particularly problematic. As an example, according to Ivanovic et al. (2018), an estimated 250 squid jigging vessels from different nations were operating beyond the EEZ of Argentina, south of 44°S, with 105 fishing within the Argentine EEZ.

For some species such as Argentine hake (*Merluccius hubbsi*), stock assessment has been carried out for the Uruguay-Argentine fishery using dynamic surplus production models for the period from 1980 to 2000 (Gutiérrez and Defeo, 2013). Results indicated a decrease in biomass of 43% over this period and an MSY of 91430 tons. Furthermore, as noted in this study, the Argentine hake has a wide distribution beyond the area fished by the Uruguay and Argentine fleets as it is fished by other fleets and undertakes seasonal migrations. Thus, adequate stock assessment requires incorporating data from other fleets and areas where the Argentine hake is fished. According to Maguire et al. (2006, cited in Bensch et al. (2009) Argentine hake was considered overexploited or depleted, with signs of recovery in recent years.

For southern hake (*Merluccius australis*), which is mainly found south of 50°S, in the SW Atlantic and SE Pacific, Giussi and Zavatteri (2016) carried out a stock assessment using a statistical catch-at-age model for the period from 1986 to 2015, concluding that spawning stock biomass in 2015 was 30% of the spawning biomass in 1986, with a strong decrease in abundance in the initial years of the fishery.

According to Maguire et al. (2006, cited in Bensch et al. (2009), Argentine short-fin squid (*Illex argentinus*), was considered fully exploited. Chen and Chiu (2009) standardized catch per unit effort (CPUE) and reported an increasing trend in abundance from 1995 to 1999 and a subsequent sharp decline from 1999 to 2003. However, as with all short-lived species, environmentally driven recruitment variability plays a major role in the population dynamics of the short-fin squid. Wang et al. (2018) used an environmentally dependent surplus production model to evaluate the southern Patagonian stock of *I. argentinus* and estimated a MSY ranging from 351 600 to 685 100 t and a biomass of 1 322 400 to 1 803 000 t, with instantaneous fishing mortality (F) less than $F_{0.1}$ and F_{MSY} . According to Wang et al. (2018) the Argentine short-fin squid is not currently overfished.

Southern blue whiting (*Micromesistius australis*) was considered fully to overexploited (Maguire et al., 2006). These findings were supported by cohort analysis carried out for the 1987 to 1999 period by Wohler et al. (2002) who used catch data from the Argentinian and other fleets operating around the Malvinas Islands as well as data from Argentine-British surveys. Results indicated decreasing trends in biomass and recruitment and a spawning biomass of 34% of the virgin biomass. This species is also considered overexploited by FAO (2016).

By-catch species such as the Patagonian grenadier (*Macruronus magellanicus*), Patagonian squid (*Loligo* spp.) are considered fully exploited, pink cusk eel (*Genypterus blacodes*) is considered overexploited, while the status of other by-catch species such flying squid (*Martialia hyadesi*), tadpole mora (*Salilota australis*), grenadier (*Macrourus whitsoni*), Antarctic cod (*Notothenia rossii*), rockcods (*Notothenia* spp.), sharks and rays are not known (FAO, 2016).

2.3 Specific challenges in CS ASW

There are specific challenges that have been identified for the ASW case study, in regard to lack of level playing field for operators, data collection and insufficient monitoring, control and surveillance.

2.3.1 Lack of level playing field

A major management challenge is the lack of level-playing field where all operators should abide by the same rules. Currently, EU operators are obliged to stricter requirements and regulations (SMEFF Regulation (EU) 2017/2403) than other international fleets operating in the area (FarFish 2018f). Furthermore, in terms of non-fishing in Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems closed for Bottom Trawl Fishing activities to protect Deep-sea habitats, the EU fleets are bound by (EC) Council Regulation 734/2008 implementing the UNGA Resolutions 61/105 and 64/72.

2.3.2 Data availability

Another challenge is data availability, as the available fisheries data appears to be fragmented and not easily accessible (not public). Data holders include Argentinean and Falkland Islands national fisheries institutions as well as flag state distant-water fishing nations (FarFish D2.3). STECF notes that it is unclear if the stocks in international waters constitute separate stocks from those in Argentinian or Falkland Islands' waters, so efforts to improve stock identification are desirable (FarFish 2018e). STECF also notes that in order to provide informative advice, information from the fisheries exploiting this stock throughout its range is required and emphasizes the need for a multilateral approach for the assessment and management of the fisheries in the SW Atlantic (FarFish 2018e).

2.3.3 Insufficient control and monitoring in ASW

The fight against IUU fisheries is important for sustainable fisheries and to ensure a level playing field for all fleets. There is a need for improved monitoring in the area and even though many fleets transmit AIS/VMS data, recent investigations show that there are many gaps in AIS signals from these and other

vessels (<http://globalfishingwatch.org>)¹². EU vessels are obliged to transmit their position at all times with a satellite monitoring system (VMS) to their flag State.

Another compulsory monitoring system for vessels over 300 gross tons (GT) engaged on international voyages is the Automatic Identification System (AIS) which is shared real-time information of ship traffic. The AIS was intended to increase security at sea and support ship to ship collision avoidance, but as AIS transposes dynamic information such as ships position, course, speed, type of ship, navigational status in addition to IMO number, and the processed AIS data can provide insights and information for regulatory bodies and researchers. Tracking AIS signals may aid monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems. The IMO Convention for the Safety Of Life At Sea (SOLAS) Regulation V/19.2 requires vessels to operate AIS Class A on-board at all times, unless there are valid security reasons to turn it off, temporarily. In 2014, the European Commission required the entire fishery fleet >15 m to install AIS Class A transmitters (Shelmerdine, 2015). As AIS is an open source information system, the EU operators transmitting AIS are continuously monitored by their competitors. This can give them indications, based on their interpretation of the AIS positions over time, of where their fishing activity might take place. and experience a public exposure of their fishing activity. If non-EU fleets do not comply be the same rules, the level playing field is undermined.

¹² <http://globalfishingwatch.org/data/ais-gaps-by-fleet/>

3 Outcome targets and indicators

This chapter identifies the OTs and associated indicators established to provide measurable performance goals for the EU distant water fleet fishery fishing in the ASW. The OTs are classified as obligatory or recommended. They have a certain degree of flexibility to adapt to the realities and evolution of the defined CS throughout the life of the project. Only obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version of the MR, as they are considered important to reach the main objectives of the MR for this CS. The obligatory OTs for the ASW relate to the main challenges in the fishery in FAO subareas 41.3.1 and 41.3.2 listed above, where the EU fleet has landed mainly hake, longtail southern cod and Argentine shortfin squid in the recent years (Figure 3).

An OT is usually a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B'), but can also be a statement of presence or absence of some entity, in which a statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time. The indicator is a variable, pointer or an index related to a criterion. Its position and trend in relation to reference points (if available) or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. The indicators that relate to OTs should commonly be SMART, namely Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timely. An example of a biological/ecological indicator could be the fishing mortality (F): an example of economic indicator could be the EBITDA (Earnings before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization); and a social indicator could be the number of jobs created.

The suggested indicators in FarFish are set to measure the degree of adherence to the OTs (Table 2) and are classified according to their level of measurability. The most detailed indicator category A, is where the level of achievement of OT is quantitative, measured in percentage. Indicator category B is qualitative, where the level of OT achievement is considered to be high level (score level 4), moderate level (score 3), fair level (score 2), low level (score 1) or not present (score 0). The last indicator category is binomial, measured to have only two outcomes such as yes (score 1) or no (Score 0), true or false, success or failure.

3.1 Obligatory OTs in ASW and their indicators

Through "pre-invitation dialogues", both by remote and physical meetings, stakeholders have discussed management challenges and the management objectives were suggested by WP4 in MP0 with collaboration with Task 4.1 contributors within the consortium (FarFish, 2018a). Based on these objectives, WP3 identified OTs which are somewhat moderate and do not refer to an indicator value as commonly applied (FarFish, 2018d). Instead, the OT refer to statements of presence or absence of some entity which can be assessed to be either true or false at given point of time (Table 2).

During the process of identifying the appropriate OTs it has become apparent the operators cannot be made solely responsible for a number of OTs, meaning that different authorities will need to take on part of the responsibility to ensure successful implementation.

Table 2: FarFish indicator categories (A- quantitative, B- qualitative C-binomial) and the level of OT achievement

Indicator category	Level of OT achievement				
A	100%	75 %	50 %	25 %	0 %
B	High level (HL) 4	Moderate level (ML) 3	Fair Level (FL) 2	Low Level (LL) 1	Not present (NP) 0
C	Yes (true/success) 1				No (False/Failure) 0

3.1.1 Develop a soft-law mechanism [International Conference] focused on sustainable management in ABNJ (FAO 41) (OT 1.1)

Improving the level playing field will increase the sustainability of the fisheries in ABNJ (FAO 41). Following, this OT states that the EU operators are committed to help facilitate increased cooperation with other fishing fleets operating in FAO area 41, as well as other key stakeholders. The operators (EU) have limited control over the potential OT and cannot be made responsible for this OT other than their own participation, meaning that the authorities will need to take on part of the responsibility to ensure successful implementation.

3.1.2 Commitment to transmit AIS data (OT 1.2)

This OT relate to the monitoring of the transmission of AIS data by vessel exceeding 300 Gross tonnes, which are required to transmit such data. The EU fleet is already obliged to transmit AIS signals, so the OT is implemented in ASW by the EU fleet, i.e. in terms of VMS and/or AIS signals. There is however, a considerable amount of detected gaps in AIS signals in the area identified by GFW for both EU and Non-EU fleet. The reason for including this OTs is to put increased pressure on other international fleets operating in the area to comply with these restrictions as well. Within this case study there are multiple international fleets operating, therefore compliance of only one fleet will have limited effects

on the overall sustainability of this fishery; aside for highlighting a true interest in achieving sustainable and responsible fishing practices.

3.1.3 Set a theoretical frame for a Specific Control and Inspection Programme in FAO 41 as basis for a future pilot project on a joint deployment plan for this region (OT 1.3)

The idea behind this OT is, as a first step, to conceptually develop a regional Specific control and inspection programme (SCIP) for international fleets operating in ASW with the view of being implemented in a second step through a Joint Deployment Plan (JDP) of control means either within the lifetime or after the life of the project.

3.1.4 Both EU and Non-EU fleet comply with the VMEs in accordance with UNGA 61/105 and FAO Guidelines for Management of Deep-Sea Waters in the High Seas (OT 1.4)

This OT relate to the commitment to honour the VMEs for bottom trawlers based on scientific research and mapping in accordance with the Council Regulation (EC) No 734/2008 and thereby implementing a precautionary approach. This obligation is already being implemented by the EU fleet in line with (EC) Council Regulation No 734/2008. The reason for them being included as OTs is to make a comparative assessment of the reporting obligations among fleets and put increased pressure on responsibility of Flag States with fleets operating in the area to comply with these restrictions as well and thereby establish a level-playing field for EU and Non-EU fleet. Within this case study there are multiple international trawl fleets operating, therefore compliance of only one fleet (i.e. EU/Spain) will have limited effects on the overall sustainability of this fishery; aside for highlighting a true interest in achieving sustainable and responsible fishing practices.

Table 3: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets (OT) and indicators

Management goal	Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries	Initiate dialogue between stakeholders involved in fishery in FAO area 41 to support a level-playing field	OT 1.1 Develop a soft-law mechanism [e.g. Conference] focused on sustainable management of ABNJ (FAO41)	I_1_CS1: Number of invited stakeholders attending the Conference Indicator score: A I_2_CS1: Conference held Indicator score: C
Improved monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS)	Supporting enforcement by utilizing latest available satellite systems and tools	OT 1.2 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals	I_3_CS1: Operator compliance Indicator score: C
	Supporting the international cooperation on MCS	OT 1.3 Set a theoretical frame for a Specific Control and Inspection Programme in FAO 41 as basis for a future pilot project on a joint deployment plan for this region	I_4_CS1: Pilot Project launched Indicator score: C
Sustainable ecosystem	Protection of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems	OT 1.4 Both EU and non-EU fleet VMEs protection in accordance with UNGA 61/105 and FAO Guidelines for Management of Deep-Sea Waters in the High Seas	I_5_CS1: Operator compliance Indicator score: C

4 Management strategies and risks

4.1 Strategy and risk for achieving OT 1.1

Organizing an International Conference on sustainable management in the ASW will contribute to a structured dialogue among stakeholders operating in the area. The Conference is designed as a driver to facilitate further cooperation steps at international level and the agenda will include topics where common understanding could be easily developed, for instance in relation to scientific advances or priority topics such as the Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems.

A tangible output of the conference could be to come up with a joint publication. The conference will be useful to identify management and control measures within FAO 41 (particularly subareas 41.3.1 and 41.3.2). The output could be a document of good practices for sustainable management in the ASW". That document would be complementary to and in line with article 28 of the International Guidelines for the Management of Deep- Sea Fisheries in the High Seas (FAO Guidelines).

We could frame this conference around two main themes:

1. How stakeholders can contribute to improve international fisheries governance within SWA in the context of identifying and overcoming existing normative and implementation gaps in terms of conservation and management of the stocks to achieve a sustainable fishing. This can be put in context with the fulfilment of the 2030 Agenda of UN Sustainable Development Goals with specific mention to SDG14 (Life below water).
2. Showcase or highlight examples of best practices of EU capital companies or fishing investments in third countries to visible/promote the socio-economic benefits and the added value to local communities and food security that these companies bring to coastal states close to these fisheries, particularly in Argentina, Brazil and the Falklands.

FarFish will use the SWA case study meeting and other stakeholders' events to raise awareness of this OT and facilitate synergies within players in the fishery.

Main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this obligatory OT would be how to motivate main fisheries players in the area to get actively involved. Measures to minimize risk could be to embed the Conference in the current International Ocean Governance Agenda of the European Commission. For instance, the international Partnership for Regional Ocean Governance (PROG). PROG actions to date since 2015 have included support to Regional Sea Programmes in their efforts to strengthen ocean governance and to conserve and sustainably use the marine biodiversity in ABNJ.

4.2 Strategy and risk for achieving OT 1.2

Increased monitoring in ASW can be achieved by utilizing latest available satellite systems and tools. Global Fishing Watch¹³ (GFW) is collecting high spatial and temporal resolution data of fishing efforts worldwide through the use of AIS records obtained from communication satellite. Currently, the available data is aggregated, but companies like Marine Traffic¹⁴ can obtain information on individual vessels if paid for.

FarFish will support the progress of achieving this OT by developing big-Data analysis by Work Group 6 leader CSIC. GFW has acknowledged FarFish as a scientific collaborator and given FarFish access to their fishing effort data for the time period 2012-2016 (FarFish, 2018b).

Main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this obligatory OT would be related to data treatment and AIS data deteriorating in quality once the vessels are aware of the existence of GFW. If individual data is required, vessel may not be willing to pay for this information.

4.3 Strategy and risk for achieving OT 1.3

The conceptualisation and implementation of the SCIP could be facilitated by a pilot project for a joint deployment plan carried out by the European Fisheries Control Agency (EFCA). This body have already set up in their Annual and Multiannual Work Programmes several Specific Control and Inspection Programmes within EU waters and outside (e.g. NAFO and NEAFC) including a targeted risk based approach to MCS and operational joint control deployment plans for several fisheries on a regional basis (e.g. cod in North Western Waters or the Baltic). This pilot project can be developed building on the methodology and experience acquired by the European Fisheries Control Agency (EFCA) in the setting of their SCIPs/JDPs in international waters.

A similar SCIP/JDP could be developed for the target species for the EU fleet, i.e. Argentinian Hake (*Merluccius hubbsi*) and Shortfin Squid (*Illex Argentinus*). EFCA has also developed training courses for inspectors and manuals.

FarFish will approach this OT by developing a proposal in this direction in a forthcoming meeting. FarFish partner LDAC is an active member of the EFCA Advisory Board and will assist in formalising this proposal.

¹³ <https://globalfishingwatch.org/>

¹⁴ www.marinetraffic.com

Main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this obligatory OT is the challenge that EFCA needs a specific mandate by DG MARE/European Commission and the subsequent endorsement by the EFCA Administrative Board (EU member states) to go ahead and allocate time and resources for such task.

4.4 Strategy and risk for achieving OT 1.4

To achieve this OT, increased monitoring in VME areas by analysing AIS data provided by GFW, could be a useful tool to monitor VME avoidance by vessels >300 GT, and to detect gaps in AIS signals taking into account technical issues related to transmission of signals.

FarFish will support the progress of achieving this OT by exploring ideas on monitoring of fisheries in VMEs applying new methods and tools.

Main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this obligatory OT would be related to adaptive planning and to data treatment and AIS data deteriorating in quality or deliberately turned off once the vessels are aware of the existence of GFW.

4.5 Internal monitoring

The internal monitoring of development of these OTs will be to follow up on the progress of the OTs, but simulation studies are not within the scope of this CS. The following institutions are suggested to take the responsibility for the OTs:

- OT 1.1 FAO Common Oceans ABNJ Program is suggested as a suitable actor for achieving the OT.
- OT 1.2 Joint Argentinean-Uruguay Technical Commission of the Maritime Front (CTMFM) is suggested as responsible for achieving the OT.
- OT 1.3 European Fisheries Control Agency in collaboration with CTMFM is suggested as a suitable actor for achieving the OT.
- OT 1.4 2 Joint Argentinean-Uruguay Technical Commission of the Maritime Front (CTMFM) is suggested as responsible for achieving the OT

5 Monitoring, compliance and sanctions

Most of the OT defined within this CS, require a commitment from other players, since the current operators have limited control over its. Therefore the responsibility cannot be established only between two actors, operators and authorities; the responsibility will be shared between different players which may play a better role to improve fisheries management within the SWA (Table 4).

The monitoring of the OTs in this MR will rely on monitoring by satellite systems (OT 1.2, OT1.4), list of invited/participated operators (OT1.1), tentative meeting agenda, list of potential training courses for inspectors and manuals already developed by EFCA should be provided (OT 1.3). A few issues related to the ASW are identified and should be monitored by suggested institutions (Table 4).

Table 4: Monitoring instruments and potential responsible

OT	Issues	Responsible
1.1	Organizing committee	FAO Common Oceans ABNJ Program
1.2	AIS signals	Global Fishing Watch
1.3	Training of inspectors and manuals	European Fisheries Control Agency
1.4	Compliance of VMEs	Global Fishing Watch

6 Documentation

A documentation system will be developed, describing how reliable and accurate information will be collected and provided to the auditor.

Suggested documentation;

- List of invited participants (OT 1.1)
- List of participants (OT 1.1)
- Conference agenda (OT1.1)
- List of events linked to Ocean Governance Agenda (EC), particularly on the international Partnership for Regional Ocean Governance Programme (OT 1.1)
- List of gaps in AIS signals (OT 1.2)
- List of potential training courses for inspectors and manuals already developed by EFCA (OT 1.3)
- Technical reports of fishing activity in VMEs (OT 1.4)

7 Auditor

FarFish partner Syntesa will audit the RFMS process and implementation process and has agreed to this at the initial stage of FarFish. It is however possible to seek different auditors if necessary.

8 Planning process

The development of MRs depend on input from other Work packages and this first version is supported by the Case study characterization (FarFish 2017), Management Plan Zero (FarFish, 2018a), Developments needed to produce relevant management tools (FarFish, 2018b), Draft 1 General Guidelines for making MPRs (FarFish, 2018c), First MR invitations (FarFish, 2018d), Report from MPR Kick-off meeting (FarFish, 2018e), Evaluation of governance structures of the cases (FarFish, 2018 f), Stakeholders hub (FarFish 2018g), Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 1 (FarFish, 2018h), Visualization materials and tools for MPR1 (FarFish, 2018i) and Description of CS value chains (FarFish, 2019).

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SOUTHEAST ATLANTIC CASE STUDY

Deliverable No. 4.3

Project acronym:

FarFish

Project title:

Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

Grant agreement No: **727891**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme

Start date of project: **1st June 2017**

Duration: **48 months**

Due date of deliverable:	31/01/2019
Submission date:	23/09/2020
File Name:	FarFish D4.3_MR1 Southeast Atlantic
Revision number:	02
Document status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public

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Deliverable D4.3

Management Recommendation 1

Southeast Atlantic

23/09/2020

Executive Summary

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) for international mixed fishery in FAO Area 47, mainly in subareas B1 and D1. The South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation (SEAFO), manages the fisheries in this area. The MR1 follows the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish [D3.1](#)) and is based on the Management Recommendation Invitation (FarFish [D3.2](#)), where the outcome targets (OTs) were proposed. The identified OTs are based on input from stakeholders and authorities who identified challenges and management objectives in the Management Recommendation zero (FarFish [D4.1](#)) and at the MR-Kick-off meeting held in Vigo in June 2018 (FarFish [D4.2](#)).

FarFish partner MATIS, will act as the leading authority, whilst considering input from the SEAFO, which is considered the competent authority in this case study. There has been a very limited fishery in the SEAFO convention area in the recent years. Therefore, FarFish partners from NOFIMA in collaboration with case study leader IMR are acting as operators in this FarFish case study, assisted by UiT the FarFish WP4 leader.

Due to the low fishing effort in this case study, the aim of this MR is more “theoretical” and aiming at serving good practice recommendations, focusing on improving monitoring for sustainable fisheries in the SEAFO convention area on fisheries managed by SEAFO. The identified OTs are classified to the governance dimension. FarFish acknowledges that the operators or the institutions acting as operators cannot be made solely responsible for achieving the OTs in this CS. It must therefore be a joint effort between authorities and operators. Indicators are suggested to measure the performance of the OTs and the strategy for achieving the OTs is outlined.

Two obligatory and one recommended OTs are proposed for this case study and only the obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version of the MR. The first OT relate to improvement of the scientific knowledge base by suggesting mandatory reporting of all catches in e logbooks. The proposed strategy includes the development of a pilot project where a dialogue meeting between one contracting party and SEAFO is initiated. The second OT is related to monitoring of fishing activity by satellite systems, as vessels are obliged to transmit both VMS and AIS signals in the SEAFO contracting area. The focus of this OT is supporting SEAFO strategy for Monitoring, Control and Surveillance, which are integrated in the “SEAFO System”. Improved monitoring ads to the prevention of IUU fisheries. The strategy for this OT includes big data analysis of Global Fishing Watch fishing effort data for the period from 2012 to 2017.

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Abbreviations

ABNJ	Areas Beyond National jurisdiction
AIS	Automatic Identification System
Bmsy	Maximum Sustainable Yield Biomass
CA	Convention Area
CCMAR	Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal)
CETMAR	Centro Tecnológico del mar Fundacion (Spain)
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CPUE	Catch per Unit Effort
CS	Case Study
CSIC	Spanish National Research Council (Spain)
DG MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (EU)
DLM	Data Limited Method
DWF	Distant Water Fleet
EBAFM	Ecosystem Based Approach to Fisheries Management
EC	European commission
EcoFishMan	Ecosystem-based Responsive Fisheries Management in Europe
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
ERS	Electronic Recording Systems
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FarFish RG	FarFish Reference Group
FMC	Fisheries Monitoring Centre
GFW	Global Fishing Watch, NGO
HCR	Harvest control rule
HS	High seas
ICMAN-CSIC	Institute for Marine Sciences of Andalucía (ICMAN)-Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) (Spain)
IMO	International Maritime Organization
IMR	Institute of Marine Research
ITLOS	International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea
IUU	Illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing
LDAC	EU Long Distance Fleet Advisory Council
MATIS OHF	Icelandic Food and Biotech R & D Institute (Iceland)
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance
MFMR	Ministry of Fisheries and Marine Resources (Namibia)
MR	Management Recommendation
MSY	Maximum sustainable Yield
NAFO	North Atlantic Fisheries Organization
NOFIMA	The Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture research (Norway)
OECD	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OT	Outcome Target

RBM	Results-Based Management
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
RFMS	Responsible Fisheries Management System
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SDG 12	Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns
SDG 14	Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development
SEAFO	South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation
SOLAs	Safety Of Life At Sea
SYN	SP/F SYNTESA (Faroe Islands)
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
UIT	The Arctic University of Norway (Norway)
UN	United Nations
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNGA	United Nations General Assembly
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System
WP	Work Package
WWF	Worldwide fund for nature

Concepts/definitions

Indicator	A variable, pointer or index related to a criterion. Indicators are selected such that their variations reflect variations in key elements of the fishery resource, the social and economic well-being of the sector and the sustainability of the ecosystem. The position and trend of an indicator in relation to reference points or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. Indicators provide a bridge between objectives and actions (source: FAO 1999).
Management goals	The higher-order objective to which a management intervention is intended to contribute (OECD 2011). A management goal is derived from a management principle (constitutional-order) and is specified into a set of more operational management objectives (collective-order).
Management intervention	Strategies or instruments aimed to impact the state of a fishery with reference to authorized objectives. Examples are input and output controls and economic measures.
Management measures	Can be technical (e.g. gear selectivity etc.), input (effort)/output (catch) control, right based.
Management objectives	Fisheries management objectives are typically framed within the overall concept of sustainable development, and may reflect one or more of the various dimensions and criteria that relate to it (FAO 1999). Operators through setting and implementing management measures control OTs.
Management Plan (MP)	A fisheries management plan is a formal arrangement between a fishery management authority and interested parties which identifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, details the agreed objectives for the fishery and specifies the management rules and regulations which apply to it and provides other details about the fishery which are relevant to the task of the management authority (Source: FAO 2002).
Management Recommendation (MR)	In RFMS, the management recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority and operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery. In RFMS, the formal responsibility for developing the management plan is delegated to an operator.
Management strategies	In FarFish context, it means the strategies applied to achieve OTs
Outcome Target (OT)	Outcome targets (OTs) are specific and measurable requirements that are set by an authority to make management goals operational. An OT is a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B') or a statement of presence or absence of some entity. On the basis of relevant information, this statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time ⁵⁴ . For instance, the management objective that "the fishery should be biologically sustainable" could be expressed in terms of one or more OTs such as 'Catch < 20 000t; 'bycatch < 20%'; SSB > 30 000t; 'a catch reporting system is present', etc.
Reference point	A classification device, defined in relation to the measure of an indicator, for distinguishing different management relevant states of the system under management. A Biological Reference Point is a metric of stock status. A Target Reference Point indicates a state of a system which is considered desirable and at which management action should aim. A Limit Reference Point indicates a state of a system, which is considered to be undesirable, that one therefore should seek to avoid through relevant management action.
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) is a fisheries management approach developed within the FP7 project EcoFishMan . The RFMS is an adaptive management approach that is results-based and ecosystem-based. The RFMS attempts to reduce micromanagement by involving stakeholders and increase the degree of co-management by delegating management responsibilities to resource users.

1 Introduction

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) from European operators with an interest in fisheries managed by South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation (SEAFO) in FAO Area 47, mainly in the subareas 47.B1 and 47.D1. The MR1 is founded on Results-Based Management (RBM) principles and based on the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) approach (Figure 1), which was developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan (Silva et al., 2015, Santiago et al., 2015, Nielsen et al., 2018). The MR is an agreement between competent authorities and relevant operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery. In the MR, strategies are defined in order to achieve the outcome targets (OTs). The OTs are established by the authorities in the MR Invitation to support sustainable fisheries (FarFish, 2018a), while taking into account the management objectives and challenges emphasized by authorities in the Management Recommendation zero (FarFish, 2018b), and following the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2018c).

Figure 1: The RFMS process. The responsibilities of each of the three entities are demonstrated with different colours. Authority: red/Operators: blue/ Auditors: yellow (FarFish, 2018c).

The authority is the organizational entity acting as the authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery (e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission). They oversee the RFMS process and issue the “MR invitation”, which includes a clear specification of measurable OTs, set in order to operationalize the goals of existing policies and the local management objectives.

The operator is defined as an organized group of resource users, e.g. an association of fishermen or stakeholders with rights in a given fishery. It is the organizational unit with delegated authority to develop management recommendations based on the OTs set by the authority and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority. In line with the RFMS approach, the engagement of stakeholders is highly prioritized in FarFish. Nevertheless, given the limited fishing activity of the EU fleet in the SEAFO area, any responsibility that is put on their shoulders within the RFMS process, depends on whether EU fishing activities will occur in the area over the

coming years. This is taken into account when identifying OTs for the case study, as the roles and responsibilities set within the FarFish RFMS framework does not initially apply to the other distant water fleets operating in the area (FarFish, 2018a).

1.1 Partners involved in MR1 in the SEAFO area

The leader of Task 3.3 (Authority role within RFMS) in FarFish, MATIS, acts as the leading authority, whilst considering input from the relevant authorities, e.g. SEAFO, coastal states and DG Mare (Table 1). As there has been no fishing activity by European flagged vessels in the SEAFO area in recent years, this MR1 will be more theoretical, and developed by WP4 acting as operators, led by WP4 with major involvement from the task contributors, NOFIMA, IMR and UCAM. WP4 will also consider input from relevant operators, e.g. LDAC (FarFish, 2018a). The audit will be conducted by the auditor, in this case Work Package 5 lead by Syntesa. They will evaluate the MR1 and provide the audit of the MR1 once approved by both operators and authorities.

Table 1: MR1 SE Atlantic, partners involved, geographical range, target species, main aims and period

MR basis	MR1 Senegal		
Partners involved	Authorities: WP3 (MATIS), SEAFO, DG MARE		
	Operators: WP4, WP3 (NOFIMA), CS LEADER IMR		
	Auditor: WP5, SYNTESA		
Target species	Common name	Scientific name	FAO code
	Alfonsino	<i>Beryx splendens</i>	BYS
	Boarfish/pelagic armourhead	<i>Pseudopentaceros richardsoni</i>	EDR
	Orange roughy	<i>Hoplostethus atlanticus</i>	ORY
	Deep-sea crab	<i>Chaceon erytheiae</i>	KEF
	Patagonian toothfish	<i>Dissostichus eleginoides</i>	TOP
Geographical range	High seas FAO area 47 (all subareas), depths <2000 m		
Fleets	EU fleet: Spain (historically also Portugal, Poland and Cyprus) Other fleets: Japan, Namibia, South Africa (historically also Republic of Korea and Norway)		
Main aims of MR	Improve monitoring for sustainable fisheries, by introducing e-logbooks, strengthening the use of VMS/AIS and observers on board		
MR planning period	Lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021)		

1.2 Aims of MR1 for the southeast

This MR1 applies to the fishery in the SEAFO area (Figure 2Figure). The aim of this MR is to serve good practice recommendations, focusing on improved monitoring for sustainable fisheries in the SEAFO convention area to support maintenance of international framework for future use and protection. The SEAFO is a modern and well-functioning RFMO, operating in an area with limited capacity of coastal states and managing fisheries on poor data stocks. SEAFO has in place a well-developed

monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) system. The management of the SEAFO fisheries is therefore well suited to function as a showcase and illustrate good practice recommendations, committing both authorities and operators.

Figure 2: Maps of SEAFO area and the FAO area 47. Source: www.seafo.org

1.3 Current legislative situation in high seas fisheries in Southeast Atlantic high seas

The scope of the MR comprises marine areas beyond national jurisdiction (ABNJ) in FAO area 47, focusing on the fishery governed by SEAFO (Figure 2). This is a non-tuna RFMO established in April 2001. Contracting parties to SEAFO are Angola, the European Union, Japan, Namibia, Norway, South Africa and South Korea. The Secretariat is based in Swakopmund, Namibia, with a staff of two, an executive secretary (ES) and a data and administrative office manager. The coastal states that border the SEAFO area are Angola, Namibia and South Africa, in addition to the United Kingdom on behalf of St. Helena and its dependencies, Tristan da Cunha and Ascension Island that are not party to SEAFO (their EEZs are marked with circles in Figure 2).

SEAFO is a relatively young RFMO, with the Convention entering into force in 2003. It is one of the first RFMOs modelled on the UN Fish Stocks Agreement, including general principles for good fishing management like the precautionary and ecosystem approaches. There are management measures in place for 5 target species (Patagonian toothfish, deep-sea red crab, alfonsino, orange roughy and pelagic armourhead), in addition to by-catch measures and measures to protect VME through establishment of closed areas for bottom fishing and procedures to explore new fisheries in the SEAFO Convention Area (CA).

SEAFO has developed a comprehensive strategy for MCS of the fisheries in the SEAFO CA. These are integrated into the so-called “SEAFO System” – the System of observation, inspection, compliance and enforcement, which are handled by the Compliance Committee. ‘The System’ contains all the SEAFO measures to ensure compliance with SEAFO regulations, including requirements for inspection at sea and in port, for monitoring and reporting requirements, and how to handle infringements (SEAFO, 2018a). According to the SEAFO System vessels fishing in the Convention area are obliged to i) record their fishing activity and onboard production in appropriate logbooks (Article 10), ii) be equipped with a VLD that automatically and continuously sends VMS data to relevant FMC (Article 13), and iii) have scientific observers onboard (Article 18). ‘The System’ is updated annually, and in 2018 the document comprised 49 pages, clearly outlining reporting guidelines, and obligations pertaining to fishing vessel as well as research vessel activity and inspection of vessels fishing in the Convention area (SEAFO, 2018a).

The international community has since 2004 made significant progresses to promote the sustainable management of fisheries resources in the ABNJ mainly through both hard and soft law instruments. For instance, UN resolutions 59/25 and 61/105, which are binding for CPCs to implement, but difficult to enforce, or the set of FAO (non-binding) International Guidelines for the Management of Deep-Sea Fisheries in the High Seas. Soft law refers to quasi-legal instruments that include hortatory, rather than legally binding, obligations (Guzman and Meyer, 2010). Soft law instruments are considered as a flexible tool of compromise that can ease bargaining problems and open up mutually preferred compromises (Abbott and Snidal, 2000).

The UNGA Resolutions 61/105¹⁵ and the FAO International Guidelines for the Management of Deep-Sea Fisheries in the High Seas (FAO, 2009)¹⁶ were implemented by (EC) Council Regulation 734/2008¹⁷. The European Union has also established a system concerning fishing activities of Union fishing vessels fishing outside Union waters on the high seas¹⁸. EU's reformed Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), which came into effect in January 2014, state that all EU fishing activities, inside and outside EU waters, are subject to the same environmental and other standards (EC 2013). Thus, the EU must conduct its external fleet in accordance with the objectives and principles set out in Articles 2 and 3 of the CFP. According to Article 2, those objectives include the application and promotion of the precautionary approach to ensure that the stocks targeted are at higher levels that deliver MSY by 2020 at the latest, the application of the ecosystem principle, the promotion of the collection of scientific data and the gradual elimination of discards (FarFish, D1.1).

¹⁵ https://www.un.org/Depts/los/general_assembly/general_assembly_resolutions.htm

¹⁶ <http://www.fao.org/3/i0816t/i0816t00.htm>

¹⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32008R0734>

¹⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32017R2403>

The main objective of the CFP is to ensure that fishing activities are environmentally, economically and socially sustainable and are managed consistently with the objectives of achieving economic, social and employment benefits, and of restoring and maintaining fish stocks above levels which can produce maximum sustainable yield and that they are contributing to the availability of food supplies. The CFP stresses the need to promote the objectives of CFP internationally, ensuring that Union-fishing activities outside Union waters are based on the same principles and standards as those applicable under Union law, while promoting a level playing field for Union operators and third-country operators. Additionally, the union has committed itself to Sustainable Development Goal 14¹⁹ (SDG 14) and Sustainable Development Goal 12²⁰ (SDG 12).

Relevant target goals in SDG 14 are:

- 14.2 By 2020, effectively regulate harvesting and end overfishing, illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing and destructive fishing practise and implement science-based management plans, in order to restore fish stocks in the shortest time feasible, at least to levels that can produce maximum sustainable yields as determined by their biological characteristics.
- 14.A Increase scientific knowledge, develop research capacity and transfer marine technology, taking into account the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission Criteria and Guidelines on the Transfer of Marine Technology, in order to improve ocean health and to enhance the contribution of marine biodiversity to the development of developing countries, in particular small island developing States and least developed countries.

Relevant target goals in SDG 12 are:

- 12.2 By 2030, achieve the sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources
- 12.3 By 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses.
- 12.6 Encourage companies, especially large and transnational companies, to adopt sustainable practices and to integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle.
- 12.A Support developing countries to strengthen their scientific and technological capacity to move towards more sustainable patterns of consumption and production.

The Automatic Identification System (AIS) is a compulsory monitoring system for vessels over 300 gross tons (GT) engaged on international voyages and shares real-time information of ship traffic. The AIS was developed to increase security at sea and support ship to ship collision avoidance and the IMO Convention for the Safety Of Life At Sea (SOLAS) Regulation V/19.2 requires vessels to operate AIS Class A on-board at all times, unless there are valid security reasons to turn it off, temporarily. However, as AIS transposes dynamic information such as ships position, course, speed, type of ship,

¹⁹ SDG14: conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

²⁰ SDG12: ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns and their targets

navigational status in addition to IMO number, the processed AIS data can provide insights and information for regulatory bodies and researchers. Tracking AIS signals may aid monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems.

1.4 Identity of Fishery in the Southeast Atlantic high seas

The SEAFO list of species includes 93 species, including crustaceans, cephalopods, bony and cartilaginous fish²¹.

Of these, the main targeted species and their geographical target areas are:

- Patagonian toothfish (actively targeted since at least 2002), concentrated over seamounts in Sub Area D (Western - and Discovery seamounts) and in D1 (Meteor seamounts).
- Orange roughy (no reported catches since 2005), mainly targeted around Ewing seamount and Valdivia Bank on the Walvis Ridge in Division B1.
- Deep-sea crab (active fishery since at least 2001), mainly targeted around Valdivia Bank in Division B1.
- Pelagic armourhead (no significant catches reported since 2003), mainly targeted by Korean trawlers in southern and northern part of Valdivia Bank, Division B1.
- Alfonsino, three main fishing grounds in B1.

²¹http://www.seafo.org/media/336844cc-5169-409a-a565-49b547a01679/SEAFOweb/pdf/COMM/seafo%20species%20list%20_2_.pdf

2 Fishery overview

The SEAFO CA in ABNJ is a deep, large area with several seamount chains, isolated seamounts, guyots and banks (FarFish, 2017). All fishing in SEAFO occurs on or around seamounts. The main target species include alfonsino (*Beryx splendens*), boarfish/pelagic armourhead (*Pseudopentaceros richardsoni*), orange roughy (*Hoplostethus atlanticus*), deep-sea crab (*Chaceon erytheiae*), and Patagonian toothfish (*Dissostichus eleginoides*). All bycatch, regardless of fishing gear, is recorded in fishing logbook and observers' forms. For the main by-catch species recorded in the period 1995-2018, which include oreo dories, wreckfish, blackbelly rosefish, imperial blackfish, silver scabbardfish, oilfish, grenadiers, and king crab, total annual catches of each of the species in the period 2012-2018 were generally less than 1 ton.

2.1 Recent trends- EU catch statistics and EU fleet

With regard to the SEAFO main target species, the area has seen limited fishing activities in recent years and in 2018 only two vessels from Japanese and Namibia were active (Table 2, SEAFO, 2018b). The vessels reported catches for Patagonian tooth fish in D1 and deep-sea red crab in B1, respectively. In 2017, only two of the five Spanish vessels with authorization²² to fish in SEAFO showed some activity (Table 2), but no reported catches. Other fleets operating in the SEAFO CA in 2017 were Japan and Namibia (FarFish, 2018, D3.2). All vessels fishing in the SEAFO CA must register and currently there are 19 vessels authorized to fish in the SEAFO CA.

²² <http://www.seafo.org/Management/Authorized-Vessel-List>

Table 2: Number of Parties and Vessels Actively Fishing in the SEAFO CS from 2005 to 2018. Source: SEAFO 2018b.

Year	Non Contracting Party	Contracting Party	Number of Vessels
2005	1		2
2006	1		1
2007	1	1	4
2008	2		4
2009	2		4
2010	2	2	4
2011	1	4	5
2012		4	4
2013		3	3
2014		2	2
2015		2	2
2016		1	1
2017		2	4
2018		2	2

In the time period from 2005 to 2018, the fishing effort measured by total number of fishing days and number of sets (pot, longline and trawl) peaked in 2011-2012 and was lowest in 2016. After 2016, both number of sets and fishing days have been increasing slightly again (SEAFO, 2018b). According to the SEAFO 14th Scientific Committee Meeting Report (SEAFO, 2018c) the only targeted species in 2017 were Patagonian toothfish (Japan; 12 tons), alfonsino (Namibia, <1 tons), deep-sea crab (Japan, 140 tons; Namibia, 7 tons) and pelagic armourhead (Namibia, <1) (Figure 3 & Figure 4). The total landings of species not included in the SEAFO species list, and not managed by SEAFO, are shown in Figure 5 for the period 2008-2016. The main species contributing to the total catch, taken largely by Spain and Portugal, were the pelagic sharks like the blue shark and the Mako shark.

Figure 3: SEAFO fleet activity in FAO 47 showing total catches (tons) of the main target species for the period 2000-2018. Source: www.seafo.org

2.2 Stock status of target species

A summary of the status of the five main target species is provided in Table 3. For most species, the assessment of the stock is limited to trends in CPUE. The status of alfonsino and pelagic armourhead is unknown, for orange roughy and Patagonian toothfish assumed stable, and for deep-sea crab, a negative CPUE trend is observed, indicating that the resource is overexploited. Biological reference points are not available for any of the species, while harvest control rules (HCRs) are available for some of the species.

Figure 4: Annual catch of TAC species in tonnes from 2010 to 2018 (Nov). Species identified include alfonsino, deep-sea red crab, Patagonian toothfish and pelagic armourhead. Source: SEAFO, 2018b.

Figure 5: Total landings in FAO 47, including species not managed by SEAFO. Source: www.seafo.org

Table 3: Summary of available stock information for the five main target species in SEAFO

Target species	Assessment	Reference point	Status	TAC 2019-2020	Division
Orange roughy	CPUE trend based on 1995-2005 time series.	- No biological ref. points - No HCR	Stable CPUE until 2005	- Zero, with 4t bycatch - 50t	B1 Remainder of SEAFO CA
Alfonsino	CPUE trend based on 2010-2012 data	-No biological ref. points - ICES HCR for cat 5 stocks	Unknown	- 200t - max 132t	SEAFO CA B1
Pelagic armourhead	CPUE data (2010-2013) combined with a depletion model	- No biological ref. points MSY = 128 t HCR in place	Unknown	- 135t	Not specified
Patagonian toothfish	Y/R analysis, length cohort analysis and ASPIC	- No biological ref. points - HCR in place (same as Gr. Halibut in NAFO)	F is likely below F_{MSY}	- 275t	D
Deep sea red crab	Standardized CPUE trend	- No biological ref. points - HCR in place (same as Gr. Halibut in NAFO)	Negative trend in CPUE	- 171t - 200t	B1 Remainder of SEAFO CA

2.3 Specific challenges in Southeast Atlantic case study

2.3.1 Data availability

Biological- and catch data is available via the SEAFO secretariat only by request. Catch data is considered to be well documented, but are sometimes submitted beyond the reporting date specified in the SEAFO system (SEAFO, 2018d). Although no reports of IUU fishing vessels were reported in 2018, there was one IUU vessel, which caught 101 tonnes of Patagonian toothfish in the SEAFO CA in 2016 according to the Executive Secretary of SEAFO (SEAFO, 2018c). Total Allowable Catch (TAC) is therefore based on limited data, especially when fishing activity is low and when IUU fishing occurs (FarFish, 2017).

2.3.2 Insufficient monitoring of the fishery

The challenge for the MCS of the SEAFO fisheries is related to capacity to physically control vessels at sea and in port. The fight against IUU fisheries is important for sustainable fisheries and initiates a level playing field for all fleets. Vessels are obliged to transmit their position at all times with a satellite vessel monitoring system (VMS) to their flag State, which should provide the requested VMS data to SEAFO, but some countries have problems with VMS requirements described in the SEAFO 'SYSTEM' (SEAFO, 2018b). Although many fleets transmit AIS, recent investigations by Global Fishing Watch (GFW) show that there are gaps in AIS signals from other vessels operating in international waters (<http://globalfishingwatch.org>)²⁴. Gaps in AIS signals can occur due to gap in signal coverage, signal inference in crowded areas etc.

The EU fleet is obliged also by EU regulation to transmit both VMS and AIS signals. As AIS is an open source information system, their competitors continuously monitor the EU operators transmitting AIS. This can give them indications, based on their interpretation of the AIS positions over time, of where their fishing activity might take place and experience a public exposure of their fishing activity. If non-EU fleets do not comply were the same rules, the level playing field is undermined.

²⁴ <http://globalfishingwatch.org/data/ais-gaps-by-fleet/>

3 Outcome targets and indicators

This chapter identifies the outcome targets and associated indicators established to provide measurable performance goals for the fishery of SEAFO species in the SEAFO CA. The OTs are classified as obligatory or recommended. This MR will address only the obligatory outcome targets, while the recommended OT is briefly treated at the draft stage and will be properly addressed in the second version of the MR.

An OT is usually a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B'), but can also be a statement of presence or absence of some entity, in which a statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time. The indicator is a variable, pointer or an index related to a criterion. Its position and trend in relation to reference points (if available) or values indicate the present state and dynamics of 'The System'. The indicators that relate to OTs should commonly be SMART, namely Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timely.

The suggested indicators in FarFish are set to measure the degree of adherence to the OT (Table 4) and are classified according to their level of measurability. The most detailed indicator category A is where the level of achievement of OT is quantitative, measured in percentage. Indicator category B is qualitative, where the level of OT achievement is considered to be high level (score level 4), moderate level (score 3), fair level (score 2), low level (score 1) or not present (score 0). The last indicator category is binomial, measured to have only two outcomes such as yes (score 1) or no (Score 0), true or false, success or failure.

Table 4: FarFish indicator categories (A- quantitative, B- qualitative C-binomial) and the level of OT achievement

Indicator category	Level of OT achievement				
A	100%	75 %	50 %	25 %	0 %
B	High level (HL) 4	Moderate level (ML) 3	Fair Level (FL) 2	Low Level (LL) 1	Not present (NP) 0
C	Yes (true/success) 1				No (False/Failure) 0

3.1 Obligatory OTs and their indicators

The background within this case study, with very limited activity in the area, make policy objectives and jurisdiction of limited relevance in the context of the RFMS in this case study. Given the nature of the case study, expectations towards the case study MR must be realistic and take the limited operations of the EU fishing fleet into consideration (FarFish, 2018a). The OTs identified in the MR invitation are therefore on a more “theoretical” level and serve as “good practice” recommendations

The obligation involved in OTs identified here, are already being implemented for the EU fleet, i.e. in terms of VMS/AIS signals and reporting of all catches via e-logbooks. The reason for them being included as OTs is to put increased pressure on other international fleets operating in the area to improve data collection for an improved monitoring and data collection in the area.

3.1.1 OT 2.1 Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks

The SEAFO system requires that all authorised vessels fishing in the area submit logbook data to the SEAFO secretariat within 30 days of leaving the convention area. There are three different logbooks, depending on which gear is applied (1) SEAFO Logbook Form 2015- Longline, (2) SEAFO Logbook Form 2015 Pot and (3) SEAFO Logbook Form 2015 –Trawl. They also have to send an entry report to the secretariat 6 hours in advance of entry, information on 5-day catch every 5 day during the fishing operation, and an exit report 6 hours in advance of leaving the convention areas. Finally, quarterly aggregated catch reports are to be submitted to the secretariat. SEAFO does not have an electronic e-logbook system in place, and the most recent reporting obligation by SEAFO from three. June 2019, does not specify the reporting method²⁵ other than providing the SEAFO Logbook Forms.

E-logbook contribute to better monitoring, as these systems can collect and transmit some data automatically at set time intervals or in near real time. When used along with vessel tracking tools, e-logbooks can help reduce misreporting at the point of harvest (Lewis and Boyle, 2017) and thereby support SDG 14, target 14.2 to fight IUU fisheries. Also, the requirement in the UNFSA to ensure the “timely collection, compilation and analysis of data” for effective fisheries conservation and management underscores the need to explore the implementation of e-logbooks. Finally, EU vessels are obliged under the CFP, Control Regulation 1224/2009 to submit catch data to their flag state by e-logbooks. This is the basis for OT 2.1 as formulated in the MR Invitation (FarFish, 2018a):

OT 2.1: Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks.

²⁵http://www.seafo.org/media/3f2ec752-fda5-45ee-b7d3-cbc757d4c8a9/SEAFOweb/pdf/Reporting%20Obligations/Reporting%20Obligations%202019_pdf

In order to measure the performance of OT 2.1, these indicators are suggested (Table 5 and Table 6):

I_1_CS2: Develop a pilot project to introduce e logbooks for developing countries.

I_2_CS2: Dialogue meeting between SEAFO and a contracting party defined as a developing country.

3.1.2 OT 2.2 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals

All authorized vessels fishing in the SEAFO area are obliged to transmit VMS data its flag state Fisheries Monitoring Centre (FMC) every two hours and allow for continuous tracking of the vessel by the flag state (SEAFO, 2018a). The flag state shall provide a copy of the reports in accordance with the 'SEAFO SYSTEM' regulations to SEAFO secretariat no later than 24 hours after receipts (SEAFO, 2018a).

Transmission of AIS data is not called for by SEAFO, but transmission of AIS to flag state by vessels over 300 gross tons (GT) engaged on international voyages is compulsory. The EU vessels are obliged to transmit VMS to their position to the flag state at all times and after 2014, the European Commission required the entire fishery fleet >15 m to install AIS Class A transmitters (Shelmerdine, 2015)

The reason for including this OTs is to support the maintenance of an international framework for future use and protection. All international fleets operating in the area must comply with the SEAFO regulations, highlighting a true interest in achieving sustainable and responsible fishing practices.

This OT relate to the transmission of AIS/VMS data. Although vessels are obliged to transmit both AIS and VMS data, Global Fishing Watch (GFW) has identified gaps in AIS signals, and a few Contracting Parties in SEAFO have challenges with compliance of VMS requirements by SEAFO (SEAFO, 2018e). Within a case study there is a potential for multiple international fleets operating, therefore compliance of only one fleet will have limited effects on the overall sustainability of this fishery. This is the basis for OT 2.1 as formulated in the MR Invitation (FarFish, 2018a):

OT 2.2: Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals.
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In order to measure the performance of OT 2.3, the following indicator is suggested (Table 5 and Table 6):

I_3_CS2: Proportion of vessels geolocated.

I_4_CS2: Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation.

Table 5: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome Targets and their indicators

Management goal	Management objective	Outcome target	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries based on the best scientific advice.	Improve the knowledge base for sustainable fisheries management.	OT2.1: Reporting of all catches via e-logbooks. OT Dimension: Governance.	I_1_CS2: Develop a pilot project to introduce e logbooks.
			I_2_CS2: Initiate a dialogue meeting between SEAFO and contracting party defined as a developing country.
Sustainable fisheries by supporting the fight against IUU fisheries.	Improve monitoring and control.	OT2.2: Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals. OT Dimension: Governance.	I_3_CS2 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocated.
			I_4_CS2 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation.

Table 6: Summary of Indicators, their category, baseline and the entity responsible

Outcome target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator category	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 2.1	I_1_CS2: Develop a pilot project to introduce e logbooks.	C	0	Authority, Task 4.3 contributors.
	I_2_CS2: Initiate a dialogue meeting between SEAFO and contracting party defined as a developing country.	C	0	
OT 2.2	I_3_CS2: Proportion of vessels, either EU of non-EU, geolocated.	B	4	Authority, SEAFO.
	I_4_CS2: Proportion of vessels, either EU of non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation.	A	0%	Authority, SEAFO.

3.2 Recommended OT 2.3 Onboard observers

Each Contracting Party in SEAFO shall ensure that all its vessels operating in the CA shall carry scientific observers qualified by the flag state (SEAFO 2018b). The observers shall ensure that all required information is provided in the relevant SEAFO Scientific observer Forms available at the SEAFO webpage, e.g. (1) SEAFO Scientific observer Form 2015 Pot, (2) SEAFO Scientific observer Form 2015 – Longline and (3) SEAFO Scientific Observers Form 2014 – Trawl. These forms are quite comprehensive, requiring a lot of information.

The compliance committee report (SEAFO, 2018c) reveals some challenges related to the competence of the inspectors, which not always are capable of reporting in line with the observer scheme.

There is a risk for not achieving OT 2.3 related to the content and quality of the data submitted in observers report, not the actual submission of the reports. An identified need is training of observers.

FarFish acknowledge the comprehensive work on compliance by SEAFO and will approach SEAFO and ask them how FarFish can contribute to their already ongoing initiatives. This approach will be made as part of developing the second version of the MR for this case study.

3.3 Other potential actions as supplement to the MR

Apart from the OTs identified for the EU fleet operating in South East Atlantic waters, two action points, A2.1 and A2.2, have been identified that could strongly support the case study objectives identified in the MR0:

A2.1: Compiling existing knowledge on main stocks being targeted in the area, which exist to some degree at different scientific institutions and research programmes e.g. Nansen programme (The data collected by the Dr. Fridtjof Nansen is though rather limited to identifying vulnerable marine ecosystems).

A2.2: Development of user friendly, digital maps (VMS/AIS based) with the intention of identifying fishing pressure of different fishing fleets. These action points have not been included in the list of OTs, as the operators cannot solely operationalise them, as they require input/action from other relevant parties (authorities, scientific institutions, other international fleets, etc.).

4 Management strategies, management measures, risks adaptive planning

4.1 Strategies and risk for achieving OT 4.1

SEAFO has three logbook schemes; for longline, pot and trawl (available at <http://www.seafo.org/Management/Reporting-Forms>). Logbook data is expected to be submitted to the Secretariat within 30 days of the completion of the fishing trip. The data must be in an electronic format as outlined by SEAFO Reporting Forms. However, SEAFO does not require vessels to use e-logbooks and the secretariat is not equipped to introduce such a system. Introduction of e-logbooks for all SEAFO fisheries will therefore require investments, capacity building and new procedures being adopted for several countries. For this to happen new requirements have to be adopted. A proposal has to be put forward by a contracting party based on input from FarFish (EU or Norway) to the Commission or the Compliance committee for the implementation of mandatory e-logbooks.

FarFish will explore the possibilities for introducing e-logbooks in SEAFO CA, by approaching FarFish Reference Group Members SEAFO and the ministry of Fisheries and Marine Resources (MFMR) in Namibia. A pilot project could be developed for deep sea crab fishery, which the Namibian fleet is targeting. FarFish task 4.3 contributor shall select a qualified institution amongst the FarFish Partners to lead this work.

This OT might be achievable but given the low level of fishing activity in the area, it is far from certain that the Commission will introduce this requirement at this point. There is therefore a high risk that this OT will not be adopted by SEAFO under the current situation with very limited fisheries. In a theoretical situation with increased fishing activity, the chances of SEAFO adopting such a measure is much higher, and a strategy to increase the chances would be to ensure funding for the least developed countries parties to SEAFO.

4.2 Strategies and risk for achieving OT 2.2

Vessels operating in SEAFO CA are obliged to transmit VMS data according as described in the comprehensive strategy for MCS by SEAFO. The parties of SEAFO seem to comply with the requirement to submit VMS data, despite some irregularity due to technical difficulties. All vessels >300GT are obliged to transmit AIS signals as well. The strategy for OT 2.2, therefore relate more to monitoring of the obliged transmission of VMS/AIS signals.

Improved monitoring can be achieved by utilizing latest available satellite systems and tools and add value to the fight against IUU. GFW²⁶ is collecting high spatial and temporal resolution data of fishing efforts worldwide through the use of AIS records obtained from communication satellite. Currently, the available data is aggregated, but companies like Marine Traffic²⁷ can obtain information on individual vessels if paid for.

FarFish will develop a big-Data analysis of AIS data through Work Group 6 leader CSIC. GFW has acknowledged FarFish as a scientific collaborator and given FarFish access to their fishing effort data for the time period 2012-2017.

Main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this obligatory OT related to the Big-Data analysis of AIS would be related to data treatment and AIS data deteriorating in quality once the vessels are aware of the existence of GFW. If individual data is required, vessel may not be willing to pay for this information. For comparisons of AIS and VMS data, flag state has to give access to VMS data for analysis. FarFish will approach FMC for the different countries for access, but such access has proven to be a challenge in other FarFish case studies. SEAFO is aware of the technical difficulties related to transmission of VMS signals by some contracting parties and it might be necessary to ensure funding for the least developed countries that are members of SEAFO for the full adoption of the VMS transmission.

4.3 Internal monitoring

The internal monitoring of the development of the OTs in this case study will be to follow up on the progress and require a commitment from other players than operators, since the current operators have limited control over the OTs. Simulation studies are not within the scope of this case study.

The authorities lead by FarFish WP3 shall promote and oversee the progress of OT2.1, with emphasis on I_1_CS2 and I_2_CS2. For OT 2.2, the operators are responsible for transmission of VMS signals, but WP3 as leading authority need to follow up and/or assist WP6 in data collection of VMS signals for both EU and non-EU vessels. If FarFish succeed in receiving both AIS and VMS data from all SEAFO contracting parties operating in the SEAFO convention area, it is theoretically possible to develop diagnostic tools to detect suspicious dynamics (e.g. Fishing vessels not providing all VMS data, vessels switching off the AIS and the level of vessels fishing on species not managed by other RFMOs) and thereby evaluate the proportion of VMS signals transmitted.

For OT 2.3 the operators are responsible for having the scientific observers on-board and have to ensure they are able to conduct their work according to the SEAFO reporting scheme. FarFish will

²⁶ <https://globalfishingwatch.org/>

²⁷ www.marinetraffic.com

approach SEAFO aiming to support SEAFO to a successful achievement of this OT in the next version of the MR. SEAFO is already monitoring that the observer protocols are submitted in accordance with the set requirements.

The following institutions are suggested to take the responsibility for the FarFish actions related to the OTs:

- SEAFO is responsible for monitoring of MCS in the SEAFO CA, including catch reporting and monitoring of VMS signals.
- FarFish partner IMR, case study leader for SE Atlantic, is responsible for initiating the dialogue between MFMR and SEAFO for the development of a pilot study. It is suggested that SEAFO and coastal state should be made responsible to follow up after the lifetime of the project.
- SEAFO as the competent authority should be responsible for monitoring of the fishing fleet using utilizing latest available satellite systems and tools, building on experiences from FarFish partner CSIS development of big data analysis.

5 Monitoring, compliance and sanctions

The nature of the obligatory OTs in this MR entail that operators cannot be made solely responsible for achieving them, so their compliance to the MR1 related to the OTs cannot be monitored in the way suggested in the Guidelines for Management Recommendations (FarFish, 2018a). FarFish is not in the position to issue potential sanctions to operators or authorities for not providing e-logbooks or transmit VMS/AIS signals.

5.1 SEAFO compliance and sanctions

Various actions are taken depending on whether an infringement falls within the jurisdiction of the port Contracting Party or not (Article 25). While each Contracting Party has to submit an Annual compliance report, SEAFO outlines 'Measures to promote compliance' as outlined in Article 26 of 'The System'. There is also discussions annually where contracting parties found to have violated or not complied with some of the requirements of 'The System' will be "confronted" and required to come up with mitigating measures (SEAFO. 2018 system). Information about this is found in the annual commission and compliance committee reports.

As to sanctions directed at operators directly, the SEAFO has the authority to not authorize a vessel to fish in the SEAFO convention area and there is an IUU list, and an agreement of mutual recognition of IUU vessels of several other RFMOS. Sanctions system is described in the 'SYSTEM' (SEAFO 2018a). The Commission will remove a vessel from the SEAFO IUU vessel list if a number of criteria are met, including i) that vessels Flag State has taken effective action, ii) that the vessel did not engage in IUU as outlined in Article 27, paragraph 4, which includes the use of prohibited fishing gear, unreported catches, land undersized fish, fishing during closed periods, and transshipping.

5.2 Monitoring of FarFish actions

The authorities lead by FarFish WP3 shall oversee the development of the pilot project to test e-logbooks (OT2.1). For OT 2.2, the operators are responsible for transmission of VMS/AIS signals, but WP3 as leading authority need to follow up WP6 in data collection of VMS signals. If FarFish succeed in receiving both AIS and VMS data from one SEAFO contracting party, it is theoretically possible to develop diagnostic tools to detect suspicious dynamics (e.g. Fishing vessels not providing all VMS data, vessels switching off the AIS and the level of vessels fishing on species not managed by other RFMOs) and thereby evaluate the proportion of VMS signals transmitted. For OT 2.3, it is the operators that are responsible for having the scientific observers on board, but it is the flag state responsibility to ensure that the scientific observers are qualified to fulfil the requirements to the observers' reports. The authorities by SEAFO already monitor that the observer protocols are submitted in accordance with the set requirements and report their results in the Annual Committee Compliance report.

6 Documentation

The information necessary to evaluate progress towards achieving the OTs in this case study will be attainable from the SEAFO secretariat and from GWF. Information on the EU fleet could also be requested from DG Mare/EFCA, there might be a risk of SEAFO or DG Mare/EFCA not providing this data. However, it will be able for the auditor to get information from the SEAFO annual commission reports and the more detailed annual compliance committee reports. This information is openly available from the SEAFO home site (www.seafo.org/documents). From this, it will be possible to score the performance of the vessels operating under the SEAFO fisheries on the specified OTs addressing measures already in place in SEAFO, i.e. transmission of VMS data and levels of observers (OT 4.3). This could be reported on indicator level A.

FarFish action related to OT 4.1 reporting via e-logbooks, include collection of the forms for the current logbooks should serve as basis of information to include for longline, trawl and pot fishery. All forms are easily available at the SEAFO website. The annual meetings in SEAFO takes place in November, hence the reports are available in the first quarter of the coming year. For the FarFish actions, to explore the potential of achieving OT 2.1 and TO 2.2, the authority is responsible (Table 7).

Table 7: Documentation matrix for FarFish actions related to MR1 Southeast Atlantic

OT	OT short	Indicators	Sources/ Data collection	Processing of data	Action/ Responsibility
2.1	E-logbooks	I_1_CS2	IMR	IMR (CS leader)	Acting operator: NOFIMA (WP3)
		I_2_CS2	IMR		
2.2	AIS/VMS transmission	I_3_CS2	FMC SEAFO	CSIC (WP6)	Authority: SEAFO
		I_4_CS2	CPC/GFW		

7 Auditor

FarFish partner Syntesa will audit the RFMS process and implementation process and has agreed to this at the initial stage of FarFish. It is however possible to seek different auditors if necessary.

8 Planning process

The development of MRs depend on input from other Work packages and this first version is supported by the Case study characterization (FarFish 2017), Management Plan Zero (FarFish, 2018d) Developments needed to produce relevant management tools (FarFish, 2018x), Draft 1 General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2018b), First MR invitations (FarFish, 2018a), Report from MR Kick-off meeting (FarFish, 2018c), Evaluation of governance structures of the cases (FarFish, 2018e), Stakeholders hub (FarFish 2018f), Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 1 (FarFish, 2018x), Visualization materials and tools for MR1 (FarFish, 2018x) and Description of CS value chains (FarFish, 2019). WP5 will provide their audit of the MR1 in FarFish deliverable D5.2 by August 2019.

Tentative planning

OT 2.1

- FarFish will approach SEAFO and propose / come up with a plan to approach this strategy by September 15th 2019.

OT 2.2

- FarFish will approach SEAFO, requesting VMS data by August 1st 2019.
- FarFish WP6, CISC, successfully has access to GFW data for the time period 2012-2017.
- Working plan when data are available:
 1. Assessment of type and amount of VMS data.
 2. Overlapping (time and place) analysis between GFW and VMS data in SEAFO CA.
 3. Implementation of massive data techniques for cross-comparison.
 4. Diagnose the results in terms of compliance.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. SEAFO Reporting Obligations 2019

SEAFO Reporting Obligations 2019

Prepared: 3 June 2019

Management Measure	Article	Report	Report To	Reporting Date	Report Frequency	Reporting Method
GENERAL PROVISIONS	SEAFO System (Art. 3.2)	CP Contact Points	Secretariat - ES	Prior to 15 March 2013	Once - then as needed	Electronically-Email
CONTROL	SEAFO System (Art. 4.1, 4.2)	Vessel List	Secretariat - ES	1st January	Annually	Electronically-Email
	SEAFO System (Art. 4.7)	Sited Illegal Vessel	Secretariat - ES	Without delay	Upon Occurrence	Not specified
	SEAFO System (Art. 8.f)	Lost Gear	Secretariat - ES	Without delay	Upon Occurrence	Not specified
MONITORING	SEAFO System (Art. 10.2)	Logbook	Secretariat - ES	Within 30 days of leaving CA	Upon Occurrence	Not specified
	SEAFO System (Art. 11.a)	Entry Report (COE)	Secretariat - ES	6 hours in advance of entry	Once	Electronically-Email/HTTPS
	SEAFO System (Art. 11.b) CMI 31/15 (Para.2)	5-Day Catch (CAT)	Secretariat - ES	After every 5 days of catch	Every 5 days	Electronically-Email/HTTPS
	SEAFO System (Art. 11.c)	Exit Report (COX)	Secretariat - ES	6 hours in advance of exit	Once	Electronically-Email/HTTPS
	SEAFO System (Art. 12.1)	Quarterly Aggregated Catch	Secretariat - ES	30 days after quarter	Quarterly	Electronically-Email
	SEAFO System (Art. 13.1-13.3)	VMS - Positions	Secretariat - ES	No later than 24 hours after Receipt	Every 2 hours	Electronically-Email/HTTPS
	SEAFO System (Art. 14.2)	Notification of Transshipments in port	Port State	24 hours before transshipment	Upon Occurrence	Not specified
	SEAFO System (Art. 14.4)	Transshipments	Secretariat - ES	Not specified	Annually	Not specified

CAPE VERDE CASE STUDY

Deliverable No. 4.3

Project acronym:

FarFish

Project title:

Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

Grant agreement No: **727891**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme

Start date of project: **1st June 2017**

Duration: **48 months**

Due date of deliverable:	31/01/2019
Submission date:	23/09/2020
File Name:	FarFish_D4.3_MR1 Cape Verde
Revision number:	02
Document status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public

Role	Name	Organisation	Date	File suffix
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Deliverable D4.3

Management Recommendation 1

Cape Verde

23/09/2020

Executive Summary

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) for the tuna fishery under the SFPFA agreement between Cape Verde and EU. The MR1 follows the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, D3.1) and is based on the Management Invitation (FarFish, D3.2) where the outcome targets (OTs) are proposed. Only the obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version of the MR. This is because they are considered the most important to reach the main objectives of the MR which were identified by authorities in Management Plan Zero (MP0) (FarFish, D4.1), and based on input from operators at the MR Kick-off meeting (FarFish, D4.2). The recommended OTs are not considered vital to the MR progress aiming to reach the management objectives, but FarFish will address these in the next iteration and in the following version of the MR (MR2). The aim of this MR is to improve data collection for the best scientific advice to promote sustainable fishery and to improve monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) through satellite monitoring. The subsequent OTs are classified to ecological and governance dimension. We acknowledge that the operators cannot be solely made responsible for achieving the OTs. It must therefore be a joint effort between authorities and operators to make progress in this MR. Indicators are suggested to measure the performance of the OTs and the strategy for achieving OTs is outlined. The strategies do not affect any of the current management conservation measures by EU, Cape Verde, or ICCAT and will not affect the catches of the fishers. The main risk identified for not achieving the OTs is data limitations.

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Abbreviations

AIS	Automatic Identification System
AMP	Maritime and Port Agency, Cape Verde
ANFACO-CECOPECA	National Association of Fish and Seafood Canning Manufactures (Representing EU fishing and processing sector)
APESC	Cape Verde Fisheries Association
BSP2	Bayesian surplus production model (stock assessment model applied for N. Swordfish by ICCAT)
CCMAR	Centro de Ciencias do Mar do Algarve, FarFish Partner
CECAF	Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries, RFMO
CECAF-SC	Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries Scientific Committee
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy, EU
COSMAR	Operations Centre for Maritime Safety, Cape Verde
CPC	Vessels entitled to fly their flags and authorized to fish species managed by ICCAT in the Convention area, flag Contracting Parties, Cooperating non-Contracting Parties, Entities or Fishing Entities
CPUE	Catch per Unit Effort
CS	Case Study
DFAD	Drifting Fish Aggregating Device
DG MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, EC. This Commission department is responsible for EU policy on maritime affairs and fisheries
DGRM	General Directorate for Marine Resources, National Fisheries Authority, Cape Verde
DNEM	Directorate National of Maritime Economy, Cape Verde
ERS	Electronic recording and reporting system
ENAPOR	National Cape Verde Port company Association
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FarFish RG	FarFish Reference Group
FIP	Fisheries Improvement Project
FMC	Fisheries Monitoring Centre
HCR	Harvest Control Rule
ICCAT	International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas, RFMO
ICMAN-CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, FarFish Partner
IMO	International Maritime Organization
INDP	National institute for Fisheries Development, Cape Verde
INDS	National fisheries Institute, Cape Verde
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estatística, Cape Verde
IPOA	International Plan of Action
IUU	Illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing
LDAC	Long Distance Advisory Council, EU fisheries body representing stakeholders of both fishing sector and other groups of interest, FarFish Partner
LL	Longline
MATIS	Icelandic Food and Biotech R&D, FarFish partner
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance

MPO	Management Plan Zero
MR	Management Recommendation
MSY	Maximum Sustainable Yield
NOFIMA	Is the fusion of several Norwegian food research institutes and covers all food sectors and links in the value chain, FarFish Partner
NPOA	National Plan of Action
OPAGAC	Organisation of Associated Producers of Large Tuna Freezer Vessels, Spain, FarFish RG
OPROPOMAR	Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín, Spain, FarFish Partner
ORPAGU	Organization of Surface Longliners from A Guarda, Galicia, Spain, FarFish RG
PGRP	Cape Verde Fisheries Management Plan
PS	Purse seine
RBM	Results-Based Management
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SEAFO	South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation, RFMO
SFPA	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements
SIGQ	Serviços de Inspeção e Garantia de Qualidade cpcp, Cape Verde
SOLAS	Safety Of Life At Sea
SSF	small scale fisheries management
SYN	SP/F SYNTESA, FarFish Partner
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
UEMOA	West African Economic and Monetary Union
UiT	University of Tromsø- The Arctic University of Norway, FarFish Partner
VIANAPESCA	COOPERATIVA DE PRODUTORES DE PEIXE DE VIANA DO CASTELO
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System

Concepts/definitions

AIS	Is an autonomous and continuous vessel identification and monitoring system used for maritime security which allows vessels to electronically exchange with other nearby ships and authorities ashore the vessel identification data, position, course and speed.
Authority	Organizational entity enacting authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission
ERS	Is used to record, report, process, store and send fisheries data (catch, landing, sales and transshipment)
Indicator	A variable, pointer or index related to a criterion. Indicators are selected such that their variations reflect variations in key elements of the fishery resource, the social and economic well-being of the sector and the sustainability of the ecosystem. The position and trend of an indicator in relation to reference points or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. Indicators provide a bridge between objectives and actions (source: FAO 1999).
Management goals	The higher-order objective to which a management intervention is intended to contribute (OECD 2011). A management goal is derived from a management principle (constitutional-order) and is specified into a set of more operational management objectives (collective-order).
Management intervention	Strategies or instruments aimed to impact the state of a fishery with reference to authorized objectives. Examples are input and output controls and economic measures.
Management measures	Can be technical (e.g. gear selectivity etc.), input (effort)/output (catch) control, right based.
Management objectives	Fisheries management objectives are typically framed within the overall concept of sustainable development, and may reflect one or more of the various dimensions and criteria that relate to it (FAO 1999). Operators through setting and implementing management measures control OTs.
Management Plan (MP)	A fisheries management plan is a formal arrangement between a fishery management authority and interested parties which identifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, details the agreed objectives for the fishery and specifies the management rules and regulations which apply to it and provides other details about the fishery which are relevant to the task of the management authority (Source: FAO 2002).
Management Recommendation (MR)	In RFMS, the management recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority and operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery. In RFMS, the formal responsibility for developing the management plan is delegated to an operator.
Management strategies	In FarFish context, it means the strategies applied to achieve OTs
Operator	Organizational unit with delegated authority to develop management Recommendations and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority
Outcome Target (OT)	Outcome targets (OTs) are specific and measurable requirements that are set by an authority to make management goals operational. An OT is a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B') or a statement of presence or absence of some entity. On the basis of relevant information, this statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time ⁵⁴ . For instance, the management objective that "the fishery should be biologically sustainable" could be expressed in terms of one or more OTs such as 'Catch < 20 000t; 'bycatch < 20%'; SSB > 30 000t; 'a catch reporting system is present', etc.

Reference point	A classification device, defined in relation to the measure of an indicator, for distinguishing different management relevant states of the system under management. A Biological Reference Point is a metric of stock status. A Target Reference Point indicates a state of a system which is considered desirable and at which management action should aim. A Limit Reference Point indicates a state of a system, which is considered to be undesirable, that one therefore should seek to avoid through relevant management action.
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) is a fisheries management approach developed within the FP7 project EcoFishMan . The RFMS is an adaptive management approach that is results-based and ecosystem-based. The RFMS attempts to reduce micromanagement by involving stakeholders and increase the degree of co-management by delegating management responsibilities to resource users.
VMS	Is a satellite-based fishing vessel monitoring system providing data to the fisheries authorities at regular intervals on the location, course and speed of vessels. Compulsory for vessels >15 m.

1 Management recommendation 1 for Cape Verde

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) from the following European operator’s active in the Cape Verde tuna fishery under the SFPA (2014-2018): LDAC, ANFACO-CECOPECA, OPROMAR, OPAGAC and ORPAGU. The proposal defines the strategies and measures suggested in order to achieve the outcome targets (OTs) received from the authorities in the first MR invitation (FarFish, D3.2) and how these strategies could be implemented in the given setting. The development of this MR1 follows the General Guidelines for making Management recommendations (FarFish, D3.1).

2 Introduction

A Management Recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority²⁸ and operators²⁹ (Figure 2.1). This MR is founded on Results-Based Management (RBM) principles in line with the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) approach, which was developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan (Nielsen et al., 2017). In line with the RFMS approach, the engagement of stakeholders is highly prioritized in FarFish and during the MR kick-off meeting in Vigo, Spain in June 2018, several operators expressed their interest and needs, which was highly relevant for development of the MR Invitation and for defining the OTs, in which this MR1 will address (FarFish, D4.2).

Figure 2.1 The RFMS process. The responsibilities of each of the three entities are demonstrated with different colours. Authority: red/Operators: blue/ Auditors: yellow (FarFish, D3.1).

²⁸ Authority: Organizational entity acting authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission

²⁹ Operator: Organizational unit with delegated authority to develop management plans and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority

2.1 Partners involved in MR1 in the Cape Verde Case Study

The authority is the organizational entity acting as authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission. They oversee the RFMS process and issue the “MR invitation”, which includes a clear specification of measurable Outcome Targets (OTs), set in order to operationalize goals of existing policies and the local management objectives. In FarFish it is the leader of Task 3.3 (Authority role within RFMS), MATIS, that acts as the leading authority, whilst considering input from relevant authorities, e.g. the National Directorate of Maritime Economy (DNEM), General Directorate for Marine Resources (DGRM) and Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE). The main contact person in this process is Jónas R. Viðarsson³⁰ from WP3, as the leader of Task 3.3.

The operator is defined as an organized group of resource users, e.g. an association of fishermen or stakeholders with rights in a given fishery. It is the organizational unit with delegated authority to develop MRs based on the OTs set by the authority and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority. In FarFish, Work Package 4 lead by UiT - The Arctic University of Norway, assists the representatives for operators in the development of the MR1.

The European operator qualified to respond to the MR Invitation for Cape Verde are the Long-Distance Advisory Council ³¹(LDAC) represented by its Executive Secretary Alexandre Rodríguez. In addition, have two members from Organisation of Surface Longliners from Guarda (ORPAGU) and three members from Organisation of Associated Producers of Large Tuna Freezer Vessels (OPAGAC) participated in MR1 meetings. ORPAGU is currently undertaking a Prospective Fisheries Improvement Plan (FIP) called FIP BLUES with WWF and other Spanish and Portuguese surface longliner organisations (namely ARVI and VIANAPESCA) for its two main commercial species, i.e. blue shark (*Prionace glauca*) and swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*). LDAC is an EU fisheries stakeholder led body represented by its Executive Secretary Alexandre Rodríguez³². LDAC has a nominal composition of 60% of fishing sector organisations (including catching, processing and marketing sectors, and trade unions). The remaining 40% is other groups of interests (mainly environmental and development NGOs).

2.2 Aims of MR1 for the Cape Verde case study

The main aims of MR1 for Cape Verde is to improve data collection and monitoring for sustainable fisheries, especially for the species of blue shark and swordfish, as there is high uncertainty in the data provided and the catch data from EU, Cape Verde and ICCAT diverge some years. Both species are

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reported as bycatch species in some fisheries, but swordfish is listed as a 1-Tuna (major species) with full assessment by ICCAT. Subsequently, there is a need to harmonize catch data protocols to ensure that the best scientific data is collected and made available for authorities and the relevant scientific institutions, including ICCAT. This also applies for bycatches, as blue shark is still considered such in the current SFP agreement (2014-2018). The insufficient control and monitoring in relation to foreign vessels in Cape Verde EEZ, are obstacles to the fight against IUU fisheries. As the EU fleet only take parts of the total allowable catch (TAC) of swordfish and blue shark in the North Atlantic inside Cape Verde EEZ and other nations catch the species too, it is not within the scope of FarFish to address the fishery of swordfish and blue shark in the North Atlantic as a whole.

2.3 Current Management Plan in Cape Verde, Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) and relevant ICCAT Recommendations

The current MP is named the Cape Verde Fisheries Management Plan (PGRP), and it was adopted in 2004 under the National Environment Plan 2004-2014 (Plano de Acção Nacional para o Ambiente - PANA II) with the objective to ensure that the fisheries of Cape Verde contribute to increase national production, food safety, quality of fishery products, employment, and to decrease the balance of payments deficit. The PGRP proposes a set of measures for a rational exploitation of fisheries resources and the development of the fisheries sector in a sustainable way. This plan also contemplates shark fishing, fished by foreign vessels.

A review of the plan is pending and, in the meantime, the plan is implemented by means of Biannual Executive Plans, published in the Boletim Oficial da República de Cape Verde, detailing the regulations and management measures (FarFish, D3.3). The current execution of the plan concerns the period 2018-2019. The plan sets out a number of policy restrictions on foreign fishing in general, as well as specific measures in relation to specific fisheries, including foreign fishing. In respect of tuna fishing, the Plan estimates the potential available in the EEZ, allows a gradual development of the fishery, and proposes a cautious expansion of the fishing effort, subject to control of the number of fishing licenses issued. Fishing for live bait by foreign vessels is prohibited within the 12 nautical miles. Live bait is normally caught within 3 nautical miles, an area reserved exclusively for artisanal fishing; support vessels are however allowed to operate in bays and in non-inhabited areas within 3 nautical miles, exclusively to catch live bait; bait caught under such circumstances shall under no circumstances be marketed for consumption.

A National Plan of Action (NPOA) for the conservation and management of sharks in the EEZ of Cape Verde is being elaborated by INDP with the support of FAO. The plan will be aligned with the FAO International Plan of Action (IPOA) for the conservation and management of sharks and the ICCAT

recommendations and is expected to be published in 2019. It is also expected that the catches of sharks will be a part of the negotiations of a new protocol.

The European Union has also established a system concerning fishing activities of Union fishing vessels fishing outside Union waters under SFPAs agreements and on the high seas³³ and the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) requires SFPAs to be limited to surplus catches. The CFP stresses the need to promote the objectives of CFP internationally, ensuring that Union fishing activities outside Union waters area based on the same principles and standards as those applicable under Union law, while promoting level playing field for Union operators and third-country operators. The main objective of the CFP is to ensure that fishing activities are environmentally, economically and socially sustainable and are managed consistently with the objectives of achieving economic, social and employment benefits, and of restoring and maintaining fish stocks above levels which can produce maximum sustainable yield and that they are contributing to the availability of food supplies. Additionally, the union has committed itself to Sustainable Development Goal 14³⁴ (SDG 14) and Sustainable Development Goal 12³⁵ (SDG 12). EU vessels operating under the SFPAs agreement shall comply with all the recommendations adopted by ICCAT (SFPAs protocol, Annex, Chpt III Technical conservation measures). All EU vessels fishing under SFPAs agreement must keep a fishing logbook (Appendix 4 in SFPAs protocol) and all vessels fishing tuna must report nominal catch (Task I) and catch & effort data (Task II) sheets to ICCAT.

In order to ensure conservation of the North Atlantic Swordfish, ICCAT recommends the goal of maintaining BMSY with greater than 50% probability (ICCAT, Rec. 17-02)

A number of ICCAT Recommendations apply to the fisheries in question

2.4 Identity of Fishery

The SFPAs between EU and Cape Verde concerns the highly migratory species of tuna (yellowfin, skipjack and bigeye), but also blue shark and swordfish are caught in a considerable extend (either as target or bycatch species). Up to 71 EU vessels (28 purse seiners, 30 surface long liners, 13 pole-and-line vessels) have the opportunity to apply for licence to fish for tuna and tuna like (highly migratory) species under the agreement, at a reference tonnage of 5,000 tonnes per year in the period 2014–2018 (FarFish, D3.4). The vessels employ the following gear within Cape Verde EEZ (Fig. 2.2): purse seiners, longlines and pole and lines. Purse seiners and pole and line vessels mainly target tropical tuna stocks, while swordfish and blue shark are the main target species of the surface longline vessels, with some catches of tropical tuna as well.

³³ REGULATION (EU) 2017/2403 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 12 December 2017 on the sustainable management of external fishing fleets, and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008

³⁴ SDG14: conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

³⁵ SDG12: ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns and their targets

Figure 2.2 Cape Verde, baseline and EEZ limits towards Mauritania and Senegal in east. Source: US Department of State, Bureau of Oceans and Environmental and Scientific Affairs³⁶ (FarFish, D3.4)

Figure 2.3 Cape Verde insular area 34.3.2 (as part of FAO area Eastern Central Atlantic) and an approximation of the Cape Verde EEZ-limits. Sources: <http://www.fao.org/fishery/area/Area34/> (left) and World Bank (2008) – (right) (FarFish, D3.4)

³⁶ See <https://www.state.gov/documents/organization/221365.pdf>

The vessels operating under the agreement are from Spain, Portugal and France. The SFPA is for tuna and tuna-like species and accounts for 5,000 reference tonnes per year for the EU fleet. Pole and line is allowed beyond 12 nm (yellowfin, bigeye, and skipjack), tuna seiners beyond 16 nm (yellowfin, bigeye, and skipjack) and surface longliners beyond 18 nm (swordfish, blue shark, yellowfin tuna and bigeye tuna). Main challenges identified in the Cape Verde Fisheries Management Plan (PGRP) in relation to foreign fleet fisheries in Cape Verde are non-compliance by foreign vessels, insufficient control and monitoring and competition with the national commercial fleet (s).

Table 2.1 MR1 Cape Verde entities, geographical range, target species, fleets, main aims and time frame

MR basis	MR1 Cape Verde
RFMS entities	Authorities: WP3, DG MARE, DNEM, DGRM
	Operators: WP4, LDAC, ANFACO-CECOPESCA, ORPAGU, OPAGAC
	Auditor: WP5
Target species	Yellowfin tuna (YFT) (<i>Thunnus albacares</i>) Bigeye tuna (BTH) (<i>Thunnus obesus</i>) Skipjack tuna (SKJ) (<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>) Blue shark (BSH) (<i>Prionace glauca</i>) Swordfish (SWO) (<i>Xiphias glaidus</i>)
Geographical range	Cape Verde EEZ area 289,400 km ² Pole and line: beyond 12 nm from the base line Tuna seiners: beyond 16 nm from the base line Surface longliners: beyond 18 nm from the base line
Fleets	EU fleet: Spain, Portugal and France Pole and line vessels Tuna seiners Surface longliners
Main aims of MR	The overall Management goal is to improve data collection for sustainable fisheries and support the fight against IUU by improved monitoring, control and surveillance
MR planning period	The active participation of operators allows FarFish to have a RBM approach within the lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021)

3 Fishery overview

The fishing opportunities are accessed by the EU fleet from Spain, Portugal and France (Table 3.1). Other non-EU vessels operating the Cape Verde waters, apart from the domestic fleet, are from Japan (8 longliners), Senegal (4 purse seiners, 2 pole & liners), El Salvador (4 purse seiners), Curacao (3 purse seiners), Panama (2 purse seiners) and Belize (1 purse seine vessel). Much of the tuna, together with most shark, swordfish and shortfin mako caught within the Cape Verdean EEZ by EU vessels, is landed in Mindelo, but are then exported directly (FarFish, D3.4). Most of the catches of swordfish and blue shark are transhipped to Vigo are auctioned and/or sold, classified and supplied on frozen to local companies such as Fandicosta (<http://fandicosta.es/en/>), Eduardo Vieira (<http://vieirasa.es/>) or Hermanos Ibañez (<http://www.hfcp.com>), amongst others. By-catches by all fleets should be in compliance with ICCAT and FAO recommendations in terms of reporting.

Table 3.1 Total number of EU vessels by gear and country allocated Cape Verde licenses, 2015–2017. PS=purse seine, LL= long liners, PL= pole and line. Source: Amador et al., (2018)

	Protocol		2015		2016		2017	
	Allocation 2014		#	Share	#	Share (%)	#	Share (%)
Spain	PS	16	12	75%	13	81%	11	69%
	LL	23	7	30%	13	57%	14	61%
	PL	7	7	100%	7	100%	7	100%
	TOT	46	26	57%	33	72%	32	70%
France	PS	12	12	100%	11	92%	10	83%
	PL	4	1	25%	1	25%	1	25%
	TOT	16	13	81%	12	75%	12	75%
Portugal	LL	7	2	29%	2	29%	2	29%
	PL	2		0%	1	50%		0%
	TOT	9	2	22%	3	33%	2	22%
TOT		71	41	58%	48	68%	46	65%

3.1 Recent trends- EU catch statistics and EU fleet

During the period from 2014 to 2017, catches of the EU fleet have varied between 4,500 and 10,000 tons (Table 3.1). In 2017, total catches from EU tuna vessels amounted to just under 10,000 tons, which is almost double the reference tonnes under the SFPA and the average EU catch in 2014-2017 was at 7,285 tonnes (Amador et al., 2018). Seven species accounted for 99.75% of the reported catch (in tonnes) in 2017; skipjack tuna (61%), blue shark (20%), yellowfin tuna (8%), bigeye tuna (8%), shortfin mako (1%), swordfish (1%) and frigate tuna (1%) (Amador et al., 2018). Catches are dominated by Spanish vessels, which accounted for 98% of the catches in 2017, while catches from French and Portuguese vessels have fluctuated, but at much lower levels (Table 3.1).

In the period from 2014-2017, the average total catch of blue shark and swordfish in North Atlantic was 39,986 and 20,812 tonnes, respectively (ICCAT, 2018 SCRS report), whereas the EU catch in Cape Verdean waters then accounted for 4.9% and 0.4% of this total catch of blue shark and swordfish respectively (Table 3.2, numbers from Amador et al., 2018). On average, blue shark accounted for approximately 96% of shark catches by EU fleet in the period from 2014-2017, while swordfish accounted for 86% of other catch category in the same time period (Table 3.2).

Table 3.2 Licensed EU vessels' catch in Cape Verdean waters by flag country in the period 2014-2017. Catches are in tonnes. (Source: FarFish D3.4, Amador et al., 2018)

	2014	2015	2016	2017	Average 2014-2017
Tuna	8,251	2,042	2,392	7,819	5,126
- skipjack	91%	88%	64%	78%	83%
Shark	1,392	2,797	1,977	2,052	2,054
- blue shark	96%	96%	96%	95%	96%
Other	56	127	126	112	105
-swordfish	84%	91%	87%	82%	86%
Total	9,699	4,966	4,494	9,983	7,285
- Spain	8,246	4,617	3,801	9,791	6,614
- Portugal		98	175	125	133
- France	1,453	251	517	66	572
> Longliners	1,445	2,947	2,119	2,178	2,172
- blue shark	92%	91%	89%	90%	90%
> Purse seine	6,969	659	962	6,477	3,767
- Skipjack tuna	90%	88%	53%	79%	83%
> Pole & line	1,284	1,361	1,414	1,328	1,347
- Skipjack tuna	99%	89%	71%	73%	83%

The ORPAGU vessels submit their daily catch data to the Flag State (Spain) through the Electronic Reporting System (known as “e-logbook”) within the requirements set under the EU Control Regulation 1224/2009 currently in force. The data officers employed by ORPAGU to fulfil the Excel data sheets required by ICCAT, have been granted authorization by the Spanish control authorities to install a “viewer” software so they have access in real time to the electronic logbook of all vessels, allowing to perform this task on a daily basis. These data are then submitted to both the Cape Verdean and Spanish authorities (Fig. 3.1). Both these authorities are obliged to cooperate and subsequently submit the data from electronic logbooks of all vessels in an aggregated manner to the ICCAT Secretary.

Figure 3.1 Transmission of catch data from ORPAGU (longline) vessels fishing under SFPA in Cape Verde EEZ, where FMC: Fisheries Monitoring Centre, ERS: Electronic Reporting System (electronic fishing logbooks).

3.2 Stock status of target species

Stock assessments of the major tunas and associated species such as billfish (e.g. swordfish) and sharks (e.g. blue shark) are carried out regularly (i.e. every 3-4 years) under the framework of ICCAT. Currently, ICCAT consider that the North Atlantic swordfish stock, nor the Northern blue shark stock to be overfished or overexploited and swordfish is assumed to be at MSY level, it should be noted though that bigeye tunas are considered in red stock status due to overexploitation (Table 3.3), but the catch of the EU fleet in Cape Verde waters only accounted for 0.6% of total catch of Bigeye on average in the period 2014-2017. Skipjack tuna dominate catches of EU tuna in Cape Verde and is considered to be at MSY level and not overfished, while yellowfin tuna has yellow status being slightly overfished (Table 3.3). As the main species addressed in this first version of the MR for Cape Verde are Blue shark and swordfish, they are described in more detail below.

Table 3.3 Summary of stock status targets species from ICCAT stock summary³⁷

Species	Catch (1000t) ³⁸	MSY (1000t)	Stock status	Surplus at regional level
Yellowfin tuna (<i>Thunnus albacares</i>)	128	126	Overfished	Overfished
Bigeye tuna (<i>Thunnus obesus</i>)	72	79	Overexploited	Overexploited
Skipjack tuna (<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>)	217	143-170	At MSY level	At MSY level
N Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>)	42		Not likely overfished or overexploited	Not likely overfished or overexploited
N Swordfish (<i>Xiphias gladius</i>)	13	10	At MSY level	At MSY level
S Swordfish (<i>Xiphias gladius</i>)	15	8	Overfished	Overfished

3.2.1 Target species swordfish (SWO)

ICCAT separates the stock assessment of the Atlantic swordfish into North Atlantic Stock (SWO-N) and South Atlantic stock (SWO-S) at 5°N and the last assessment was in 2017. The North Atlantic stock is distributed between 5°N-55°N latitude and 10°W-65°W longitude. The fishery in Cape Verde EEZ targets the SWO-N in ICCAT statistical area BIL94B (Figure 3.2). Swordfish is mainly targeted by longline (LL) (Fig. 3.1). Current management recommendations from ICCAT for SWO-N provides probability of maintaining $B < B_{msy}$ and maintaining $F < F_{msy}$ over a range of TAC options for a period of 10 years, where the current TAC of 13,200 tons would have a 50% probability of resulting in a biomass above the B_{msy} with a probability greater than 50% (Appendix 1, ICCAT, 2018 SCRS report).

3.2.2 Target species Blue shark (BSH)

Although not directly covered by the ICCAT convention, such as tuna species and swordfish, the blue shark is identified under the ICCAT convention and management measures adopted by ICCAT such as fishing capacity and catch limits, area and seasonal restrictions, etc. There are two pelagic blue shark (BSH) stocks in the Atlantic, the North Atlantic stock (BSH-AN) and the South Atlantic stock (BSH-AS) and the stock targeted in Cape Verde waters is the North Atlantic stock, which was last assessed in 2015. ICCAT considers the reported and estimated catches for blue shark Task I generally subjected to higher level of uncertainty than the major tuna stocks, but nevertheless the reported data have been considered sufficiently complete for the purpose of quantitative stock assessment. The next assessment by ICCAT is planned in 2021.

³⁷ <https://www.iccat.int/en/assess.html>

³⁸ 2016 figures, <https://www.iccat.int/en/assess.html>

3 Maps (billfishes)

3.1 SWO (*Xiphias gladius*)

Name (UK): Swordfish
 Name (FR): Espadon
 Name (ES): Pez espada

Stocks: 3
 Stat. areas: n/a
 SA's: 9

SA codes by Stock

Stock code	SA code (*)
SWO-N	BIL91
	BIL92
	BIL93
	BIL94A
	BIL94B
	BIL94C
SWO-S	BIL96
	BIL97
SWO-M	BIL95

* Under revision (changes expected in near future)

Figure 3.2 ICCAT geographical definitions (version 2016.2 EN). Swordfish sampling area, stock and statistical area³⁹

The Cape Verde national fleet has limited interest in the blue shark fishery, mainly due to the high cost of production and lack of suitable vessel types. Catches of blue shark by foreign fleets have however increased over the past few years. The blue shark is considered capable to sustain relatively high levels of fishing mortality, compared to other shark species (Cortés et al., 2012), and the latest stock assessment by ICCAT in 2015 (Appendix 2, Anon, 2015) showed that the north Atlantic stock was unlikely to be overfished.

ICCAT considers the reported and estimated catches for blue shark generally subject to higher level of uncertainty than the major tuna stocks, they have been considered sufficiently complete for the purpose of quantitative stock assessment. In addition to Task I reports, blue shark is considered one of the three major sharks species obliged to report Task II effort and size data to ICCAT as well, but SCRS consider the information available for Task II to be very incomplete for this species. It is especially the requested information in reports T2CE and T2SC that are missing information.

The current management recommendation for blue shark in the north Atlantic by ICCAT summarized (Appendix 2, ICCAT, 2018 SCRS report); while all model formulations explored predicted that the stock

³⁹ <https://www.iccat.int/en/>

was not overfished and that overfishing was not occurring, the level of uncertainty in the data inputs and model structural assumptions was high enough to prevent the Committee from reaching a consensus on a specific management recommendation (ICCAT, 2018 SCRC Report 2018).

3.3 Specific challenges in the Cape Verde case study

There are specific challenges that have been identified for the Cape Verde case study, in regard to data collection and insufficient monitoring, control and surveillance.

3.3.1 High level of uncertainty in data collection

ICCAT acknowledge that the current data collection and/or data processing entails a high level of uncertainty for blue shark caught by the EU fleet in large volumes. Such uncertainty affects the quality of scientific data applied in stock assessment and hampers the development of sustainable fisheries. The need to harmonize data collection and processes between EU and ICCAT has also been expressed by operators represented by ORPAGU. They are required to provide a lot of documentation, but there seems to be little consistency in the documentation requirements of EU, ICCAT, national flag state and the coastal state authorities. ORPAGU claim that the lack of a harmonized protocol and reporting for all the data submitted is a challenge, but they are also concerned about the way the information is transferred to the authorities as well as the processing and treatment of data in terms of communication between administrations (software, expertise, logistic etc.) as well as the feedback provided to the operators.

In the fishing logbooks described in Annex Chapter IV and attached in Appendix 4 of the SFPA agreement, it is only mentioned “Tuna and similar highly migratory species” and those listed in the Fishing logbook are; Bluefin tuna (BFT), Yellowtail tuna (YTF), Bigeye tuna (BET), Albacore (ALB), Swordfish (SWO), striped marlin (MLS)/white marlin (WHM), Black marlin (BLM), Sailfish (SAI), Skipjack tuna (SKJ) and Miscellaneous fish. This is in accordance with Annex I of UNCLOS, but here oceanic sharks are only listed generally. This poses problems in practices as it ignores the reality that most of the recent year catches in Cape Verde under the SFPA (near 80%) for the ORPAGU fleet is blue shark and that can generate conflicts with inspections due to ambiguity.

Another problematic issue raised by ORPAGU is related to the scientific observer programme developed by the Spanish Fisheries Secretariat, where each of the ORPAGU vessels produce a comprehensive observer report of the fishing trips (2-3 month-time average). This provides the Spanish Administration with a lot of information in relation to catches of sharks: volume, number of individuals, length, sex ratios, females pregnant, embryos, by-catches of other species, etc. Nevertheless, it seems that the datasets submitted by operators and data obtained from scientific campaigns of IEO (they have historical time series of these fisheries for more than 30 years) does not

go through a valid format in the ICCAT advisory process, so it is not validated or accepted in the stock assessments made by the ICCAT SCRS. FarFish aims to explore this issue in the next loop of this MR.

3.3.2 Insufficient control and monitoring in the Cape Verde EEZ

The fight against IUU fisheries is important for sustainable fisheries and to ensure a level playing field for all fleets. As part of this work, monitoring is important, and the case study leader for Cape Verde has pointed out insufficient control and monitoring as a challenge in addition to non-compliance of the Cape Verde Fisheries Management Plan (PGRP) by foreign vessels. Competition with the national commercial fleet(s) has also been mentioned as a challenge. Amador et al. (2018) emphasise the ineffectiveness of monitoring and surveillance in Cape Verde, with only having the sharing of European logbooks as the means to determine catches (FarFish D3.4). EU vessels are obliged to transmit their position at all times with a satellite monitoring system (VMS) to their flag State⁴⁰. ORPAGU vessels send their VMS positions (location and speed) every 2 hours to its Flag State (Spain), which subsequently transmits these data to the Cape Verde authorities when fishing in their EEZ. It has been noted that INDP and other Cape Verde authority institutions cannot at present access and process the VMS data submitted by EU vessels, as their system is not currently compatible to the EU system (Amador et al., 2018), but according to the Ex-ante report of the last SFPAs agreement 2014-2018, this issue was supposed to be solved by the end of the last SFPAs agreement period. This is an issue that must be addressed if not already solved, but it is not within the power of FarFish or the operators to do so.

Another compulsory monitoring system for vessels over 300 gross tons (GT) engaged on international voyages is the Automatic Identification System (AIS) which is shared real-time information of ship traffic. Tracking AIS signals may aid monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems. The IMO Convention for the Safety Of Life At Sea (SOLAS) Regulation V/19.2 requires vessels to operate AIS Class A on-board at all times, unless there are valid security reasons to turn it off, temporarily. The AIS was intended to increase security at sea and support ship to ship collision avoidance, but as AIS transposes dynamic information such as ships position, course, speed, type of ship, navigational status in addition to IMO number, and the processed AIS data can provide insights and information for regulatory bodies and researchers. In 2014, the European Commission required the entire fishery fleet >15 m to install AIS Class A transmitters (Shelmerdine, 2015).

As AIS is an open source information system, the EU operators transmitting AIS are continuously monitored by their competitors and experience a public exposure of their fishing activity. As a consequence, they have been expelled from traditional fishing grounds due to increasing competition and proliferation of Asian vessels there.

⁴⁰ Protocol between European Union and Cape Verde, Annex, chapter VII, 1. Vessel position messages

4 Outcome targets and indicators

This chapter identifies the OTs and associated indicators established to provide measurable performance goals for the EU distant water fleet fishery under the SFPA agreement between Cape Verde and the EU.

In the MR invitation (FarFish, D3.2), the OTs are classified as obligatory or recommended, with a certain degree of flexibility to adapt to the realities and evolution of the defined case study throughout the lifetime of the project. Only obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version MR, as they are considered important to reach the main objectives of the MR for the Cape Verde case study. An OT is usually a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point. The indicator can be a variable, a pointer or an index related to a criterion. Its position and trend in relation to reference points (if available) or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. Often the indicator can be in the form of an inequality ('A>B'), but it can also be a statement of presence or absence of some entity, in which a statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time.

The indicators that relate to OTs should commonly be SMART, namely Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timely. However, during the stakeholder interaction in FarFish, it has become evident that some management objectives lead to OTs that are not SMART, but highly desirable by stakeholders and are therefore listed as obligatory OTs in the MR Invitation. An example of a biological/ecological indicator could be the fishing mortality (F); an example of economic indicator could be the EBITDA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization); and a social indicator could be the number of jobs created.

The suggested indicators in FarFish are set to measure the degree of adherence to the OTs and are classified in three dimensions: Ecological, Socio-Economic and Governance. The indicators are classified according to their level of quality achieved from the most detailed measuring achievement in percentage (type A), followed by a moderate type of evaluation where the level of achievement is considered to be high level (score level 4), moderate level (score 3), fair level (score 2) and low level (score 1) and not present (NL) (score 0). The last type of indicator measurability is type C, reflecting a measurement of indicators related to OT that can only have two outcomes such as yes (score 1) or no (Score 0), true or false, success or failure.

Table 4.1 FarFish indicator categories and their level of measurability

Indicator type	Level of quality achieved				
A	100%	75 %	50 %	25 %	0 %
B	High level (HL) 4	Moderate level (ML) 3	Fair Level (FL) 2	Low Level (LL) 1	Not present (NL) 0
C	Yes (true) 1				No (False) 0

4.1 Suggested outcome targets for the Cape Verde case study

The Cape Verde authorities, represented by the case study leader INDP, expressed key interest in the management objectives to improve data collection, improve compliance of PGRP by foreign vessels, and improve Cape Verdes control and monitoring capabilities (FarFish, D4.1). In order to monitor the compliance of area restrictions for different gears, it was suggested to collect and analyse satellite data from vessels operating in the area, in which all semi-industrial and industrial fleets are obliged to transmit according to PGRM, EU regulations and ICCAT Recommendation 14-09 GEN.

The suggested OTs defined in the Management Recommendation Invitation (FarFish, D3.2) are founded on the management objectives emphasized by the authorities during the development of Management Plan Zero, in line with the identified challenges in the case study (FarFish, D4.1), input from key stakeholders (from both EU and Cape Verde) received at the MR kick-off meeting in Vigo (FarFish, D4.2) and CS/WP leader meeting in Mindelo (November, 2018). The management goals, management objectives and the following suggested OTs are summarized in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome Targets for the Cape Verde

Management goal (CFP (SFPA) PGRM, SDG 14, ICCAT)	Management objectives	Outcome Target
Sustainable fisheries based on the best scientific advice	Improved data collection, In conformity with ICCAT, collect and analyse data on bycatch of swordfish and blue shark	OT 3.1 A harmonised catch data protocol that facilitate improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data, in place OT Dimension: Ecological
Sustainable fisheries by supporting the Fight against IUU fisheries	Improved monitoring and control by supporting enforcement through utilizing the latest available satellite systems and tools	OT 3.4 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals OT Dimension: Governance

During the process of identifying the appropriate OTs, it became apparent that the operators cannot be made solely responsible for some OTs, meaning that the authorities will need to take on part of the responsibility to ensure successful implementation.

4.1.1 Outcome Target 3.1 Harmonising of catch protocols –how we got there

As acknowledged above and already in the MR invitation the operators can not solely be made responsible for achieving the OT. So, this must be considered a joint effort where operators provide the necessary documentation to authorities, whilst the authorities provide the necessary data for analysis and input for the development of harmonized catch data protocols and logbooks. FarFish WP2 lead by CCMAR, will contribute to this process.

The following OT was proposed in the MR Invitation

OT 3.1 Development of an operational method for strengthening and harmonizing data protocols and reporting of swordfish and blue shark. This includes improved data recording in e-logbooks of all catches (target- and bycatches) and might require recording more detail than only species and volume e.g. sizes and number of individuals. Obligatory OT.

OT 3.1 was rephrased at WP/CS leader meeting at Cape Verde, November 2018; aiming to make it more specific and in accordance with feedback from ICCAT who is responsible for the assessment of tuna and tuna like species in this case study;

OT 3.1 A harmonised catch data protocol in place that facilitate improved reporting of swordfish and blue shark commercial and biological data

In order to measure the performance of OT 3.1, the following indicator suggested (Table 4.3);

- I_1: Harmonised protocols in place (This can be made more specific when the FarFish team has gotten overview of the variables and species lists provided now in the action suggested below)

Action by FarFish to facilitate the indicator: Report comparing all relevant catch report forms demonstrating harmonization of these forms.

Comments from the operators (ORPAGU):

The desirable OT would be to harmonize the data information systems linked to the SFPA and ICCAT, rather than relying on the Flag and Coastal States to submit the data according to the requirements of the EU and ICCAT in isolation.

4.1.2 Outcome Target 3.4 Transmission of VMS signals

The EU fleet is committed to transmit both VMS and AIS signals. The tracking of AIS signals may also aid monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems. As the EU fleet is already transmitting both VMS and AIS data, the reason for including this OT is to put increased pressure on other international fleets operating in the area⁴¹ to commit to VMS/AIS transmission as well, initiating a level playing field as has been requested by operators during the progress of developing this MR. The suggested OT as listed in the MR Invitation;

OT 3.4 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals (Obligatory OT)

The following indicators are suggested for OT 3.4 (Table 4.3):

- I_2 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocalization
- I_3 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS), geolocalization

⁴¹ „The parties hereby undertake to promote responsible fishing in Cape Verdean waters on the basis of the principle of non-discrimination between the various fleets fishing in those waters. All technical conservation measures which must be met in order for a fishing licence to be issued, as specified in Appendix 2 of the Annex, shall apply to all

Comments from operator (ORPAGU)

ORPAGU is already using AIS and VMS as it is compulsory. They would like that other fleets fishing in the area would also abide by the rules, in particular the Asian longline fleet (China) promoting a level playing field.

Table 4.3 Indicators related to obligatory OTs in MR1 for CS Cape Verde

Outcome target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator scoring	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 3.1	I_1 Harmonised protocols in place	C	0	Authority, WP2, CCMAR
OT 3.4	I_2 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocated	A	0	Authority, WP6, CSIC
	I_3 Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation	A	0	Authority, WP6, CSIC

4.2 Recommended outcome targets in the Cape Verde case study

The recommended OTs, which are not considered vital to the MR progress aiming to reach the management objectives for the CS, are listed below. These OTs will be addressed more thoroughly in MR2, when more socio-economic data will be available. The FarFish Partners ANAFACO and FarFish RG member OPAGAC have already been consulted for input on the following OTs.

A need for improved scheduling and logistic system for onboard observers on EU vessels has been identified due to lack of coordination, distribution, expenses and support. Thus, the following OT is identified:

OT 3.2 R: Setting of conditions for a better coordination of observer programme: content (protocols, criteria), schedules, processes, sharing of information. This is an OT that will have to be worked on in collaboration between operators and authorities as it includes harmonisation of Cape Verde, EU and ICCAT protocols on onboard observers (Recommended OT)

Information on trade flows within the value chains of Cape Verde i.e. catches of all fleets operating within the Cape Verde EEZ, is very limited. Cape Verdean authorities have therefore very little oversight of what happens to a big part of the catches caught in their EEZ or on the value streams. It is recognised that some of the data relevant for this OT can be confidential information (for example between fishing companies and their customers) and it is therefore expected that the MR draft will take that into consideration i.e. by suggesting what data can be provided, on what format, aggregation

etc. This is also of concern in terms of food safety and value chain development (including local consumption), the following OT is therefore identified:

OT3.3 R: Increase knowledge and data collection of trade flows to include for example destination, utilization, quantity, value. (Recommended OT)

5 Management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning

This section outlines and describes the strategies and key measures by which the operators/authorities plan to achieve the obligatory OTs. Potential risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving the OTs are mentioned, but not found significant for OT 3.1. For OT 3.2, the risk of not receiving the requested data is critical.

5.1 Management strategy

The current management goal to achieve sustainable fisheries under the SFPA agreement is regulated under the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP, distant water fleet), Cape Verde Fisheries Management Plan (PGRM) and ICCAT. Application of best scientific advice is crucial when aiming to achieve sustainable fisheries, and such advice depends on data collection where reliable catch statistics are a key.

In order to make progress in achieving OT 3.1, the management strategy is to perform an analysis of all current catch data protocols, forms and templates, which the EU fleet is obliged to submit to their flag state, Cape Verde and ICCAT. ICCAT performed a similar exercise in 2010, and their methods are described in the final report on ICCAT By-catch and Co-ordination study (ICCAT, 2010).

FarFish (WP2) facilitates this by providing an example reporting template and suggesting how harmonization can be achieved. The discrepancy between reported catches in the databases of Eurostat (EU), ICCAT and Cape Verde will be analysed, aiming to improve the quality of data for comparison and scientific purposes, thereby improving stock assessment, and potentially adding value to development of harvest control rules (HCR) for swordfish and blue shark. Harmonized catch data protocols will ease the workload for vessel owners and may potentially increase the reliability of submitted data. This action will also support the coherence of reported catch statistics reported by EU, flag state, Cape Verde and ICCAT.

ORPAGU, representing the Spanish surface longline fishery which target both swordfish and blue shark, requested that both in the SFPA protocol and in the issuing of fishing licenses it is specified or clearly listed down the species that can be fished. ORPAGU has volunteered to document and submit templates and examples about the level of information contained on their data submissions (both data sheets by paper and electronically), which are very detailed and go above and beyond the requirements of the SFPA and ICCAT in terms of catch reporting by (targeted and by catch) species, observer coverage, etc. Since the entry into force of this requirement in 2012 under the EU Fisheries Control Regulation. ORPAGU is already following a management strategy aiming for sustainable fishery

as they entered a Prospective⁴² Fishery Improvement Project (FIP) “Prospective European Union blue shark and swordfish-longline”⁴³. The FIP is a tool for companies who want to transition their seafood sources towards sustainability over time and prospective FIPs intent to meet the requirement for active FIP within one year, as they are not yet demonstrating enough progress towards sustainability. In order to meet the requirements, the EU surface longline fleet has been concentrating efforts on the implementation of national and regional strategies for conservation of their target species including measures such as minimizing incidental catches, collaboration with the scientific community and finning bans. In 2014, an MSC pre-assessment was conducted for the North and South Atlantic swordfish Spanish longline fishery (CAB, 2016) and the fishery was close to meeting the MSC standard for north and south Atlantic swordfish.

In order to combat IUU and to improve monitoring of the fishery in the Cape Verde EEZ, the fishing activities are monitored by satellite-based systems such as VMS. The EU fleet is obliged to transmit both VMS and AIS according to the SFPA agreement with Cape Verde and Directive 2009/17/EC the vessels >15 m. The management strategy to improve monitoring of the EU fleet is therefore in place and transparent, as data should be available. Yet, the access to of VMS/AIS data by non-EU fleet is close to non-existing, weakening the transparency and sustainability of the fishery. By getting access to VMS data from Cape Verde authorities, for the purpose of protection of the marine environment (including sustainable fish stocks) in accordance to EC No 1224/2009 Art.12, transparency can be increased.

FarFish facilitates this initiative and has requested access to VMS/AIS data from Cape Verde for both EU fleet and non-EU fleet. FarFish intends to analyse this data and compare it with the AIS data obtained from the Global Fishing Watch, in order to validate the compliance on signal transmitting. FarFish and operators suggest that commitment and continuous routine to transmit VMS signals should apply to both EU and non-EU fleets to ensure a level playing field. Transparency of submissions of such VMS signals should create incentives for compliance for VMS transmission and should encourage authorities to give preference to fleets complying with such transparency.

5.2 Management measures

The obligatory OTs for Cape Verde addressed in MR1, can be achieved by adopting to the existing management measures that apply to the EU fleet fishing under the SFPA agreement for Cape Verde, relevant ICCAT recommendations and Cape Verdean PGRM. For the non-EU fleet, the latter two also apply when flag state is a contracting party in ICCAT.

⁴² Prospective FIPs intent to meet the requirement for active FIP within one year, as they are not yet demonstrating progress towards sustainability.

⁴³ <https://fisheryprogress.org/fip-profile/european-union-blue-shark-and-swordfish-longline>

5.2.1 Management measures related to OT 3.1

There are already a number of management measures related to OT 3.1 (harmonising of catch protocols) within the current SFPAs, PGRM and ICCAT. These are as follows:

5.2.1.1 Management measures in the SFPAs relevant for OT3.1

The best scientific advice is based on reliable catch statistics and is described in chapter IV in the Agreement Annex. It states that all EU vessels fishing under the Agreement must keep a fishing logbook, completed by the vessels master each day while in the Cape Verde EEZ. The logbook shall contain records of quantity of each species, identified by its FAO A3 code⁴⁴, including those thrown back to sea, expressed in kilograms of live weight, and where necessary, the number of individual fish. Where applicable, the same must be filled out for discarded fish. The fishing logbook shall be transmitted to the appropriate authority when the vessel passes through a Cape Verdean port. If leaving Cape Verdean EEZ without passing through a Cape Verdean port, the logbook must be submitted to the authorities within 14 days (FarFish, D3.3). Tuna fishing vessels and surface longlines must also send copies of the logbooks to either Institut de recherche pour le développement (IRD), Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO), Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfêra (IPMA) or Instituto Nacional de Desenvolvimento das Pescas (INDP).

The Scientific cooperation on responsible fishing is described in the SFPAs, Article 4 and Appendix 2 in Annex; All technical conservation measures which must be met in order for a fishing licence to be issued, shall apply to all foreign industrial fleets operating in the Cape Verdean fishing zone under technical conditions similar to those applicable to the Union fleets. Given that pelagic sharks may be among the species caught by the union fleet in connection with tuna fisheries and in view of the vulnerability of these species as expressed in ICCAT scientific opinions, any catches of the species in question by longline vessels engaged in fishing under the protocol require particular attention in line with the precautionary principle. The parties shall cooperate with a view to improving the availability and monitoring of scientific data related to the species caught. The parties shall comply with the recommendations and resolutions of the ICCAT regarding the responsible management for fisheries.

The parties shall set up a mechanism for strict monitoring of the fishery where blue shark occurs as either target or bycatch species in order to ensure sustainable exploitation of the resource. The monitoring mechanism shall, in particular, be based on a quarterly exchange of data on shark catches. If in the course of a year these catches exceed 30 % of the reference tonnage referred to in Article 2(2)(a), reinforced monitoring based on a monthly exchange of data and consultation between the parties shall be set up. If in the course of a year such catches exceed 40 % of the reference tonnage referred to above, the Joint Committee shall, where appropriate, adopt further management measures setting a more adequate framework for the longliner fleet's activities.

⁴⁴ <http://www.fao.org/fishery/collection/asfis/en>

Vessels fishing in RFMO area 34 for tunas are also committed to report to ICCAT who is responsible for stock assessment of tuna and tuna like fish. It is important to collect all the data necessary to perform good stock assessment to ensure a sustainable management, and there're are therefore a number of different forms that are to be filled out and delivered to ICCAT. Observers are responsible for collecting much of the data and filling out these forms. These forms can be seen in ICCAT Manual⁴⁵.

5.2.1.2 Management measures in the Cape Verdean management plan relevant for OT 3.1

A review of the PGRM plan is pending and, in the meantime, the plan is implemented by means of Biannual Executive Plans, published in the Boletim Oficial da República de Cape Verde, detailing the regulations and management measures. The current execution of the plan concerns the period 2018-2019. The plan sets out a number of policy restrictions on foreign fishing in general, as well as specific measures in relation to specific fisheries, including foreign fishing (FarFish D3.3).

Fishing for live bait by foreign vessels is prohibited within the 12 nautical miles. Live bait is normally caught within 3 nautical miles, an area reserved exclusively for artisanal fishing; support vessels are however allowed to operate in bays and in non-inhabited areas within 3 nautical miles, exclusively to catch live bait; bait caught under such circumstances shall under no circumstances be marketed for consumption.

5.2.1.3 Management measures within ICCAT relevant for OT 3.1

Fishing entities are obliged to provide the available statistical, biological and other scientific information the Commission may require in order to carry out the objectives of the ICCAT Convention. Non-Eu vessels fishing in Cape Verdean waters such as Japan, Korea, Russia, China, Senegal, Belize, Curacao, El Salvador, are ICCAT Contracting Parties (CP).

ICCAT recommendations for swordfish given in ICCAT Rec. 17-02 and point 8 is related to data collection for SWO; All CPCs catching swordfish in the North Atlantic shall endeavour to provide annually the best available data to the SCRS, including catch, catch at size, location and month of capture on the smallest scale possible, as determined by the SCRS. The data submitted shall be for broadest range of age classes possible, consistent with minimum size restrictions, and by sex when possible. The data shall also include discards (both dead and alive) and effort statistics, even when no analytical stock assessment is scheduled. The SCRS shall review these data annually.

CPCs may allow bycatch of North Atlantic swordfish by vessels not authorized to fish for North Atlantic swordfish pursuant to paragraph 13, if the CPC establishes a maximum onboard bycatch limit for such vessels and the bycatch in question is accounted for within the CPC's quota or catch limit. Each CPC

⁴⁵ <https://www.iccat.int/en/iccatmanual.html>

shall provide in its Annual Report the maximum bycatch limit it allows for such vessels. That information shall be compiled by the ICCAT Secretariat and made available to CPCs.

5.2.2 Management measures related to OT 3.4

There are already a number of management measures related to OT 3.4 (Transmission of VMS signals) within the current SFPAs, PGRM and ICCAT. These are as follows:

5.2.2.1 Management measures in the SFPAs relevant for OT 3.4

Requirements for satellite monitoring system is described in the SFPAs Annex, chapter VII. It states that all vessels must be fitted with Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) to ensure continuous communication of their position to the FMC (Fisheries Monitoring Centre) of their flag state. The FMC shall forward this information to the FMC of Cape Verde. The position reports must include the vessels identification, their geographical position, date and time, speed, and course. In the event of breakdown, the VMS of the vessel shall be repaired or replaced within a month. After that period, the vessel shall no longer be permitted to fish in the Cape Verdean zone. Vessels fishing in the Cape Verdean zone with a defective VMS must send their position messages by e-mail, radio or fax to the FMC of the flag State, at least every four hours, and must provide all the compulsory information.

5.2.2.2 Management measures in the Cape Verdean management plan relevant for OT3.4

VMS is required by Cape Verdean law (amended in Legislative Decree 2/2015 of 9 October) and applies to semi-industrial and industrial fishing vessels, both domestic and foreign; national fishing vessels operating in international waters and/or in third countries; and to fishing vessels used exclusively for aquaculture and recreational fishing. COSMAR operates and hosts the VMS Centre (as well as other monitoring tools such as AIS, surveillance and inspection reports etc.) which is based in Praia.

5.2.2.3 Management measures within ICCAT relevant for OT 3.4, Rec 14-09 GEN

ICCAT recommendation 14-09 require that all CPCs shall implement VMS for its commercial vessel exceeding 20 meters between the perpendiculars ensuring that the vessels shall be equipped with an autonomous system able to automatically transmit a message to the Fisheries Monitoring Centre (FMC) of the flag CPC allowing continuous tracking of the position of a fishing vessel by the CPC of that vessel (Appendix 8). The CPC shall also require that the fishing vessels' autonomous system shall be able to automatically transmit a message to the FMC of the flag CPC allowing continuous tracking of the position of a fishing vessel by the CPC of that vessel. The satellite tracking device shall be fitted on board the fishing vessels enabling the vessel to continuously collect and transmit, at any time, to the FMC of the flag CPC the following data:

- I. the vessel's identification;
- II. the most recent geographical position of the vessel (longitude, latitude) with a margin of error lower than 500 metres, with a confidence interval of 99%;
- III. the date and time of the fixing of the said position of the vessel.

The flag CPC shall also ensure, in cooperation with the coastal State, that the position messages transmitted by its vessels while fishing in waters under the jurisdiction of that coastal State are transmitted automatically and in real time to the FMC of the coastal State that has authorized the fishing activity, provided that due consideration has been given to minimizing the operational costs, technical difficulties, and administrative burden associated with transmission of these messages.

Each CPC shall take appropriate measures to ensure that the VMS messages are transmitted and received and ensure that the masters of fishing vessels flying its flag shall confirm that the satellite tracking devices are permanently operational and that the information identified in paragraph 1.b) is collected and transmitted at least every four (4) hours. Failure is addressed in the REC 14-09 as well.

A new recommendation was published in 2018 Rec 18-10, but it is not active yet. The new Recommendation changes the interval between transmission from four to hourly for purse seine vessels and at least every two hours for all other vessels.

5.3 Internal monitoring of performance towards achieving OTs

Due to the classification of the OTs as environmental/governmental, the operators are not solely responsible for achieving the obligatory OTs 3.1 and 3.4, this responsibility will therefore be shared between operators and the leading authority in WP3. The internal monitoring of development of OT 3.1 and OT 3.4 will be to follow up on the data collection by operators and other FarFish partners.

- List of all current catch reporting forms required for purse seine vessels (to Flag state, EU, ICCAT, Cape Verde)
- List of all current catch reporting forms required for the longline vessels (to Flag state, EU, ICCAT, Cape Verde)
- List of all current catch reporting forms required for the pole and line vessels (to Flag state, EU, ICCAT, Cape Verde)

5.4 Address risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving OTs

The risk in OT 3.1 could be difficulties to collect templates for all data protocols, templates and forms for catch statistics. As all of these templates are publicly available in the SFPA protocol and at ICCAT website, this is considered a very low risk.

The risks related to OT3.1 are:

- Diverse use and need as well as potential new upcoming requirements on data collection (variables, species etc.) from flag state, EU, Cap Verde and ICCAT Agreement on statistical areas for reporting

Risk for FarFish not being able to support harmonisation: Late submission of templates from operators and authorities, although many are made available already (ORPAGU, ICAT, SFPA). A close follow up by operators to submit the templates in time by WP2 should mitigate the risk of not getting the templates in time to perform an analysis.

The risk of not achieving OT3.4 for other foreign fleet fishing in Cape Verde EEZ can be related to the same technical issues experienced by EU fleet transmission of VMS signals and problems in Cape Verde to receive the data. FarFish has requested data on submission of VMS data from FMC in Spain, and there is a risk of not getting the data or very late access to data. There is uncertainty in the reliability of more recent AIS signals to compare with VMS data, but FarFish has got access to AIS data from 2016 from Global Fishing Watch.

The risks related to OT3.4 are:

- Not getting VMS data from the country or the state of the vessel for EU fleet.
- Not getting VMS data from the country for non-EU fleet.
- AIS data deteriorating in quality once the vessels are aware of the existence of GFW (GFW is not releasing data since 2016)
- Risks related to the treatment of data

If EU states do not provide VMS data, there is a possibility of studying legal actions in light of the transparency laws of the Union, this also applies for non-EU countries who also are to respect treaties and FarFish might look for legal actions according to such treaties as well.

5.5 Adaptive planning

Adaptive planning is needed to facilitate immediate adaptation within the planning period to support successful management of fisheries in case of abrupt changes occur, for example political, distribution of fish stocks etc. The nature of the obligatory OTs in this MR does not rely on any data collection which can be exposed to abrupt changes that would require adaptive planning.

6 Monitoring, compliance and sanctions

The nature of the obligatory OTs in this MR entail that operators cannot be made solely responsible for achieving them, so their compliance to the MR1 related to the OTs cannot be monitored in the way suggested in the Guidelines for Management Recommendations (FarFish D3.1). The authorities lead by FarFish WP3 shall monitor that the selected WPs acting as operators within the RFMS concept, comply in means of developing harmonized catch protocols for improved data collection (WP2). For OT 3.4, the operators are responsible for transmission of VMS signals, but WP3 as leading authority need to follow up and/or assist WP6 in data collection of VMS signals for both EU and non-EU vessels. If FarFish succeed in receiving both AIS and VMS data from EU and non-EU countries, it is possible to develop diagnostic tools to detect suspicious dynamics (e.g. Country not providing all VMS data from non-EU countries or the vessels switching off the AIS) and thereby evaluate the proportion of VMS signals transmitted. Potential sanctions are not relevant in this MR as resource users are not fully responsible for achieving the OTs.

7 Documentation

In order to be able to analyse and potentially harmonize catch reporting to improve data collection and the reliability of the reporting, all the required data collection protocols, templates and forms are going to be collected from the EU, Cape Verdean authorities and ICCAT; with information on how to fill them out. The operators representing the longline fleet, ORPAGU will provide a list of all forms they are filling out and submit to authorities, while FMC from Spain and Cape Verde should provide a list of forms they submit to EU and ICCAT. Vessels provide fishing logbooks in paper to Cape Verdean authorities when leaving the Cape Verdean EEZ. CCMAR (WP2) will analyse the collected forms and develop a system to merge or harmonize these data protocols to improve quality and save time for vessel owner to fill in all these forms.

As most of the data is already available; either online or in the documentation systems of FarFish partners and RG members, there is no extra cost expected for this work by either operators nor FarFish partners, as they area already financed for their personnel cost through the FarFish project. Table 7.1 shows what fisheries statistics data is required to be reported to ICCAT and Table 7.2 shows what documentation is required for the suggested indicators for OT 3.1 and OT 3.2.

Table 7.1 Explanation of required Fishery statistics to be reported to ICCAT

Dataset	Form (sub form)
Task I catch statistics	Nominal annual catch of tuna, tuna like and sharks, by region, gear, flag and species, and where possible, by EEZ and High Seas. Catches shall be reported in kilograms, round (live) weight
Task I fleet characteristics	Number of fishing vessels by size classes, gear and flag
Task II catch and effort	Catch and effort statistics by area, gear, flag, species and by month
Task II size data	Actual size frequencies of fish sampled by area, gear, flag, species, and by month and by sex if possible
Catch at size data	Catch at size data for Bluefin, albacore, yellowfin, bigeye and skipjack tunas and swordfish, by gear, sampling area and by sex and by 5x5 degree squares if possible. The ICCAT form 3-6 to show sampling coverage and data substitutions is also required.

Table 7.2 Documentation required for indicators and OT 3.1 and OT 3.4.

OT	Documentation	Responsible	Availability for auditor
OT 3.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICCAT Task I required forms ST10-T1FC: (ST01A, ST01B) ST02-T1NC: (ST02A, ST02B) • ICCAT Task II required forms Catch and effort: ST03-T2CE Size sampling: ST04-T2SZ Catch at size estimations: ST05-CAS⁴⁶ • Catch report to Cape Verde -longline - purse seine - pole and line • SFPA protocol Fishing logbook 	ORPAGU/LDAC/CCMAR ORPAGU/LDAC/CCMAR ORPAGU LDAC LDAC UiT	Internal FarFish report available at the FarFish internal webpage
OT 3.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of active vessels from website www.whofishesfar.eu • Spanish FMC list of VMS transmission data • ICCAT list of VMS regulations, authorization and compliance by gear, fleet and nation 	UiT LDAC/CISC UiT/CISC	Internal FarFish report available at the FarFish internal webpage

⁴⁶ For the species: Bluefin tuna, albacore, yellowfin tuna, bigeye tuna, skipjack tuna and swordfish

8 Planning process

As the nature of the OTs addressed in this MR1 for Cape Verde are ecological/governance, it is not up to the operators organizations to address the issues in above sections, but they are involved in delivering templates for catch protocols and for their transmission of VMS signals. The authorities (WP3) are mostly responsible for the progress towards achieving the OTs and the roles for FarFish partners WP2 and WP6 are clearly defined above. When all catch data protocols are analysed, FarFish will make suggestions on how to harmonize the catch reporting for the EU fleet operating in the Cape Verdean EEZ under the SFPA. The operators will thereafter be consulted and asked to give feedback on these suggestions. Table 8.1 shows a documentation matrix for the Cape Verde case study, where indicators, data sources and responsibility for collecting and processing the data is identified.

Table 8.1 Documentation matrix for the Cape Verde case study

OT		Indicators	Sources/ Data collection	Processing of data	Action/ Responsibility
3.1	Harmonize catch data protocols	I_1	ORPAGU LDAC LDAC CCMAR UiT	CCMAR (WP2)	Operator; ORPAGU, LDAC, Authority: CCMAR
3.4	VMS transmission	I_2 I_3	FMC Spain FMC Cape Verde	CSIC (WP6)	Operator: ORPAGU

Planning process OT3.1

Most of the forms are available online or within the documentation systems of FarFish partners or RG members. These are to be submitted to WP2 leader CCMAR by April 15th 2019.

CCMAR is then to make the templates of all forms available for audit by April 20th 2019.

CCMAR is to analyse and make suggestions for harmonized data protocols to be presented at the FarFish annual meeting in June; where they will be discussed with partner operators.

CCMAR will then finish the first version of harmonized data protocol one month before WP/CS meeting in November 2019, Deadline October 2019.

Tentative planning process OT3.4

Request for Spanish VMS data was submitted in January 2019.

Request for Non-Eu fleet VMS data to Cape Verde authorities (COSMAR) was submitted in February 2019.

Desired reception of VMS data by May 2019.

Working plan when data are available

- 1) Assessment of type and amount of VMS data.
- 2) Overlapping (time and space) analysis between GFW and VMS data.
- 3) Implementation of massive data techniques for cross-comparison.
- 4) Diagnose of the results in terms in inter-comparative compliance EU and non-EU.

First draft on analysis comparing VMS data from EU and non- EU fleet completed by October 2019
FarFish and operators suggest that c and continuous routine

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Summary of ICCAT North Atlantic swordfish

ATLANTIC SWORDFISH SUMMARY		
	<i>North Atlantic</i>	<i>South Atlantic</i>
Maximum Sustainable Yield	13,059 (11,840-14,970) ¹	14,570 (12,962-16,123) ²
Current (2017) Yield ³	10,046 t	10,512 t
Yield in last year used in assessment (2015) ⁴	10,668 t	10,227 t
B _{MSY}	82,640 t (51,580-132,010) ⁵	52,465 t (35,119-80,951) ²
SSB _{MSY}	21,262 t (14,797-27,728) ⁶	Unknown
F _{MSY}	0.17 (0.10-0.27) ¹	0.28 (0.17-0.44) ²
Relative Biomass (B ₂₀₁₅ /B _{MSY})	1.04 (0.82 - 1.39) ⁷	0.72 (0.53 - 1.01) ⁸
Relative Fishing Mortality (F ₂₀₁₅ /F _{MSY})	0.78 (0.62-1.01) ⁷	0.98 (0.70 - 1.36) ⁸
Stock Status (2015)	Overfished: NO Overfishing: NO	Overfished: YES Overfishing: NO
Management Measures in Effect	TAC (2018): 13,200 t [Rec. 17-02] 125/119 cm LJFL minimum size	TAC (2018): 14,000 t [Rec. 17-03] 125/119 cm LJFL minimum size

¹ Average from base case BSP2 and SS models; range corresponding to the lowest and highest 95% CIs from the two models.

² From base case JABBA model with 95% CIs.

³ Provisional and subject to revision.

⁴ Based on catch data available in July 2017 for the stock assessment session.

⁵ From base case BSP2 model, with 95% CIs.

⁶ From base case SS model, with 95% CIs.

⁷ Median and 95% quantiles from base case SS and BSP2 models.

⁸ Median and 95% quantiles from base case JABBA model.

Appendix 2. Summary of ICCAT North Atlantic blue shark

NORTH ATLANTIC BLUE SHARK SUMMARY		
Current Yield (2017)		39,675 t ¹
Yield (2013)		36,748 t ²
Relative Biomass	B ₂₀₁₃ /B _{MSY}	1.35-3.45 ³
	B ₂₀₁₃ /B ₀	0.75-0.98 ⁴
Relative Fishing Mortality	F _{MSY}	0.19-0.20 ⁴
	F ₂₀₁₃ /F _{MSY}	0.04-0.75 ⁵
Stock Status (2013)	Overfished	Not likely ⁶
	Overfishing	Not likely ⁶
Management Measures in Effect:		[Rec. 16-12]

¹ Task I catch.

² Estimated catch used in the 2015 assessments.

³ Range obtained with the Bayesian Surplus Production (BSP) and SS3 models. Value from SS3 is SSF/SSF_{MSY}.

⁴ Range obtained with the BSP model.

⁵ Range obtained with the BSP and SS3 models.

⁶ Although the models explored indicate the stock is not overfished and overfishing is not occurring, the Committee acknowledges that there still remains a high level of uncertainty.

Appendix 3. Species identification by FAO alpha 3 codes used to submission of logbooks, their scientific, English and Spanish name and ICCAT classification of species.

FAO 3A code	English name	Spanish name	Scientific name	ICCAT IccSpGrp
ALB	Albacore	Atún blanco	<i>Thunnus Alalunga</i>	1-Tuna (major sp.)
BET	Bigeye tuna	Patudo	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	1-Tuna (major sp.)
BFT	Atlantic Bluefin tuna	Atún rojo del Atlántico	<i>Thunnus thynnus</i>	1-Tuna (major sp.)
BLM	Black marlin	Aguja negra	<i>Makaira indica</i>	1-Tuna (other sp.)
BSH	Blue shark	Tiburón azul	<i>Prionace glauca</i>	2-Sharks (major sp.)
LMA	Longfin mako	Marrajo carite	<i>Isurus paucus</i>	2-Sharks (other sp.)
MLS	Stiped marlin	Marlín rayado	<i>Tetraptunus audax</i>	1-Tuna (other sp.)
SAI	Sailfish	Pez vela del Atlántico	<i>Istiophorus albicans or platypterus</i>	1-Tuna (major sp.)
SKJ	Skipjack tuna	Listado	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	1-Tuna (major sp.)
SMA	Shortfin mako	Marrajo dientuso	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	2-Sharks (major sp.)
SSP	Shortbill spearfish	Marlín trompa corta	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	1-Tuna (other sp.)
SWO	Swordfish	Pez espada	<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	1-Tuna (major sp.)
WAH	Wahoo	Peto	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	1-Tuna (small t.)
WHM	White marlin	Aguja blanca del Atlántico	<i>Tetraptunus albidus</i>	1-Tuna (major sp.)
YTF	Yellowfin tuna	Rabil	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	1-Tuna (major sp.)
	Miscellaneous fish			

Appendix 4. ORPAGU ICCAT logbook sheet

ZEE: CABO VERDE		ICCAT LOGBOOK For TUNA FISHERY										Palangrero de Superficie		X		
NOMBRE BIQUE		Toneladas Brutas														
BANDERA		Capacidad (M.T.)										DIA		MES	AÑO	Puerto
MATRICULA		CAPITAN										Puerto de Salida				
COMPAÑIA		Fecha										Puerto de Entracia				
DIRECCIÓN		Enviado por:										Días de marea		Días de Pesca		Tripulantes
DATOS		AREA										CAPTURAS				
MES	DIA	Latitud N	Longitud W	Agua °C	Anzuelos	SWO	SMA	BSH	BET	SAI	LMA	SSP	WAH	DOL	LEC	TOTALES
						Espada Nº PESO	Marrajo Nº peso	Quella Nº PESO	Atún Nº PESO	Pez vela Nº PESO	marr. M Nº PESO	Marlín Nº PESO	Peto Nº PESO	Lampuga Nº PESO	escolar Nº PESO	
1																0
2																0
3																0
4																0
5																0
29																0
30																0
31																0
Pesca Mes Especies (solo Kg.)						0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SWO	<i>Xiphias gladius</i> Swordfish															
SMA	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i> Shortfin mako															
BSH	<i>Prionace glauca</i> Blue shark															
BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i> Bigeye tuna															
SAI	<i>Istiophorus albicans</i> Atlantic sailfish															
LMA	<i>Isurus paucus</i> Longfin mako															
SSP	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i> Shortbill spearfish															
WAH	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i> Wahoo															
DOL	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i> Common dolphinfish															
LEC	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i> Escolar															

Appendix 5. SFPA Protocol, Fishing logbook

Appendix 4
Fishing logbook

Vessel name: _____ Flag country: _____ Registration No: _____ Vessel owner: _____ Address: _____		Home range: _____ Agency—(M): _____ Maker: _____ No. of crew: _____ Reporting date: _____ Reported by: _____		Vessel DEPARTED: _____ Month: _____ Date: _____ Year: _____ Port: _____ Vessel RETURNED: _____ No. of days at sea: _____ No. of fishing days: _____ No. of days at sea: _____ No. of nets made: _____ Tty number: _____		Length: _____ Last haul: _____ First catch: _____ Trawl: _____ Other: _____	
Date: _____ Month: _____ Date: _____ Year: _____ Latitude N°: _____ Longitude E°W: _____ Number water trap: _____ No. of traps used: _____ Net type: _____		Fish catch: _____ Species: _____ Weight (kg): _____ No. of fish: _____ Length (cm): _____		Catches: _____ (Strip malin) (White malin) (Black marlin) (Sailfish) (Skipjack) (Miscellaneous fish) (Yellowfin tuna) (Albacore) (Thunnus alalunga) (Thunnus makaira) (Thunnus albacares) (Thunnus albacares) (Thunnus albacares) (Xiphias gladius) (Makaira indica) (Istiophorus albicans) (Katsuwonus pelamis)		Fish used: _____ Species: _____ Weight (kg): _____ No. of fish: _____ Length (cm): _____	

1 — Use one sheet per month and one line per day.
 2 — Tty refers to the logbook file line.
 3 — Indicate the date to the nearest of the month, the hour, the minute and second degree of latitude and longitude, the name to record (S) and (W).
 4 — The last line (landing weight) should be completed only at the end of the trip. Actual weight at the time of unloading should be recorded.
 5 — All information reported herein will be kept strictly confidential.

Species listed in SFPA Fishing logbook

BFT	<i>Thunnus thynnus</i>	Atlantic Bluefin Tuna
YFT	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Yellowfin tuna
BET	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Bigeye tuna
ALB	<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Albacore
SWO	<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Swordfish
MLS/WHM	<i>Tetrapturus audax / Tetrapturus albidus</i>	Strip malin/white marlin
BLM	<i>Makaira indica</i>	Black marlin
SAI	<i>Istiophorus albicans</i>	Sailfish
SKJ	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Skipjack
		Miscellaneous fish

Appendix 6. ICCAT statistical and biological information required

Appendix 1

GUIDELINES AND INSTRUCTIONS CONCERNING THE STATISTICAL AND BIOLOGICAL INFORMATION REQUIRED

Data coverage

Tuna, tuna-like species and pelagic sharks fished in the **ICCAT Convention area** (Atlantic and adjacent seas) as specified below:

- For all species: **2017** (calendar year) data are required.
- **Updates to previous years (up to 2016)** can also be reported (formats specified below) taking into account the current SCRS revision rules:
 - o Provisional and preliminary data (three most recent years: 2016, 2015, 2014): can be updated.
 - o Historical data (before 2014): require a SCRS document explaining and supporting the proposed changes.

Formats

All the data reporting follows the **structures and formats adopted by the SCRS**. These are available at www.iccat.int/en/submitSTAT.htm. NOTE: data provided in the **Annual Reports and/or in other documents are not** considered as being submitted in fulfilment of the requirements of this circular.

Please note that the electronic forms were updated again in 2018 (Version: "**2018a**"), following the recommendations adopted by the SCRS and the Commission in 2017. Thus, only data reported using this version (available at: www.iccat.int/en/submitSTAT.htm) or posterior versions will be taken into account. Please, report all the statistical data to the email account: STATS_info@iccat.int.

Major changes to ICCAT forms:

ST01-T1FC (Task I fleet characteristics): Added in sub-form ST01A (vessel based data) the option to report the vessel tonnage in GT or GRT.

ST04-T2SZ (Task II size frequencies): Adapted to accept reporting multiple years in a unique submission. All the information should now be reported by month (mandatory).

ST05-T2CS (Task II catch-at-size): Renamed from "ST05-CAS", following the SCRS requirements. It was also adapted to accept reporting multiple years in a unique submission. All the information should now be reported by month (mandatory).

ST07-TropSupVes: Adapted to accept reporting multiple years in a unique submission.

ST08-FadsDep (FAD deployments): The form contains all the elements requested under Rec. 16-01 and has been updated to include a year field.

ST09-NatObProg: This form has been revised and shortened, requesting far less detailed operational information.

ST11-ObPrgsInf: The previous form entitled CP45-NatObPrgsInf has been revised and updated, requesting only key information regarding national observer programmes coverage.

Appendix 7. Requested ICCAT datasets and sub forms

Dataset	Form (sub form)
Task I- Fleet characteristics	ST10-T1FC (ST01A, ST01B)
Task I -Nominal catches	ST02-T1NC (ST02A, ST02B)
Task II - Catch and effort	ST03-T2CE
Task II - Size sampling	ST04-T2SZ
Catch at size estimations	ST05-CAS
Support vessel activity	ST07-TropSupVes
FAD Deployments	ST08-FasdDep
National Observer programme data	ST09-NatObProg
Port Sampling data	ST10-PortSamp
National Observer programme meta-data	ST11-ObPrgsInf

Appendix 8. ICCAT Recommendation concerning minimum standards

14-09	GEN
RECOMMENDATION BY ICCAT AMENDING RECOMMENDATION 03-14 BY ICCAT CONCERNING MINIMUM STANDARDS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A VESSEL MONITORING SYSTEM IN THE ICCAT CONVENTION AREA	

IN ACCORDANCE WITH the Needs and Principles set forth in the General Outline of Integrated Monitoring Measures Adopted by ICCAT, adopted by the Commission in 2002 to ensure effective monitoring measures;

CONSIDERING the deliberations of the ICCAT Working Group to Develop Integrated Monitoring Measures, held in Madeira from 26 to 28 May 2003;

RECOGNIZING the developments in satellite-based vessel monitoring systems (VMS), and their utility within ICCAT;

RECOGNIZING the legitimate right of coastal States to monitor the vessels fishing in waters under their jurisdiction;

CONSIDERING that real-time transmission to the Fishing Monitoring Center (FMC) of the coastal State of VMS data of all the vessels (including catching, carrier and support vessels) flying the flag of a CPC authorised to fish ICCAT species enables this coastal State, particularly in the case of a developing State, to ensure the effective implementation of ICCAT conservation and monitoring measures;

THE INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION FOR THE CONSERVATION OF OF ATLANTIC TUNAS (ICCAT) RECOMMENDS THAT:

1. Each flag Contracting Party, Cooperating non-Contracting Party, Entity or Fishing Entity (hereinafter referred to as CPC) shall implement a Vessel Monitoring System (hereinafter referred to as VMS) for its commercial fishing vessels exceeding 20 meters between perpendiculars or 24 meters length overall and:
 - a) require its fishing vessels to be equipped with an autonomous system able to automatically transmit a message to the Fisheries Monitoring Center (hereinafter referred to as FMC) of the flag CPC allowing continuous tracking of the position of a fishing vessel by the CPC of that vessel.
 - b) ensure that the satellite tracking device fitted on board the fishing vessels shall enable the vessel to continuously collect and transmit, at any time, to the FMC of the flag CPC the following data:
 - i) the vessel's identification;
 - ii) the most recent geographical position of the vessel (longitude, latitude) with a margin of error lower than 500 metres, with a confidence interval of 99%;
 - iii) the date and time of the fixing of the said position of the vessel.
 - c) Ensure, in cooperation with the coastal State, that the position messages transmitted by its vessels while fishing in waters under the jurisdiction of that coastal State are transmitted automatically and in real time to the FMC of the coastal State that has authorized the fishing activity, provided that due consideration has been given to minimizing the operational costs, technical difficulties, and administrative burden associated with transmission of these messages.
 - d) In order to facilitate the transmission and receipt of position messages, as described in subparagraph 1(c), the FMC of the flag State and the FMC of the coastal State shall exchange their contact information and notify each other without delay of any changes to this information. The FMC of the coastal State shall notify the flag State FMC of any interruption in the reception of consecutive position messages. The transmission of position messages between the FMC of the flag State and that of the coastal State shall be carried out electronically using a secure communication system.
2. Each CPC shall take appropriate measures to ensure that the VMS messages are transmitted and received, as specified in paragraph 1.

3. Each CPC shall ensure that the masters of fishing vessels flying its flag shall ensure that the satellite tracking devices are permanently operational and that the information identified in paragraph 1.b) is collected and transmitted at least every four (4) hours. In the event of a technical failure or non-operation of the satellite tracking device fitted on board a fishing vessel, the device shall be repaired or replaced within one month, unless the vessel has been removed from the list of authorized LSFVs. After this period, the master of a fishing vessel is not authorized to commence a fishing trip with a defective satellite tracking device. Furthermore, when a device stops functioning or has a technical failure during a fishing trip, the repair or the replacement has to take place as soon as the vessel enters a port; the fishing vessel shall not be authorized to commence a fishing trip without the satellite tracking device having been repaired or replaced.
4. Each CPC shall ensure that a fishing vessel with a defective satellite tracking device shall communicate to the FMC, at least daily, reports containing the information in paragraph 1(b) by other means of communication (radio, telefax or telex).
5. CPCs are encouraged to extend the application of this Recommendation to their fishing vessels of less than 20 meters between perpendiculars or 24 meters length overall if they consider this to be appropriate to ensure the effectiveness of ICCAT conservation and management measures.
6. The Commission shall review this Recommendation no later than 2017 and consider revisions to improve its effectiveness, including by changing the transmission frequency, taking into account SCRS advice, the different nature of various fisheries, cost implications, and other relevant considerations, including generally accepted MCS best practices.
7. To inform this review, the SCRS is requested to provide advice on the VMS data that would most assist the SCRS in carrying out its work, including frequency of transmission for the different ICCAT fisheries.
8. This measure shall repeal and replace Recommendation 03-14.

SENEGALESE CASE STUDY

Deliverable No. 4.3

Project acronym:

FarFish

Project title:

Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

Grant agreement No: **727891**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme

Start date of project: **1st June 2017**

Duration: **48 months**

Due date of deliverable:	31/01/2019
Submission date:	23/09/2020
File Name:	FarFish_D4.3_MR1 Senegal
Revision number:	02
Document status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public

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Deliverable D4.3

Management Recommendation 1

Senegal

23/09/2020

Executive Summary

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) for the black hake fishery under the SFPA agreement between Senegal and the EU. The EU vessels currently targeting black hake are trawlers from Spain. Two different species of black hake are targeted and there is a lack of distinction between the two in catch reports, observers reports and catch statistics. The two black hake species are assessed as one by the Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries (CECAF).

The Senegalese Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Affairs (MPAM) and the Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG Mare) are considered the competent authorities in this FarFish case study; but FarFish Work Package 3 (WP3) acts as the leading authority in the process of developing the MRs, considering input from the authorities and other stakeholders. The operators are represented by the Long-Distance Advisory council (LDAC) and the Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín (OPROMAR) from Spain, assisted by FarFish Work Package 4 (WP4).

This MR1 is developed following the “draft General Guidelines for making MRs” developed in FarFish ([D3.1](#)) and is based on the Management Recommendation Invitation ([D3.2](#)), where the outcome targets (OTs) are proposed. Only the obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version of the MR. The proposed OTs are based on input from Management Plan Zero ([D4.1](#)), input from operators at the MR Kick-off meeting ([D4.2](#)) and additional stakeholder meetings facilitated by FarFish stakeholder interaction (WP1), and input from FarFish Work package (WP)/Case study (CS) leader meeting in Mindelo (Cape Verde, Nov. 2018). The recommended OTs will be addressed in the second version of the MR.

The aim of this MR is to improve data collection to promote sustainable fisheries and to improve monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS). The subsequent OTs are related to improved data collection on bycatch in black hake fisheries and on species discrimination of the two black hake species in catch. The third OT is related to monitoring by satellite systems, supporting Senegal’s National action plan to combat IUU fisheries. The OTs are classified to ecological and governance dimension and we acknowledge that the operators cannot be solely made responsible for achieving the OTs. It must therefore be a joint effort between authorities and operators to make progress in this MR. Indicators are suggested to measure the performance of the OTs, and the strategy for achieving OTs is outlined. The strategies do not affect any of the current management conservation measures by EU or Senegal.

A regional approach is outside the scope of FarFish, but should be applied, as black hake is considered a shared stock between several coastal states, and actions taken in Senegalese EEZ is only part of the solution for a sustainable fishery of black hake.

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Abbreviations & concepts/definitions

AIS	Automatic Identification System
BSP2	Bayesian surplus production model (stock assessment model applied for N. Swordfish by ICCAT)
CCMAR	Centre of Marine Science (Portugal)
CECAF	Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries
CECAF-SC	Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries Scientific Committee
CETMAR	Centro Tecnológico del mar Fundación CETMAR
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy (EU)
Cmsy	Catch msy
COREWAM	Conservation and Research of West African Aquatic Mammals (Senegal)
CRODT	Oceanographic Research Centre of Dakar-Thiaroye (Senegal)
CPUE	Catch per Unit Effort
CS	Case Study
CSC	Joint Scientific Committee on Fisheries Agreement between Senegal and the EU
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
DG MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, EC. This Commission department is responsible for EU policy on maritime affairs and fisheries
DPM	Directorate of Maritime Fisheries
DPSP	Directorate of Fisheries Protection and Surveillance
ERS	Electronic Recording Systems
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FarFish RG	FarFish Reference Group
HCR	Harvest Control Rule
IEO	The Spanish Institute of Oceanography
IMO	International Maritime Organization
ISRA	Senegalese Institute of Agricultural Research
IUU	Illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing
LDAC	Long Distance Advisory council, EU fisheries body representing stakeholders of both fishing sector and other groups of interest, FarFish Partner
MPAM	Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Affairs
MATIS	Icelandic Food and Biotech R & D Institute (Iceland)
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance
MPO	Management Plan Zero
MSY	Maximum sustainable yield
NOFIMA	Is the fusion of several Norwegian food research institutes and covers all food sectors and links in the value chain, FarFish Partner
OPRPOMAR	Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín, Spain, FarFish Partner
RBM	Results-Based Management
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
UIT	University of Tromsø- The Arctic University of Norway, FarFish Partner
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System

Concepts/definitions

Indicator	A variable, pointer or index related to a criterion. Indicators are selected such that their variations reflect variations in key elements of the fishery resource, the social and economic well-being of the sector and the sustainability of the ecosystem. The position and trend of an indicator in relation to reference points or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. Indicators provide a bridge between objectives and actions (source: FAO 1999).
Management goals	The higher-order objective to which a management intervention is intended to contribute (OECD 2011). A management goal is derived from a management principle (constitutional-order) and is specified into a set of more operational management objectives (collective-order).
Management intervention	Strategies or instruments aimed to impact the state of a fishery with reference to authorized objectives. Examples are input and output controls and economic measures.
Management measures	Can be technical (e.g. gear selectivity etc.), input (effort)/output (catch) control, right based.
Management objectives	Fisheries management objectives are typically framed within the overall concept of sustainable development, and may reflect one or more of the various dimensions and criteria that relate to it (FAO 1999). Operators through setting and implementing management measures control OTs.
Management Plan (MP)	A fisheries management plan is a formal arrangement between a fishery management authority and interested parties which identifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, details the agreed objectives for the fishery and specifies the management rules and regulations which apply to it and provides other details about the fishery which are relevant to the task of the management authority (Source: FAO 2002).
Management Recommendation (MR)	In RFMS, the management recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority and operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery. In RFMS, the formal responsibility for developing the management plan is delegated to an operator.
Management strategies	In FarFish context, it means the strategies applied to achieve OTs
Outcome Target (OT)	Outcome targets (OTs) are specific and measurable requirements that are set by an authority to make management goals operational. An OT is a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B') or a statement of presence or absence of some entity. On the basis of relevant information, this statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time ⁵⁴ . For instance, the management objective that "the fishery should be biologically sustainable" could be expressed in terms of one or more OTs such as 'Catch < 20 000t; 'bycatch < 20%'; SSB > 30 000t; 'a catch reporting system is present', etc.
Reference point	A classification device, defined in relation to the measure of an indicator, for distinguishing different management relevant states of the system under management. A Biological Reference Point is a metric of stock status. A Target Reference Point indicates a state of a system which is considered desirable and at which management action should aim. A Limit Reference Point indicates a state of a system, which is considered to be undesirable, that one therefore should seek to avoid through relevant management action.
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) is a fisheries management approach developed within the FP7 project EcoFishMan . The RFMS is an adaptive management approach that is results-based and ecosystem-based. The RFMS attempts to reduce micromanagement by involving stakeholders and increase the degree of co-management by delegating management responsibilities to resource users.

1 Introduction

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) from European operators active in Senegal waters under the SFP agreement (2014-2019). The MR1 is founded on Results-Based Management (RBM) principles and based on the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) approach (Figure 1), which was developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan (Silva et al., 2014, Santiago et al., 2015, Nielsen et al., 2017). Basically, the MR is an agreement between competent authorities, relevant operators and potentially other stakeholders. In the MR, strategies are defined to achieve outcome targets (OTs) which are established by authorities in the MR invitation (D3.2) to support sustainable fisheries (FarFish, 2018a), while following the draft General Guidelines for making MRs (D3.1) developed in the FarFish project (FarFish, 2018b).

Figure 1: The RFMS process. The responsibilities of each of the three entities are demonstrated with different colours. Authority: red/Operators: blue/ Auditors: yellow (FarFish, 2018b).

The partners in the fishery and their respective roles and responsibilities are identified in the MR, which also provides a detailed overview of the fishery and the geographical boundaries for the MR, which were outlined in the Management Plan zero (MP0) in D4.1 (FarFish, 2018c). The authority is the organizational entity acting as the authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery (e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission). They oversee the RFMS process and issue the “MR invitation”, which includes a clear specification of measurable OTs, set in order to operationalize the goals of existing policies and the local management objectives.

The operator is defined as an organized group of resource users, e.g. an association of fishermen or stakeholders with rights in a given fishery. It is the organizational unit with delegated authority to develop management recommendations based on the OTs set by the authority and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority. In line with the RFMS approach, the engagement of stakeholders is highly prioritized in FarFish. At the MR kick-off meeting

in Vigo (Spain, June 2018), operators representing the distant water fleet (DWF) from the European Union expressed their interests and needs (FarFish, 2018d), which were relevant for the development of the MR Invitation and defining the OTs, in which this MR1 will address

1.1 Partners involved in MR1

The leader of Task 3.3 (Authority role within RFMS) in FarFish, MATIS, acts as the leading authority within the project, whilst considering input from relevant authorities, e.g. Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Affairs (MPAM) and DG MARE (Aims of MR1 for the southeast

This MR1 applies to the fishery in the SEAFO area (Figure 2Figure). The aim of this MR is to serve good practice recommendations, focusing on improved monitoring for sustainable fisheries in the SEAFO convention area to support maintenance of international framework for future use and protection. The SEAFO is a modern and well-functioning RFMO, operating in an area with limited capacity of coastal states and managing fisheries on poor data stocks. SEAFO has in place a well-developed monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS) system. The management of the SEAFO fisheries is therefore well suited to function as a showcase and illustrate good practice recommendations, committing both authorities and operators.

Figure 2: Maps of SEAFO area and the FAO area 47. Source: www.seafo.org

). The European operators qualified to respond to the first MR Invitation for Senegal on OTs related to black hake are the Long Distance Advisory Council⁴⁷ (LDAC) represented by its Executive Secretary Alexandre Rodríguez and Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín⁴⁸ (OPROMAR). Two members from OPRMAR have participated in the MR1 meetings.

Table 1: MR1 Senegal partners involved, geographical range, target species, main aims and period

MR basis	MR1 Senegal		
Partners involved	Authorities: WP3, MPAM, DG MARE		
	Operators: WP4, LDAC, OPRMAR		
	Auditor: WP5, SYNTESA		
Target species	Common name	Scientific name	FAO code
	Tropical African hake	<i>Merluccius polli</i>	HKB
	Senegalese hake	<i>Merluccius senegalensis</i>	HKM
Geographical range	The Senegalese coast extends between 16°04'N (St. Louis, northern border with Mauritania) and 12°20'N (Cap Roxo, southern border with Guinea-Bissau) that encloses Gambian waters (13°05'N13°36'N).		
Fleets	EU fleet: Spain Demersal trawler		
Main aims of MR	The main aims this MR1 is to improve data collection and monitoring, especially for bycatch and for the proportion of the two black hake species in catch. In		

⁴⁷ <http://ldac.eu/>

⁴⁸ <http://opromar.com/>

	addition, FarFish aim to improve monitoring and control by utilizing the latest available satellite systems and tools.
MR planning period	Lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021)

LDAC has a nominal composition of 60% of fishing sector organisations (including catching, processing and marketing sectors, and trade unions). The remaining 40% is represented by other groups of interests (mainly environmental and development NGOs). OPROMAR represents 35 fishing companies including demersal trawlers, surface longliners and purse-seiners vessels. Currently, they have two trawlers authorized to fish in the Senegalese EEZ, operating under the license based on the terms of the SFPA, targeting black hake. The leader for work package 4 (WP4) in FarFish, UiT - The Arctic University of Norway, assists the representatives for operators in the development of the MR1.

1.2 Aims of MR1 for the Senegal case study

This MR1 applies to the EU Fishery for deep-sea demersal fishery targeting mainly black hake in Senegal EEZ, FAO subdivision 34.3.11, 34.3.12 and 34.3.13 (Figure 2). The black hake fishery target two different species, Tropical African hake (*Merluccius polli*) and Senegalese hake (*Merluccius senegalensis*). There is a lack of knowledge about the proportion of the two species caught in Senegalese waters. To support sustainable fisheries, FarFish aim is to address the availability of bycatch data in the black hake fishery, enhance data collection for species identification of black hake in catches and support the fight against illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (IUU) in Senegalese EEZ.

Figure 2: Left: Map of Northwest Africa- Eastern Central Atlantic (FAO Fishing area 34). The Mauritanian EEZ is located in subdivisions 34.3.11 and 34.1.32. Source: García-Isarc et al., (2016). Right: Senegal EEZ. Source: Flanders Marine Institute; www.marineregions.org

1.3 Current Management Plan in Senegal, Common Fisheries Policy and relevant recommendations by CECAF and the Joint Scientific Committee (CSC)

The fishing regulations in Senegal are based on two main texts, Law No. 98-32 of 14 April 1998 on the Maritime Fishery Code (well-known as "the Code of 1998") and Decree no. 98-432 of 10 June 1998 laying down the detailed rules for the application of the law on the maritime fishing code. A new Maritime Fisheries Code was adopted in 2015, whereas the main objective is to increase penalties against IUU fishing, to organize management of fisheries, and to ban the manufacture and import of monofilament and multifilament nets. The Senegalese Fisheries Code establishes the principle for the conservation, management and monitoring measures of the various fisheries, through the establishment of fisheries management plans (FarFish, 2018e).

Senegalese vessels and inspectors carry out monitoring and control at sea in the Senegalese fishing zones. Vessel monitoring system (VMS) has been mandatory since 2006 and the Directorate of Fisheries Protection and Surveillance (DPSP) is responsible for the surveillance of marine and inland fisheries (FarFish, 2018e). Senegal adopted a strategy against IUU fishing in 2013, where the main objective is to eradicate IUU fishing in the Senegalese EEZ by strengthening the means of fisheries surveillance and better coordination of interventions and actions at national, regional and international levels, the national action plan to combat IUU fishing requires external support in order to be implemented though (FarFish, 2018e). EU supported strengthening of control and monitoring of fishing activities in the Senegalese EEZ during the last protocol.

The European Union has also established a system concerning fishing activities of Union fishing vessels fishing outside Union waters under SFPAs agreements and on the high seas⁴⁹ and the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) requires SFPAs to be limited to surplus catches. EU has reformed the CFP, which came into effect in January 2014, state that all EU fishing activities, inside and outside EU waters, and are subject to the same environmental and other standards (EC 2017). Thus, the EU must conduct its external fleet in accordance with the objectives and principles set out in Articles 2 and 3 of the CFP. According to Article 2, those objectives include the application and promotion of the precautionary approach to ensure that the stocks targeted are higher levels that deliver MSY by 2020 at the latest, the application of the ecosystem principle, the promotion of the collection of scientific data and the gradual elimination of discards

⁴⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32017R2403>

The main objective of the CFP is to ensure that fishing activities are environmentally, economically and socially sustainable and are managed consistently with the objectives of achieving economic, social and employment benefits, and of restoring and maintaining fish stocks above levels which can produce maximum sustainable yield and that they are contributing to the availability of food supplies. Additionally, the union has committed itself to Sustainable Development Goal 14⁵⁰ (SDG 14) and Sustainable Development Goal 12⁵¹ (SDG 12). EU vessels operating under the SFPA agreement shall comply with all technical conservation measures as set out in the SFPA protocol. The CFP stresses the need to promote the objectives of CFP internationally, ensuring that Union-fishing activities outside Union waters area based on the same principles and standards as those applicable under Union law, while promoting a level playing field for Union operators and third-country operators. In 2014, the European Commission required the entire fishery fleet >15 m to install Automatic Identification System (AIS) Class A transmitters (Shelmerdine, 2015).

AIS is a compulsory monitoring system for vessels over 300 gross tons (GT) engaged on international voyages is the which share real-time information of ship traffic. The IMO Convention for the Safety Of Life At Sea (SOLAS) Regulation V/19.2 requires vessels to operate AIS Class A on-board at all times, unless there are valid security reasons to turn it off, temporarily. The AIS was intended to increase security at sea and support ship-to-ship collision avoidance, but as AIS transposes dynamic information such as ships position, course, speed, type of ship, navigational status in addition to IMO number, the processed AIS data can provide insights and information for regulatory bodies and researchers. Tracking AIS signals may aid monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems.

The FAO/CECAF working group on the Assessment of Demersal Resources – northern subgroup, contribute to the management of demersal resources is northwest Africa. The provide assessment of the state of the stocks and fisheries to ensure optimal and sustainable use of resources in African coastal countries (FAO 2018b), including the black hake. The black hake is, according to the most recent assessment, fully exploited. CECAF has informed managers of the state of concern of some demersal stocks in their countries, so that they can implement the recommendations developed by the CECAF working group organized by FAO.

The Joint Scientific Committee (CSC) on the Fisheries Agreement between Senegal and EU has made several recommendations for EU fishery under Category 1: Deep demersal species (mostly black hake). These are concerning the importance of harvesting, sharing and analysing scientific observations data aboard ships and difficulties implementing obligations in of the Agreement (Fall et al., 2018). Given the high level of catches in the whole sub region the last years, the fishing mortality is high and catch level in the sub region is not considered sustainable in the long term. Following, CSC support FAO/CECAF

⁵⁰ SDG14: conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

⁵¹ SDG12: ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns and their targets

recommendation to reduce the fishing mortality and thereby apply a precautionary approach, especially the catch of black hake as an bycatch species in other fisheries, especially in Mauritania (Fall et al, 2018).

CSC also recommend a more frequent monitoring of the productivity of black hake at a regional level by reinforcement of the data collection via fishing journals and the placement of observer programmes onboard hake fishing vessels, thus in all the vessels where black hake occurs, specifically by the vessels targeting shrimp (both high seas and coastal), regardless of flag state.

In the recent Ex-ante evaluation of the SFPA agreement between Senegal and EU, it is stated that the renewal possibilities to maintain deep-sea fishing opportunities needs to be based on an in-depth analysis of the state of the black hake stock to ensure that EU vessels to an exploitable surplus in Senegal's waters, as required under the CFP (Caillart, 2019).

1.4 Identity of Fishery

The current SFPA covers the period from 20th November 2014 to 19th November 2019 and allows for 28 EU seiner vessels and eight pole-and-line vessels, targeting highly migratory species in Senegalese EEZ. The vessels targeting tuna (TAC 14,000 tons) are from Spain and France. Two trawlers are allowed to target deep Sea demersal species (TAC 2,000 tons) (Table 2). The black hake quota includes two different species, i.e. tropical African hake (*Merluccius polli*) and Senegalese hake (*Merluccius senegalensis*), which have been denominated under the generic name of black hake *Merluccius ssp.* for more than 60 years (FAO, 2018c). Due to their morphological resemblance and overlapping distribution at certain depths and areas, both species are mixed in catches and are commonly marketed as *Merluccius spp.* (FAO, 2016). They are also reported as black hake in catch statistics. Neither the SFPA agreement, nor the stock assessment recommendation by FAO/CECAF discriminate between the two species, even though they have different biological characteristics and should therefore preferably be managed separately (Fernández-Peralta et al., 2017).

Table 2: Fishing opportunities by categories, allowed catch, gear and utilization. Source: Caillart 2019

EU categories	Species	Allowed catch	Gear	Utilization 2017	Utilization average (2015-2018)
Deep-sea demersal	Black hake Allowed bycatch: 7% cephalopods 7% crustaceans 15% fish	2,000 t	Bottom trawl	105%	66%
Highly migratory species	Tunas	14,000 t	Seiners Pole and line	75% 100%	100% 77%

2 Fishery overview

Spanish demersal trawlers are the only foreign fleet allowed to target black hake in Senegalese waters (Figure 3), but there are also Senegalese trawlers that target these species. In general, the species are targeted at depths between 150 and 1000 m (Fall et al., 2018). In 2017, four Spanish vessels were targeting black hake under the SFPA agreement; (1) Manuel Nores, (2) Ivan Nores, (3) Villa de Marin and (4) Fuente de Macenlle. In the north, European freezer boats are fishing a little deeper than the Senegalese vessels, with most of their activity between 500-600m, frequently exceeding the 600m isobath, with a boat fishing further north between 100-300m. Senegalese trawlers still fish between 300-600m.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of EU hake activity in Senegal's fishing zone in 2017 (three freezer trawlers and one fresh fish vessel). Source: Fall et al., (2018) based on data from IEO-SGP (Spain).

The catches of black hake in the Senegalese EEZ have been highly variable in the period from 1983 to 2017, with some periods with no fishery at all (Figure 4).

Figure 4: EU catch of black hake in Senegalese EEZ in the period from 1983 to 2017.
 Source data 1983-2014 FAO 2018a

The catches in Senegal have been increasing since 2015 and they now constitute a larger part of the total catch in North region of CECAF zone (Figure 5). The majority of black hake in Senegalese EEZ is taken by the Senegalese industrial fleet (two vessels in 2015, three in 2016/2017 and 4 in 2018) taking on average 96,3% of all black hake catches (Table 3Table, Figure 7, Caillart, 2019). The catch taken by Senegalese industrial fleet has been increasing during the last SFP agreement (2014-2019). According to IEO studies in Morocco and Mauritania, the maximum overlap of the species are at depths between 300-350 m in Mauritania and between 500 and 600 m in Morocco (Fall et al., 2018). Their maximum overlap depth in Senegalese waters has not been documented yet.

Figure 5: Catches (tonnes) of black hake, *Merluccius polli* and *M. senegalensis* in the north of CECAF area.
 Source: FAO (2018)

Table 3: Black hake catches in the fishing zone of Senegal by the different fleet segments. Source: Caillart (2019).

Fleet	2015	2016	2017	2018
EU trawlers				
Number of vessels	2	2	2	2
Catch (tons)	1,394	138	1,700	1,237*
Senegalese demersal fish trawlers				
Number of vessels	2	3	3	4
Catch (tons)	3,822	3,781	3,924	n.a
Other trawlers**				
Catch (tons)	102	149	130	
Artisanal fishing				
Catch (tons)		25	32	
Total catch (tons)	5,318	4,093	5,786	

*provisional data extracted from Aggregated Catch Data Reporting (ACDR) database 5/2/2019

** mainly deep demersal trawlers deep shrimp

Important bycatch species reported by Spanish vessels are cephalopods (mainly *Todarodes sagittatus* and *Todaropsis eblanae*), deep sea shrimp (mainly *Aristeus varidens*) and other fish (main species St.Peter and Monkfish *Lophius.sp*) (Fall et al., 2018). There are differences in the landings of the two species of cephalopods between fleets and years, which could be due to confusion in the recording of these cephalopods in logbooks. Boarding observers could provide a more accurate proportion of these species in the catches. According to the CSC annual report 2018, the bycatch data for the Senegalese fleet is not available (Fall et al., 2018).

2.1 Recent trends- EU catch statistics and EU fleet

In the period from 2015 to 2017, the landings from Spanish DWF targeting black hake in Senegalese waters shifted from being dominated by the fresh trawler fleet to the freezer trawlers (Figure). In 2015, the fresh trawler landings accounted for 82.2% of total black hake landings by EU fleet in Senegal, but in 2017 the fishery shifted to 1.5% fresh and 98.5% from freezer trawlers (Fall et.al, 2018). Although the historically most important European fleet has been the fresh hake fishery, the freezer trawlers are now dominating. Four vessels have been utilizing the fishing opportunities in Senegal in the SFPA period, three freezer trawlers and one fresh fish trawler. In 2015, one freezer and one fresh fish trawler were fishing in Senegalese waters for 186 days, only for 21 days in 2016 and 246 days in 2017. The total catches by the EU fleet were 1,394 tons in 2015, 138 tons in 2016 and 1,700 tons in 2017, approaching the full utilization of the fishing opportunity (Table 3).

Total catches of black hake in Senegalese EEZ, both by EU vessels and Senegalese vessels, amounted close to 6,000 tons in 2017 (Figure 7, Caillart, 2019) and the average total catch in Senegalese EEZ in the period 2015-2017 was 5,066 tons. The EU catch constituted for 26.2%, 3.4% and 29.4% of the total catch in the Senegalese EEZ in 2015, 2016 and 2017 respectively (Fall et al., 2018). This accounts for less than 10% of the total EU catches of black hake in this sub region (compared 70% in Mauritania).

Figure 6: Annual catch of black hake *Merluccius spp.* by EU fleet in Senegalese EEZ by freezer trawl (grey) and fresh/ice trawlers (white). Source data: Fall et al., (2018)

Figure 7: Total catch of black hake in Senegal EEZ in the period 2015-2017 by EU and Senegal. Source: Caillart (2019).

2.2 Stock status of target species

The black hake is a shared resource in the sub-region between Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal and Gambia and the two species *M. polli* and *M. senegalensis* are generally assessed as one *Merluccius* spp. The stock is considered fully exploited (although not overfished, $B_{cur} > B_{0.1}$) by the FAO/CECAF Working group on the Assessment of Demersal Resources Subgroup North in 2017, as shown in Table 4 (FAO, 2018a).

Table 4: Summary of stock assessment of black hake stocks in CECAF North area in 2017 and management recommendations. Source: FAO (2018a)

	Catches (tonnes) 2016 [Average 2012-2016]	$B_{cur}/B_{0.1}$	$F_{cur}/F_{0.1}$
Sub-regional stock of black hake: <i>Merluccius polli</i> and <i>M. senegalensis</i>	16,972 [9,668]	115%	137%
Evaluation	Fully exploited - The catch level of the last year is not sustainable in the short term. This stock has also been evaluated by other models (Bayesian and CMSY which give the same situation as Biodyn ⁵²)		
Management Recommendations	Given the relatively low level of effort targeting black hake and the bycatch of these species in 2016 (7,076 tons), the Working Group recommends that the necessary steps be taken to reduce bycatch at the average of the 2014-2015 period (3,300 tons)		

Due to an increased fishing mortality exceeding $F_{0.1}$ (137%), there is considered a risk of overexploitation of the stock in short-term if the current catch levels are maintained (FAO, 2018b). The catch levels during the last years have been at approximately 17,000 t in the whole sub-region, which is well above MSY that is estimated to be 10,900 tons (FAO 2018b). CECAF recommend that steps should be taken to reduce the bycatch of black hake in non-hake fisheries to the 2014-2015 levels i.e. 3,300 tons (FAO, 2018a). The total catch of black hake is now higher than total catch of white hake in the area, as shown in Figure .

⁵² Biodyn: Assessment tool, spreadsheet approach assists understanding of models and allows for adaptation, here for Schaefer surplus model. Bayesian refers to statistical method applied.

Figure 8: Capture of hake in northern zone of CECAF (1990-2016). Source: FAO/CECAF (2018b)

2.3 Specific challenges in CS related to black hake fishery

The listed challenges in the CS of Senegal are identified by the CS leader from COREWAM and aided by the ISRA/CRODT partner (FarFish, 2018c), expressed by stakeholders at the MR Kick-off meeting and other stakeholder meetings (FarFish, 2018d), and from the CSC annual report (2018) and in the SFPA evaluation (DG MARE, 2019). These are summarized as follows:

2.3.1 Insufficient availability/reporting of bycatch data in the black hake fisheries

There are concerns related to sharing and analysing of observation reports data and difficulties related to the implementation of obligations in of the Agreement related to such data (Fall et al., 2018). There are also challenges related to logistic and deployment of European observers, which relate to the fact that the EU fleet targeting black hake do less frequent trips. Reporting of bycatch is a joint responsibility by the master of fishing vessel and observers.

The EU vessels are obliged to report their catches in accordance to chapter IV in the Annex of the Protocol of the SFPA Agreement. On a daily basis, they shall transmit the fishing logbook by the Electronic Reporting System (ERS) data to the Fisheries Monitoring Centre (FMC) of their flag state. This FMC shall automatically, and immediately, send the data to the Senegalese FMC. In the electronic logbook of EU vessels, they shall record the quantity of each species caught and kept on board as target species or bycatch, or discarded, for each fishing operation. The allowed bycatch includes 7% of cephalopods, 7% of crustaceans and 15% of other deep-water demersal fish that shall be calculated at the end of each trip, in relation to the total catch weight, in accordance with Senegalese regulations.

The observers onboard the vessels shall, according to section 5 Chapter IV in the Annex of the Protocol, submit a report of his observations to the master of the vessel before leaving the vessel. Both the observer and the master shall sign this observer report. This report shall also include a verification of the percentages of bycatches and estimate the discarded catches.

Senegalese observers following the obligation stated in the protocol have observed the trips of the EU fishing trawl fleet. However, the Senegalese observers are not providing their observers' report to the master of the vessel and in general very little feedback, thus not encouraging transparency and no incentives for operators to cooperate. The observer's reports have not been made available to the scientific institutes either, as obliged by the protocol.

The challenges related to logistic and deployment of European observers relate to the fact that the EU fleet targeting black hake do less frequent trips. To address the complications related logistics and deployment of European observers to ensure a sufficient coverage program, the IEO has proposed to share their methodology of common scientific observation, which would also include training of Senegalese observers in simplified taxonomic differentiation of the two species of black hake as described in Annex 5 in CSC report of 2018.

Regarding the Senegalese trawlers, there are no record of observers on board as this initiative is voluntary. In the absence of comprehensive datasets of catch and effort; lack of sampling in length; and information on discards at sea, the CSC has not been able to produce a precise diagnosis on the state of the stock. However, it has reflected the different interactions existing between fleet segments, being the Senegalese bottom trawlers, the ones representing the majority of the catch.

There is an urgent need to improve this part of the reporting as expressed in the last CSC Reports (2018) and in the Ex-ante report of 2019 (Caillart, 2019).

2.3.2 Data limitation for sustainable conservation and separate stock assessment of the two species of black hake

Due to their morphological resemblance and overlapping occurrence at certain depths, both species of black hake are mixed in catches and commonly marketed as *Merluccius* spp (FAO, 2016). Neither in the SFPA agreement, nor in the stock assessment by CECAF, is it discriminated between the two species, even though they have different biological characteristics and should therefore preferably be managed separately (Fernández-Peralta et al., 2017). The two species are reported together as black hake in catch statistics by CECAF/FAO.

2.3.3 Insufficient monitoring of the fishery

The fight against IUU fisheries is important to ensure sustainable fisheries and for promoting a level playing field for all fleets. Senegal adopted a strategy against IUU fishing in 2013, but in order to combat IUU fishing external support is required.

EU vessels are obliged to transmit their position at all times with a satellite monitoring system (VMS). All EU vessels holding a fishing authorization through the SFPA agreement shall be equipped with a satellite monitoring system (Vessel Monitoring System) to enable automatic and continuous communication of their position, every two hours, to the Fishing Monitoring Centre (FMC) of their flag state. The FMC of the flag state shall ensure the automatic processing and if necessary, the electronic transmission of the position messages which shall be recorded in a secure manner and kept for a period of three years.

In 2014, the European Commission required the entire EU fishery fleet >15 m to install Automatic Identification System (AIS) Class A transmitters (Shelmerdine, 2015). As AIS is an open source information system, the competitors of the EU fleet may continuously monitor the EU operators transmitting AIS. This can give them indications, based on their interpretation of the AIS positions over time, of where their fishing activity might take place. If non-EU fleets do not comply by the same rules, the level playing field is undermined.

3 Outcome targets and indicators

This chapter identifies the OTs and associated indicators established to provide measurable performance goals for the EU distant water fleet fishery under the SFPa agreement between Senegal and the EU. The OTs are classified as obligatory or recommended, with a certain degree of flexibility to adapt to the realities and the evolution of the defined CS throughout the lifetime of the FarFish project. Only obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version of the MR. The obligatory OTs for the Senegal CS address the challenges related to the black hake fishery and monitoring, as listed in the MR Invitation (FarFish, 2018a).

An OT is usually a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B'), but can also be a statement of presence or absence of some entity, in which a statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time. The indicator is a variable, pointer or an index related to a criterion. Its position and trend in relation to reference points (if available) or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. The indicators that relate to OTs should commonly be SMART, namely Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timely. An example of a biological/ecological indicator could be the fishing mortality (F); an example of economic indicator could be the EBITDA (Earnings before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization); and a social indicator could be the number of jobs created.

The suggested indicators in FarFish are set to measure the degree of adherence to the OT (Table 5) and are classified according to their level of measurability. The most detailed indicator category A, is where the level of achievement of the OT is quantitative e.g. measured in percentage. Indicator category B is qualitative, where the level of OT achievement is considered to be high level (score level 4), moderate level (score 3), fair level (score 2), low level (score 1) or not present (score 0). The last indicator category is binomial, measured to have only two outcomes such as yes (score 1) or no (Score 0), true or false, success or failure.

Table 5: FarFish Indicator categories (A- quantitative, B - qualitative and c-binomial) and the level of OT achievement

Indicator category	Level of OT achievement				
	100%	75 %	50 %	25 %	0 %
A	100%	75 %	50 %	25 %	0 %
B	High level (HL) 4	Moderate level (ML) 3	Fair Level (FL) 2	Low Level (LL) 1	Not present (NP) 0
C	Yes (true/success) 1				No (False/Failure) 0

3.1 Obligatory OTs and their indicators

Through “pre-invitation dialogues”, both by remote and physical meetings, stakeholders have discussed challenges in the black hake fishery and the management objectives were suggested by WP4 in MPO in collaboration with Task 4.1 contributors within the consortium (FarFish, 2018c). Based on these objectives, WP3 identified three obligatory OTs which are somewhat moderate and do not refer to an indicator value as commonly applied (FarFish, 2018b). Instead, most of the OTs refer to statements of presence or absence of some entity which can be assessed to be either true or false at given point of time.

3.1.1 *Make bycatch data available (OT 4.1)*

The FarFish partner OPROMAR, raised the concern that the observer’s reports are not submitted to the master of the vessel as required by the Protocol. The observer reports are not made available and/or do not contain bycatch data. The observer reports should be submitted to the scientific institutions (1) the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO) and/or (2) the Fisheries Research of the coastal state; the Oceanographic Research Centre of Dakar-Thiaroye (CRODT) (Fall et al., 2018). There is an urgent need to improve this part of the reporting as expressed in the last CSC Reports (2018) and in the Ex-ante report of 2019 (Caillart, 2019). This is the basis for OT 4.1 as formulated in the MR Invitation (FarFish, 2018a):

OT4.1: Improved data collection and reporting from all operators in Senegalese waters where data on catches and landings of all species is reported via electronic reporting (including target- and bycatches and should ideally account for discards where applicable).

During the WP/CS leader meeting in Cape Verde, November 2018, the text of the OT was amended to be more specific and measurable according to the RFMS approach;

OT4.1: Make bycatch data available

In order to measure the performance of OT 4.1, the following indicators are suggested:

- **I_1_CS4:** Bycatch data available by operators in fishing logbook to IEO and/or CRODT
- **I_2_CS4:** Report on bycatch data by scientific observers made available to IEO and/or CRODT

These indicators can be measured as C category (Yes/No), with the potential of becoming at least B category (high level, moderate level, etc.), or even A category by aiming for a number/percentage of fish logbooks/observers reports that include bycatch data.

Comments from operators related to OT 4.1:

The main activity related to bycatch reporting is being made by operators and onboard scientific observers. The observers and the operators are however receiving very little feedback, which projects lack of transparency and creates no incentives for them to cooperate. One recommendation from the operators is to improve communication between authorities and operators by setting up a workshop where they both exchange experiences and views on fisheries data reporting and exchange data. This would help identifying gaps and would promote research initiatives such as industry-science partnerships.

3.1.2 Provide information on proportion of the two species of hake in catches (OT 4.2)

Due to their morphological resemblance and overlapping occurrence at certain depths, both species are mixed in catches and in catch statistics. Both the CSC and CECAF recommend that actions should be taken to advance knowledge on the catch composition of the two species in CECAF area north. The work has been initiated in Mauritania and Morocco, but only scarce information is collected in Senegal. An improvement of the estimation of the proportion of *Merluccius polli* (HKB) and *Merluccius senegalensis* (HKM), will add value to a separated stock assessment. This OT is classified with an ecological dimension as reflects the knowledge strengthening of black hake fishery, through an estimation of the catch composition of the different species of black hake.

There is a strong indication of dominance of *M. polli* in studies conducted in Mauritanian waters (Fernandez-Peralta et al., 2017), both by surveys and visual identification on board by trained observers and/or skippers and fishermen. The proportion of the two species in catches taken in Senegalese waters has not been investigated in the same extent as in Mauritania. Following, the proportion of the two black hake species in catches taken in Senegalese waters is largely unknown. This is the basis for OT 4.2 as formulated in the MR Invitation (FarFish, 2018a):

OT4.2: Enhance data collection to enable for more accurate estimations of the share of each black hake species in total catches (Obligatory OT).

During the WP/CS leader meeting in Cape Verde, November 2018, the text of OT was amended to be more specific and measurable according to the RFMS approach;

OT4.2: Provide information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches

In order to measure the performance of OT 4.2, the following indicators are suggested:

- **I_3_CS4:** Training of Senegalese observers in visual species identification of black hake.
- **I_4_CS4:** Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis.
- **I_5_CS4:** Preliminary molecular analysis study to verify visual identification of black hake.

Comments from operators related to OT 4.2:

OPROMAR represents trawlers who are already doing some on board identification and separate storage, as both species have different FAO identification codes *M. polli* (HKB) and *M. senegalensis* (HKH). The Spanish Scientific Institute (IEO) has been training observers for visual identification of both hake species and provided guides to skippers and crews; thus, anglers could be able to identify each species. Oproamar were not completely against visual ID of black hake, but stress that such identification could contain mistakes or inaccuracies as it is done very fast during the fishing operations due to logistic issues. The operators propose to proceed with the identification of species on the port after landing, as it is more efficient in terms of logistic operations.

3.1.3 Commitment to transmit VMS and AIS signals (OT 4.3)

In a national action plan, Senegal adopted a strategy against IUU fishing in 2013, where the main objective is to eradicate IUU fishing in the Senegalese EEZ. Although VMS has been mandatory since 2006 and Senegalese vessels and inspectors carry out monitoring and control at sea, the action plan requires external support to strengthening the means of fisheries surveillance and better coordination of interventions and actions at national level (FarFish, 2018e).

The following OT is included to put increased pressure on all fleets operating in the area to commit to VMS/AIS transmission as well, promoting sustainable fisheries and initiating a level playing field. The suggested OT aimed to target the goal related to improved monitoring was listed as OT4.3 in the Management Recommendation Invitation (FarFish, 2018a):

OT 4.3 Commitment to transmit VMS/AIS signals. (Obligatory OT)

In order to measure the performance of OT 4.3, the following indicators are suggested:

- **I_6_CS4** Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocalization
- **I_7_CS4** Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS), geolocalization

Comments from operators related to OT 4.3:

OPROMAR vessels have two “blue boxes” to report on their VMS positions due to different satellite information systems which are not compatible (Euteltracs vs Argos). One VMS reports to Spanish fisheries control center (Flag State) and the other to Senegal. The last switches on automatically when they enter into the Senegalese EEZ. They report on a daily basis at periodic intervals as agreed under the SFPA. VMS reporting is the solely tool which is objective and verifiable for fisheries control (AIS is for maritime safety and avoiding collisions). Operators express their concerns about the lack of AIS range in some fishing areas, as it might look like it is switched off deliberately. It is therefore preferable the commitment to transmit the VMS in all cases.

Table 6: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome Targets (obligatory) and their suggested indicators for CS Senegal

Management goal	Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries (SFPA), Conserve and Sustainable use of the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development (SDG 14)	Improved quality of the current stock assessment for the species included in the agreement	OT 4.1 Make bycatch data available OT Dimension: Ecological	I_1_CS4: Bycatch data specified by operators in fishing logbook to IEO and/or CRODT. Indicator score: C
			I_2_CS4: Observers report, including bycatch data made available to IEO and/or CRODT and master of vessel. Indicator score: C
	Improved input data for sustainable and potentially separate stock assessment of the two species of black hake <i>M.palli</i> and <i>M.senegalensis</i>	OT 4.2 Provide information on the proportion of the two species of black hake in catches OT Dimension: Ecological	I_3_CS4: Training of Senegalese observers in visual species identification of black hake Indicator score: A
			I_4_CS4: Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis. Indicator score: A
Improved monitoring and control	Support enforcement by utilizing the latest available satellite systems and tools	OT 4.3 Commitment to transmit VMS and/or AIS signals OT Dimension: Governance	I_6_CS4: Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocated Indicator score: B
			I_7_CS4: Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation Indicator score: A

Table 7: Summary of Indicators, indicator their scoring and baseline and the entity responsible

Outcome target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator scoring	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 4.1	I_1_CS4: Bycatch data specified by operators in fishing logbook to IEO and/or CRODT	C	1	Operators by OPROMAR
	I_2_CS4: Report on bycatch data by scientific observers made available to master of vessel, IEO and/or CRODT	C	0	Authority by observers
OT 4.2	I_3_CS4: Training of Senegalese observers in visual species identification of black hake	A	0%	Authority by CRODT/IEO ⁵³
	I_4_CS4: Collection of fin samples of black hake for molecular analysis	A	0%	Authority by CRODT observers
	I_5_CS4: Preliminary molecular analysis study to verify visual identification of black hake	A	0%	Authority by CCMAR
OT 4.3	I_6_CS4: Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, geolocated	B	3	Authority, WP6 (CSIC)
	I_7_CS4: Proportion of vessels, either EU or non-EU, with redundant (AIS+VMS) geolocation	A	n.a	Authority, WP6 (CSIC)

3.2 Recommended OT (OT 4.4)

The recommended OTs are not to be addressed in this first version of MRs, but are based on important interests and needs reported through stakeholder interaction, both from authorities and operators. One of the main needs identified on a socio-economic level is the need to increase supply/demand and local markets, including those of neighbouring countries (and other African countries) such as Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire and Cameroon, and increase local prices for black hake. Currently, hake consumption in Senegal is limited, few markets exist for the species and the prices are low. Through increased effort in marketing activities, value-chain development and analysis, black hake could become an important contribution to local markets and social aspects (e.g. employment and revenues).

It is recognized that some of the data relevant for this OT can be confidential information (for example between fishing companies and their customers) and it is therefore expected that the MR1 draft will take that into consideration i.e. by suggesting what data can be provided, on what format, aggregation etc. The recommended OT will be addressed in the next version of the MR, named MR2.

⁵³ In accordance with CSS recommendation. The scientific institutions are suggested here by their participation has not been confirmed.

OT 4.4 as defined in MPR Invitation (FarFish D3.2)

OT 4.4: Increase knowledge and data collection of all fleets operating in the Senegalese EEZ on trade flows to include for example catches, destination/landings, utilization/processing, exports, value etc. This could include providing copies of sales invoices (sales certificates) in order to verify what markets the catches enter. Major aim of this OT is to support efforts to increase local supply and demand and strengthen local markets for black hake. Recommended OT

Comments from operators related to OT 4.4:

It is noted that all landings of black hake caught in Senegal and destined to the European market is commercialized on first sale at the Cadiz Auction so it is relatively easy to trace the trade flow of this species across the value chain.

3.3 Other potential actions as supplement to the MR

Apart from the OTs identified for the EU fleet operating in Senegal, a number of action points have been identified that could strongly support the case study objectives identified in the MPO. These action points have not been included in the list of OTs, as the operators cannot solely operationalize them, as they require input/action from other relevant parties (authorities, scientific institutions, other international fleets, etc.).

These are:

- Improved quality of current stock assessments for black hake, with separate stock assessments for the two species. FarFish aim is to contribute through OT4.2.
- Knowledge gap analysis is needed, in order to identify key knowledge and data gaps, especially for the black hake stocks. The responsibility for this cannot realistically be placed on the operators. FarFish aim is to contribute to this action through OT4.1.
- Effort should be put into increasing local demand and local markets for black hake, including those in other African countries e.g. Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire and Cameroon. Analysis of the Senegalese black hake value chains is a part of the FarFish project (FarFish, 2019) and contributes to this.

4 Management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning

4.1 Strategies and risk for achieving OT 4.1

Bycatch data shall be recorded by both scientific observers and in the fishing logbook. The fishing logbook shall be transferred electronically to FMC in both the flag state and to Senegal according to the protocol (although there are technical issues of receiving electronic logbooks in Senegal), while the observers report shall be submitted to the master of the vessel when leaving the ship. In addition, it shall be sent to the scientific institutions of CRODT and IEO (as only Spanish vessels target black hake under the SFPA). It is important that the bycatch be reported in the same way in the fishing logbook and in the observers report to prevent misunderstandings and misinterpretations of the collected information.

As a part of the approach to identify what causes the lack of availability of the observers report, FarFish approached the institution who provide the Senegalese observers, ISRA/CRODT. CRODT explained that the current observers from Senegal onboard the EU vessels in question are technical and not scientific observers. There is a lack of expertise on the technical personnel and they are not able to identify the species composition, nor are they able to quantify. However, CRODT has other good scientific observers, which could fulfil this task. These scientific observers were trained for taxonomic identification of bycatch species in the shrimp fisheries and successfully identified bycatch from shrimp trawlers in 2010 and 2014.

The current observer reports are submitted to CRODT, but does not contain the requested information on bycatch and FarFish aim to address this challenge in OT 4.1. In light of this new information, the strategy for achieving OT4.1 has two steps. First, ensure that the reporting of bycatch species in the electronic logbook from vessels contain the requested information and that the bycatch is reported in the same way in observers report and fishing logbooks, i.e. If aggregated group of species apply, ensure that the same species are aggregated as in the observers report. Secondly, ensure that the observers report contain bycatch data. This can be done by either training of current technical observers or by replacing technical with trained scientific observers who can fulfil this task.

Main risk and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this OT would be (1) Lack of template for registration of bycatch species from scientific institutions. (2) Lack of training of technical observers to identify and quantify catch species composition or (3) scientific observers not available.

FarFish facilitates this approach by approaching CRODT and request that scientific observers trained in taxonomic identification of bycatch species replace the technical observers, or provide the necessary

training for such identification to technical observers. FarFish will explore the possibility to assist CRODT in this training if requested. FarFish will also request a template for observers report from CRODT, with specification on how bycatch should be reported. This template will be compared to the fishing log requested from vessels in the Protocol (Appendix 1. Fishing logbook sheet from SFP agreement) and if significant different procedures are found, a suggestion for harmonization of the way bycatch data is reported will be provided. FarFish partner CCMAR will lead the work with this action.

FarFish recommendations;

- (1) Bycatch data should be reported in the same way in fishing logbook and observers reports.
- (2) Technical observers should be trained to identify and quantify species composition of the catch/bycatch or be replaced by scientific observers who have such expertise.
- (3) Observers report shall be submitted to the master of the vessel when leaving the ship according to the Protocol

4.2 Strategies and risk for achieving OT 4.2

Two alternatives for enhancing data collection for species identification include training of observers in visual identification of the two species of black hake, and verification of the visual identification by molecular analysis of samples collected onboard.

FarFish recommends a joint approach where the Senegalese observers are trained in visual identification of black hake species identification following the guidelines provided by IEO in the CSC annual report 2018 (Fall et al., 2018, annex 5). This training is suggested by IEO in CSC report and listed as one their recommendation. FarFish supports the recommendation by CSC to train Senegalese observers from CRODT in species identification of black hake.

In order to verify the visual identification of black hake, FarFish suggests conducting molecular analysis from samples of fish which were visually identified to species *M. polli* or *M. senegalensis*. Fin samples should be collected from visually identified species from fresh catch onboard. A sampling protocol (Annex 3), templates for data collection must be provided and a competent scientific institution must perform the molecular analysis of the fin clips.

FarFish will facilitate this action by approaching CRODT to initiate progress in the training of observers in black hake species identification as proposed in the CSC report as a joint effort by CRODT/IEO.

FarFish will ask CRODT for their observers' participation in the collection of fins samples for molecular analysis and provide all necessary equipment, sampling protocols and templates for the forms that

must be filled out. FarFish WP2 lead by CCMAR, will lead the progress towards the collection of samples and logistics for transport from vessel to laboratory facilities. A first version of the sampling protocol is provided in Annex 1, describing how the samples of 20-30 fin clips from different locations and depths shall be collected from fresh catch and stored in small tubes of ethanol. CCMAR has successfully established contact with Prof. Gonzalo Machado-Schiaffino at the University of Oviedo, Spain for molecular analysis of the collected fin samples. Preliminary calculations of cost of the analysis are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Preliminary estimated cost for molecular analysis for species identification of the black hake's species *M.polli* and *M.senegalensis* in catch.

	Cost of analysis per sample	Number of samples	Total cost per location	Total cost of molecular analysis at selected number of locations (L)			
				L=5	L=10	L=15	L=20
Minimum	€ 10	30	€ 300	€ 1 500	€ 3 000	€ 4 500	€ 6 000
Maximum	€ 15	30	€ 450	€ 2 250	€ 4 500	€ 6 750	€ 9 000
Minimum	€ 10	20	€ 200	€ 1 000	€ 2 000	€ 3 000	€ 4 000
Maximum	€ 15	20	€ 300	€ 1 500	€ 3 000	€ 4 500	€ 6 000

Main risk and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this OT would be (1) lack of training of the Senegalese observers in visual black hake species identification, (2) contamination of samplers for molecular analysis, (3) risk of damage to samples during logistic procedures between vessel and laboratory. In order to minimize risks related to failure in sampling and storage of samples for molecular analysis, a comprehensive protocol, potentially with video clips illustrating the sampling procedure, will be produced lead by WP2 leader CCMAR in collaboration with other task contributors. Risk of failure in laboratory analysis is reduced by following the procedures for such analysis.

FarFish recommendation:

- (1) FarFish supports the recommendation by CSC to train Senegalese observers from CRODT in species identification of black hake by following the Guidelines provided by IEO.
- (2) Visual identification of black hake onboard by fishermen and/or observers following the Guidelines provide by IEO should be verified by molecular analysis.
- (3) In the future, FarFish suggest that the operators shall be trained in visual identification of black hake onboard and quantify the proportion of the two black hake species in their catch, and FarFish will ask for their participation in self-sampling by collecting fin samples for molecular analysis to verify the visual identification. FarFish will create training materials in accordance with IEO identification guidelines if necessary.

- (4) In the future, a financial incentive could be presented to operators to perform self-sampling by visually identification black hake species in accordance to training and guidelines, and to collect samples onboard of black hake for molecular analysis. One such incentive could be to give those vessels priority in the fishery with respect to area, time and/or share of quota.

4.3 Strategies and risk for achieving OT 4.3

Increased monitoring in Senegal was been requested in Management Plan zero (FarFish, 2018c) and can be achieved by utilizing latest available satellite systems and tools. Global Fishing Watch⁵⁴ (GFW) is collecting high spatial and temporal resolution data of fishing efforts worldwide with AIS records obtained from communication satellite. Currently, the available data is aggregated, but companies like Marine Traffic⁵⁵ can obtain information on individual vessels if paid for.

If both AIS and VMS data from EU and non-EU vessels are made available, it is possible to develop diagnostic tools to detect suspicious dynamics (e.g. Country not providing all VMS data from non-EU countries or the vessels switching off the AIS) and thereby evaluate the proportion of VMS signals transmitted. Such diagnosis can also document challenges related to the range of AIS in some areas, which may increase the risk for ship collisions and reduce maritime safety.

FarFish will support the progress of achieving this OT by developing big-Data analysis by Work Group 6 leader CSIC for AIS signals. GFW has acknowledged FarFish as a scientific collaborator and given FarFish access to their fishing effort data for the period 2012-2017.

Main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this obligatory OT would be related to data treatment and AIS data deteriorating in quality once the vessels are aware of the existence of GFW. If individual data is required, vessel may not be willing to pay for this information.

⁵⁴ <https://globalfishingwatch.org/>

⁵⁵ www.marinetraffic.com

4.4 Internal monitoring

The internal monitoring of the development of the OTs in this case study will be to follow up on the progress, but simulation studies are not within the scope of this case study. The following institutions are suggested to take the responsibility for the FarFish actions related to the OTs:

- FarFish partner CRODT/ISRA is suggested to take the responsible for training of observers for species identification of catch composition related to both OT4.1 and OT4.2
- FarFish partner CCMAR and UiT are responsible for exploring templates for bycatch registrations in SFPA template and/or electronic fishing logbook and observers report.
- FarFish partner CCMAR is responsible for data collection for molecular analysis related to OT4.2
- FMC of Senegal is suggested to take the responsible for achieving OT 4.3, while WP6 CSIS is responsible for developing the big data analysis of AIS signals.

5 Monitoring, compliance and sanctions

Most of the OT defined within this CS, require a commitment from other players than operators, since the current operators have limited control over the OTs. Therefore, the responsibility cannot be established only between only two actors, operators and authorities; the responsibility will be shared between different players, which may play a better role to improve fisheries management og black hake in Senegalese waters. FarFish is not in the position to issue potential sanctions to operators or authorities for not providing data collection.

The monitoring of the OTs in this MR will rely on the actual training and embarking of competent observers (OT 4.1 and OT 4.2), submission of observers reports and fishing logbooks contain bycatch data (OT 4.1 and OT 4.2) and monitoring by satellite systems (OT 4.3).

6 Documentation

In order to be able to potentially harmonise the way bycatch is reported in ERS and observers report, templates for bycatch registration by both EU (in SFPA Protocol) and the Observers report must be made available for comparison and analysis. The template vessel owners are obliged to submit is available in the SFPA agreement, while CRODT should provide the template, which should be applied by Senegalese scientific observers.

FarFish partner CCMAR will provide the protocol for collection of samples for molecular analysis (Appendix 3) and FarFish partner CSIC will provide the letter of confirmation from GWF giving FarFish

access to aggregated AIS data to auditor. The documentation required and responsible institution for FarFish action is listed in Table 9, while the more detailed documentation matrix is given in Table 10.

Table 9: Documentation required for FarFish actions related to indicators and OTs

OT	Documentation	Responsible	Availability for auditor
OT 4.1	SFPA protocol, Fishing logbook (Protocol, Appendix 3c) Observers Report template Certificate on trained observers	UiT COREWAM/CRODT CRODT	Internal FarFish report available at the FarFish internal webpage
OT 4.2	Protocol for collection of samples for molecular analysis Guidelines for visual identification of black hake	CCMAR UiT	Internal FarFish report available at the FarFish internal webpage
OT 4.3	Confirmation from GFW to use their aggregated data.	CSIC	CSIC send the letter of confirmation to auditor

Table 10: Documentation matrix for MR1 Senegal

OT	OT short	Indicators	Sources/ Data collection	Processing of data	Action/ Responsibility
4.1	Bycatch data available	I_1_CS4 I_2_CS4	Operator CRODT observers	IEO/CRODT IEO/CRODT	Operator Authority: CRODT provide bycatch data in observers report
4.2	Black hake species identification	I_3_CS4 I_4_CS4 I_5_CS4	CRODT/ISRA CRODT observer CRODT observer	IEO/CRODT University of Oviedo, Spain	Authority: IE and CRODT Authority: CCMAR Authority: CCMAR/ University of Oviedo, Spain
4.3	AIS/VMS transmission	I_6_CS4 I_7_CS4	FMC Spain/Senegal GFW	FMC Senegal	Authority: FMC Senegal

7 General considerations

The participation in data collection is crucial for improved stock assessment and management of black hake, but it must be emphasized that this hake is considered a shared stock between several coastal states so that the effort done in Senegal is only part of the solution for a sustainable fishery of black hake. A regional approach should follow up the previous work by Fernandes-Peralta and the actions which FarFish will explore in this research project. As CECAF is responsible for the stock assessment of the species, they could be reporting to DG MARE about potential improvements in reporting of bycatch species in the black hake fisheries as well as improved catch statistics where the proportion of the two species of black hake is taken into consideration.

8 Auditor

FarFish partner Syntesa will audit the RFMS process and implementation process and has agreed to this at the initial stage of FarFish, but other auditors can be selected if necessary.

9 Planning process

The development of MRs depend on input from other FarFish WPs and this first version is supported by the Case study characterization (FarFish 2017), First MR invitations (FarFish, 2018a), Draft 1 General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2018b), Management Plan Zero (FarFish, 2018c), Report from the MR Kick-off meeting (FarFish, 2018d), Evaluation of governance structures of the cases (FarFish, 2018e), Developments needed to produce relevant management tools (FarFish, 2018f), Stakeholders hub (FarFish 2018g), Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 1 (FarFish, 2018h), Visualization materials and tools for MR1 (FarFish, 2018i) and Description of CS value chains (FarFish, 2019). WP5 will provide their audit of the MPR1 in FarFish deliverable D5.2 by August 2019.

Tentative planning process

A comparison of how bycatch is reported in fishing logbook and observers' reports shall be available by October 15th 2019.

FarFish will approach FarFish partner ISRA/CRODT and ask for their response by August 1st regarding a) the competence of observers onboard with respect identification of bycatch species and the suggested strategies; replacement of technical observers or training.

b) the progress of the suggested CSC training of scientific observers for identification of black hake and or potentially.

The working plan for OT 4.3, will follow a similar approach as in MR1 for Cape Verde, OT 3.4, with the exception of including VMS data in this first version of the MR. (Inclusion of VMS data is a challenge as to access the data and the fact that there are currently less than three EU vessels active in Senegalese EEZ targeting hake.) If VMS data would become available, the following working plan is suggested;

- a) Assessment of type and amount of VMS data
- b) Overlapping (time and space) analysis between GWF and VMs data
- c) Implementation of massive data techniques for cross-comparison
- d) Diagnose the results in terms of inter-comparative compliance by EU and Senegal.

A first draft of analysis of the GWF data shall be completed by October 2019.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Fishing logbook sheet from SFPa agreement

Appendix 3c

SFPa - SENEGAL
YEAR - QUARTER

Catch declaration for deep-sea demersal trawlers

Name of vessel

Flag State

Zone (*)

Catch in kilograms

Month	(*) (FAO CODE)	Hake	Pardona	Angler fish					Other fish (*)	Other cephalopods (*)	Other crustaceans (*)	Other shellfish (*)	Total catch
January													
February													
March													
April													
May													
June													
July													
August													
September													
October													
November													
December													
Total													

(*) Indicate whether 'Senegal' or 'Senegal/Guinea-Bissau common zone'

(*) One column for each species caught (with FAO code)

(*) Indicate aggregate catches if species is not determined

Appendix 2. Annex, Chapter IV Monitoring, Control and Surveillance, Section 5 Observers

SECTION 5

Observers

1. Observation of fishing activities

- 1.1. Vessels holding a fishing authorisation shall be subject to a scheme for observing their fishing activities carried out within the framework of the Agreement.
- 1.2. For tuna vessels this observation scheme shall conform to the provisions provided for in the recommendations adopted by ICCAT (International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas).

2. Designated vessels and observers

- 2.1. When the fishing authorisation is issued, Senegal shall inform the EU and the vessel owner, or its consignee, of the designated vessels and observers and the times at which the observer will be present on board each vessel.
- 2.2. Senegal shall inform the EU and the vessel owner, or its consignee, of the name of the designated observer at the latest 15 days before the date provided for the embarkation of the observer. Senegal shall without delay inform the EU and the vessel owner or its consignee of any change in the designated vessels and observers.
- 2.3. Senegal shall endeavour not to designate observers for vessels which already have an observer on board, or to allow an observer to embark during the fishing season in question as part of their activities in fishing zones other than the Senegalese zones.
- 2.4. For deep-sea demersal trawlers the time on board shall not exceed two months. The observers shall not spend more time on board the vessel than is necessary to carry out their duties.

3. Flat-rate financial contribution

- 3.1. At the time the annual flat-rate fee is paid, owners of freezer tuna seiners and pole-and-line vessels shall also pay the DPSP a flat-rate sum of EUR 400 per vessel for the proper functioning of the observer programme.
- 3.2. At the time the quarterly flat-rate fee is paid, owners of trawlers shall also pay the DPSP a flat-rate sum of EUR 100 per vessel for the proper functioning of the observer programme.

4. Observer's salary

The salary and social contributions of the observer shall be borne by Senegal.

5. Embarkation conditions

5.1. The embarkation conditions for the observer, in particular the duration of his presence on board, shall be defined by mutual agreement between the vessel owner or its consignee and Senegal.

5.2. The observer shall be treated on board as an officer. However, receiving the observer on board shall take into account the technical structure of the vessel.

5.3. The vessel owner shall bear the costs of providing accommodation and food for the observer on board.

5.4. The master shall take all the measures for which he is responsible to guarantee the physical safety and general well-being of the observer.

5.5. The observer shall be offered every facility needed to carry out his duties. He shall have access to means of communication and to documents relating to the fishing activities of the vessel, in particular the fishing logbook and navigation log, and the parts of the vessel directly linked to his duties.

6. Observer's obligations

6.1. Whilst on board the observer shall:

6.2. take all appropriate measures so as not to interrupt or hinder fishing operations;

6.3. respect on-board property and equipment;

6.4. respect the confidential nature of any document belonging to the vessel.

7. Embarkation and landing of observers

7.1. The observer shall embark in a port chosen by the vessel owner.

7.2. The vessel owner or his agent shall notify Senegal, with a notice period of 10 days before the embarkation, of the date, time and port of embarkation of the observer. If the observer is embarked in a foreign country, his travel costs to the port of embarkation shall be borne by the vessel owner.

7.3. If the observer does not present himself for boarding within 12 hours of the date and time set, the vessel owner shall be automatically discharged from his obligation to allow the observer to embark. The vessel shall be free to leave the port and start fishing operations.

7.4. Where the observer is not put ashore in a Senegalese port, the vessel owner shall bear the costs of the observer's repatriation to Senegal as soon as possible.

8. Observer's obligations

The observer shall carry out the following duties:

8.1. observe the fishing activities of the vessel;

8.2. verify the position of the vessel during fishing operations;

8.3. perform biological sampling in the context of a scientific programme;

8.4. note the fishing gear used;

- 8.5. verify the catch data for the Senegalese fishing zones recorded in the logbook;
- 8.6. verify the percentages of bycatches and estimate the discarded catches;
- 8.7. communicate observations by radio, fax or e-mail at least once a week while the vessel is fishing in the Senegalese zones, including the quantity of catch and bycatch on board.

9. Observer's report

- 9.1. Before leaving the vessel, the observer shall submit a report of his observations to the master of the vessel. The master of the vessel shall have the right to make comments in the observer's report. The report shall be signed by the observer and the master. The master shall receive a copy of the observer's report.
- 9.2. The observer shall send his report to Senegal, which shall send a copy of it to the EU within eight days of the observer's disembarkation.

Appendix 3. Self-Sampling protocol

	Action	Scheme	Responsible to provide template
1	Record haul location, date, time and depth	CS4_1_vessel	CCMAR
2	For each fish: a) Assign a unique identifier and link to record haul location (code/number) b) Identify the species by morphological method c) Record total length and sex	CS4_2_Fish	CCMAR
3	Procedure for collection of sample a) Prepare tubes with ethanol b) Cut a small piece of fin (1 cm ²) and c) Put the small piece of the fin in tube with ethanol d) Label the tube with the unique identifier e) Clean/disinfect the scissors with ethanol before taking the next sample f) Store the tubes in a cool place	CS4_3_Procedure	CCMAR
5	Logistics Send the tubes with the sampling sheet containing the unique identifier, haul location, date, time, depth, species sex and total length data.	Address to analysing lab will be provided	CCMAR

MAURITANIAN CASE STUDY

Deliverable No. 4.3

Project acronym:

FarFish

Project title:

Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

Grant agreement No: **727891**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme

Start date of project: **1st June 2017**

Duration: **48 months**

Due date of deliverable:	31/01/2019
Submission date:	23/09/2020
File Name:	FarFish D4.3_MR1 Mauritania
Revision number:	02
Document status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public

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Management Recommendation 1

Mauritania

23/09/2020

Executive Summary

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) with particular focus on the black hake fishery under the SFPA agreement between the Islamic Republic of Mauritania and EU. The EU vessels currently targeting black hake are trawlers from Spain. Two different species of black hake are targeted and there is a lack of distinction between the two in catch statistics. Therefore, the two species of black hake are assessed as one by the Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic Fisheries (CECAF).

The Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Economy (MPEM), the Management of Oceanic Resources (DARE) and the Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG Mare) are considered the competent authorities in this FarFish case study and FarFish Work Package 3 acts as the leading authority in the process of developing the MR, considering input from the authorities. The confirmed operators are represented by Long Distance Advisory council (LDAC) and the Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín (OPROMAR) from Spain, assisted by FarFish Work Package 4.

The MR1 follows the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish [D3.1](#)) and is based on the Management Recommendation Invitation (FarFish [D3.2](#)), where the outcome targets (OTs) are proposed. Only the obligatory OTs related to the black hake fishery are addressed in this first version of the MR. The proposed OTs area based on input from Management Recommendation Zero (FarFish [D4.1](#)), input from operators at the MR Kick-off meeting (FarFish [D4.2](#)) and additional stakeholder meetings facilitated by WP1, and input from FarFish Work package/Case study leader meeting that was held in Mindelo, Cape Verde, in November 2018).

This MR1 aims to improve knowledge on the species composition of black hake in catches and thereby adding value to stock assessment for both species. FarFish recommends to enhance data collection for species identification of black hake in catches, by fleets targeting black hake and by fleets where black hake occurs as bycatch. The subsequent OTs are related to improved data collection by species discrimination of the two black hake species in catch and collection of samples for molecular analysis. The OTs are classified to ecological dimension and we acknowledge that the operators cannot be solely made responsible for achieving the OTs. It must therefore be a joint effort between authorities and operators to make progress in this MR. Indicators are suggested to measure the performance of the OTs, and the strategy for achieving OTs is outlined. The strategies do not affect any of the current management conservation measures applied by the Islamic Republic of Mauritania or the EU. A regional approach is outside the scope of FarFish, but should be applied, as black hake is considered a shared stock between several coastal states, and actions taken in Mauritanian EEZ is only part of the solution for a sustainable fishery of black hake.

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Abbreviations

CCMAR	Centro de Ciencias do Mar do Algarve (Portugal)
CETMAR	Centro Tecnológico del Mar-Fundación CETMAR (Spain)
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
Cmsy	Catch msy
CS	Case Study
CSC	Joint Scientific Committee on Fisheries Agreement between the Islamic Republic of Mauritania and the EU (Comités Científicos Conjoints)
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spain)
DARE	Directory of Fisheries Management in Mauritania
DG MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, EC.
EC	European Commission, executive of European Union
ERS	Electronic Recording Systems
IEO	Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO)
IMROP	Mauritanian Institute for Oceanographic Research and Fisheries
LDAC	Long Distance Advisory council
MATIS	Matís ohf. – Icelandic Food & biotech R&D (Iceland)
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MPEM	Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Economy
MR	Management Recommendation
MSY	Maximum sustainable yield
NEAFC	North East Atlantic Fisheries Commission
ONISPA	National Office for Sanitary Inspection of Fishery and Aquaculture Products (Mauritania)
OPROMAR	Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín (Spain)
RBM	Results-Based Management
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System is a fisheries management approach. The RFMS is an adaptive management system that is results-based and ecosystem-based.
SEAFO	South East Atlantic Fisheries Organisation
SFPA	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements
SGP	Secretaría General de Pesca (Spain)
SRFC	Sub Regional Fisheries Commission
SSB	Spawning Stock Biomass
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
UiT	University of Tromsø (Norway)
UNU-FTP	United Nations University Fisheries Training Programme
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System
WP	Work Package

Concepts/definitions

Indicator	A variable, pointer or index related to a criterion. Indicators are selected such that their variations reflect variations in key elements of the fishery resource, the social and economic well-being of the sector and the sustainability of the ecosystem. The position and trend of an indicator in relation to reference points or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. Indicators provide a bridge between objectives and actions (source: FAO 1999).
Management goals	The higher-order objective to which a management intervention is intended to contribute (OECD 2011). A management goal is derived from a management principle (constitutional-order) and is specified into a set of more operational management objectives (collective-order).
Management intervention	Strategies or instruments aimed to impact the state of a fishery with reference to authorized objectives. Examples are input and output controls and economic measures.
Management measures	Can be technical (e.g. gear selectivity etc.), input (effort)/output (catch) control, right based.
Management objectives	Fisheries management objectives are typically framed within the overall concept of sustainable development, and may reflect one or more of the various dimensions and criteria that relate to it (FAO 1999). Operators through setting and implementing management measures control OTs.
Management Plan (MP)	A fisheries management plan is a formal arrangement between a fishery management authority and interested parties which identifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, details the agreed objectives for the fishery and specifies the management rules and regulations which apply to it and provides other details about the fishery which are relevant to the task of the management authority (Source: FAO 2002).
Management Recommendation (MR)	In RFMS, the management recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority and operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery. In RFMS, the formal responsibility for developing the management plan is delegated to an operator.
Management strategies	In FarFish context, it means the strategies applied to achieve OTs
Outcome Target (OT)	Outcome targets (OTs) are specific and measurable requirements that are set by an authority to make management goals operational. An OT is a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B') or a statement of presence or absence of some entity. On the basis of relevant information, this statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time ⁵⁴ . For instance, the management objective that "the fishery should be biologically sustainable" could be expressed in terms of one or more OTs such as 'Catch < 20 000t; 'bycatch < 20%'; SSB > 30 000t; 'a catch reporting system is present', etc.
Reference point	A classification device, defined in relation to the measure of an indicator, for distinguishing different management relevant states of the system under management. A Biological Reference Point is a metric of stock status. A Target Reference Point indicates a state of a system which is considered desirable and at which management action should aim. A Limit Reference Point indicates a state of a system, which is considered to be undesirable, that one therefore should seek to avoid through relevant management action.
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) is a fisheries management approach developed within the FP7 project EcoFishMan . The RFMS is an adaptive management approach that is results-based and ecosystem-based. The RFMS attempts to reduce micromanagement by involving stakeholders and increase the degree of co-management by delegating management responsibilities to resource users.

1 Introduction

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) from European operators active in Mauritanian fishery under the SFA agreement (2015-2019). The MR1 is founded on Results-Based Management (RBM) principles and based on the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) approach (Figure) which was developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan (Silva et al., 2014, Santiago et al., 2015, Nielsen et al., 2017). Basically, the MR is an agreement between competent authorities, relevant operators and potentially other stakeholders. In the MR, strategies are defined to achieve outcome targets (OTs) which are established by authorities in the MR invitation to support sustainable fisheries (FarFish, 2019a), while following the General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2019b).

Figure 1: The RFMS process. The responsibilities of each of the three entities are demonstrated with different colours. Authority: red/Operators: blue/ Auditors: yellow (FarFish, 2019b).

The partners in the fishery and their respective roles and responsibilities are identified in the MR, which also provides a detailed overview of the fishery and the geographical boundaries for the MR, which were outlined in the Management Recommendation zero (MP0) (FarFish, 2018a). The authority is the organizational entity acting as the authority in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery (e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission). They oversee the RFMS process and issue the “MR invitation”, which includes a clear specification of measurable OTs, set in order to operationalize the goals of existing policies and the local management objectives.

The operator is defined as an organized group of resource users, e.g. an association of fishermen or stakeholders with rights in a given fishery. It is the organizational unit with delegated authority to develop management recommendations based on the OTs set by the authority and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority. In line with the RFMS approach, the engagement of stakeholders is highly prioritized in FarFish. At the successful MR kick-off meeting in Vigo (Spain, June 2018), operators representing the distant water fleet (DWF) from the

European Union expressed their interests and needs (FarFish, 2019c), which were relevant for the development of the MR Invitation and defining the OTs, in which this MR1 will address.

During the development of MR0 (FarFish, 2018a), it was considered unattainable to cover all target species under the SFPA agreement between EU and the Islamic Republic of Mauritania in this first version of the MR. The Mauritanian CS leader expressed interest in the shrimp fishery when asked to prioritize between the target species under the SFPA agreement categories. However, based on feedback after the MR Kick-off meeting in Vigo (Spain, June 2018) and the low utilization rate in the shrimp fishery under the SFPA is the selection of target species was reconsidered. The selection of the target species was thereafter carried out according to the following criteria: (1) clear claim by the EU and coastal authority and (2) a certain level of stakeholder urgency. The urgency level was defined taking the conclusions from the CSC report for Mauritania (Cervantes et al., 2017; Bouzouma et al., 2018), which were supported by the operators. Thus, the black hake and the small pelagic fishery were highly prioritised by Spanish fleet, where Spanish licences do represent 86% (with variation among different categories).

1.1 Partners involved in MR1

The leader of Task 3.3 (Authority role within RFMS), MATIS, acts as the leading authority, whilst considering input from relevant authorities, e.g. Ministry of Fisheries and Maritime Economy (MPEM), the Management of Oceanic Resources (DARE) and the Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE) (Table 1). The European operators qualified to respond to the first MR Invitation for Mauritania on OTs related to black hake are the Long-Distance Advisory Council⁵⁶ (LDAC) represented by its Executive Secretary Alexandre Rodríguez and Organization of Fresh Fish Producers of the Port and Ría de Marín⁵⁷ (OPROMAR). Two members from OPROMAR have participated in the MR1 meetings. LDAC has a nominal composition of 60% of fishing sector organisations (including catching, processing and marketing sectors, and trade unions). The remaining 40% is other groups of interests (mainly environmental and development NGOs). OPROMAR represents 35 fishing companies including demersal trawlers, surface longliners and purse-seiners vessels. The leader of work package 4 (WP4) in FarFish, UiT- The Arctic University of Norway, assists the representatives for operators in the development of the MR1.

⁵⁶ <http://ldac.eu/>

⁵⁷ <http://opromar.com/>

Table 1: MR1 Mauritania entities, area, target species, fleets, main aims and MR planning period

MR basis	MR1 Mauritania		
RFMS entities	Authorities: WP3, MPEM, DARE, DG Mare		
	Operators: WP4, LDAC, OPROMAR		
	Auditor: WP5		
Target species	Common name	Scientific name	FAO code
	Tropical African hake	<i>Merluccius polli</i>	HKB
	Senegalese hake	<i>Merluccius senegalensis</i>	HKM
Geographical range	The Mauritanian coast extends from the 15 th to the 21 st North parallel, and the Mauritania EEZ covers an area of 234,000 km ² . The fishing zone areas are specified in SFPA Protocol, Appendix 2		
Fleets	EU fleet: Spain Demersal trawlers fishing under SFPA agreement <i>category 2</i> and <i>2bis</i> . Demersal and pelagic trawlers fishing under other categories catch black hake as bycatch.		
Main aims of MR	Improve knowledge on proportion of two black hake species in total black hake composition in catch.		
MR planning period	Lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021)		

1.2 Aims of MR1 for Mauritania

This MR1 applies to the EU fishery of black hake caught under the SFPA agreement in Mauritania EEZ, FAO subdivision 34.3.11 and 31.1.32 (Figure 23). Two different species of black hake are targeted under *category 2* and *2bis* under the SFPA agreement (2015-2019), i.e. the tropical African black hake (*Merluccius polli*) and the Senegalese hake (*Merluccius senegalensis*), but considerable amounts of black hake is also taken as bycatch under other fleet categories. The MR1 aims to improve knowledge on the species composition black hake in catches and thereby adding value to stock assessment for both species. To support sustainable fisheries, FarFish aim to enhance data collection for species identification of black hake in catches, taking into account technical considerations related to the species identification based on previous studies by Fernández-Peralta et al., (2018), published in the Joint Scientific Committee (CSC) report of 2018 (Bouzouma et al., 2018)

Figure 23: Map of Northwest Africa- Eastern Central Atlantic (FAO Fishing area 34). The Mauritanian EEZ is located in subdivisions 34.3.11 and 34.1.32. Source: García-Isarc et al., (2016)

1.3 The National Fisheries Management Plan, CFP and relevant recommendations by CECAF and the CSC

The main objective of the 2015-2019 Action Plan named National Fisheries Management Plan (MFMP) in Mauritania is defined as: “Harness the fishing heritage of the country, in a sustainable way, the maximum benefit for the people of Mauritania, and participate more actively in efforts to develop an inclusive blue economy source of wealth and employment” (FarFish, 2017). Following, the management goals of the MRMP are:

- (1) Improve knowledge of fisheries resources and their environment
- (2) Optimize the management of the exploitation of fishery resources
- (3) Strengthen integration of the fisheries sector to the national economy
- (4) Develop maritime business
- (5) Promote the development of continental fishing and aquaculture
- (6) Strengthen good governance of fisheries

The European Union has also established a system concerning fishing activities of Union fishing vessels fishing outside Union waters under SFPAs agreements⁵⁸ and on the high seas. The Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) also requires SFPAs to be limited to surplus catches. EU has reformed the CFP, which came

⁵⁸ REGULATION (EU) 2017/2403 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 12 December 2017 on the sustainable management of external fishing fleets, and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008

into effect in January 2014, state that all EU fishing activities, inside and outside EU waters, and are subject to the same environmental and other standards (EC 2017). Thus, the EU must conduct its external fleet in accordance with the objectives and principles set out in Articles 2 and 3 of the CFP. According to Article 2, those objectives include the application and promotion of the precautionary approach to ensure that the stocks targeted are higher levels that deliver MSY by 2020 at the latest, the application of the ecosystem principle, the promotion of the collection of scientific data and the gradual elimination of discards.

The main objective of the CFP is to ensure that fishing activities are environmentally, economically and socially sustainable and are managed consistently with the objectives of achieving economic, social and employment benefits, and of restoring and maintaining fish stocks above levels which can produce maximum sustainable yield and that they are contributing to the availability of food supplies. Additionally, the union has committed itself to Sustainable Development Goal 14⁵⁹ (SDG 14) and Sustainable Development Goal 12⁶⁰ (SDG 12). EU vessels operating under the SFPA agreement shall comply with all technical conservation measures as set out in the SFPA protocol. The CFP stresses the need to promote the objectives of CFP internationally, ensuring that Union-fishing activities outside Union waters area based on the same principles and standards as those applicable under Union law, while promoting a level playing field for Union operators and third-country operators.

The FAO/CECAF working group on the Assessment of Demersal Resources – northern subgroup, contribute to improve the management of demersal resources is northwest Africa. They provide assessment of the state of the stocks and fisheries to ensure optimal and sustainable use of resources in African coastal countries (FAO 2018b), including the black hake. The black hake is, according to the most recent assessment, fully exploited. CECAF has informed managers of the state of concern of some demersal stocks in their countries, so that they can implement the recommendations developed by the CECAF working group organized by FAO. The Joint Scientific Committee (CSC) on the Fisheries Agreement between Mauritania and EU has made several recommendations for the EU fishery under *Category 2 and 2bis* who are targeting black hake:

- (1) Considering the stock status in the sub-region, the dynamics of exploitation, the new opportunities allocated (*category 2bis*) and the level accessory catches of black hake, the CSC considers again that an increase in the effort and catches cannot be considered for the black hake fisheries in Mauritania.
- (2) The divergencies detected between the different data sources deserve particular attention, looking at the repercussions that they can have under the real estimation of the mortality by catch of hake. This is why the CSC recommends the organisation of a special workshop for the revision of the black hake data matrix.

⁵⁹ SDG14: conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

⁶⁰ SDG12: ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns and their targets

- (3) The CSC notes the importance of the accessory catches of black hake, seemingly by the pelagic vessels. It recommends the reduction of this accessory catches and equally that the data of this pelagic fishery and the rest of the fleets that fish black hake as bycatch are clarified in the databases and followed (observations at sea and sampling done at landings) with the aim to clarify their impacts on the black hake stocks.
- (4) The CSC recommends to continue studying the separation of the two species in the catches, in order to develop and implement a harmonized sampling protocol that will allow to differentiate the two species of black hake in the catches and a separate assessment of the two species.
- (5) Regarding the available information of the exploitation of resources and of the *category 2bis*, the CSC recommends to redefine the protocol conditions concerning this category to adjust them to the reality of the fishery:
 - a. The CSC, after analysing catches from fishery *2bis*, noted that the main catch of cephalopods of this segment is deep-sea squid and therefore suggested to the mixed commission to considering a potential redefinition of the term “squid” used in the protocol to include as well the “deep sea squid”, or an inclusion of the deep cephalopods as an accessory commercial species in the fishery.
 - b. To the extent that freezer trawlers (*category 2bis*) can operate in the same areas and use the same mesh size as the fresh fish trawlers in the (*category 2*), the CSC recommends that the authorized by-catch is generalised in the trawler fleet as a whole targeting black hake, keeping the same bycatch possibilities.
 - c. In view of the proposed modifications, the CSC recommends that *category 2bis* is included in *category 2* and that the same conditions apply to both types of vessels.
- (6) The CSC recommends to continue the analysis and assessment of cephalopod catches made by the two black hake trawler fleets (*category 2* and *2bis*), in order define common conditions for the technical specifications of the Agreement. The analysis of the cephalopod catches made by scientific observers onboard the two fleets will make it possible to evaluate their impact on these resources and to determine the most appropriate technical conservation measures.
- (7) The CSC proposed that the estimation factor estimated by the IEO based on sampling (1.51) is applied when estimating the quantity of black hake caught in the logbooks, instead of the current value 1.67.

Following, CSC support the precautionary approach by FAO/CECAF by not recommending an increase in effort or catches, and to reduce the bycatch of black hake as an assessor species in other fisheries.

In the recent Ex-ante evaluation of the SFPA agreement between the Islamic Republic of Mauritania and EU, it is also expressed a need to improve the catch monitoring schemes by EU vessels, as they have not been effective enough to prevent excesses of allowable catch volumes for vessels targeting black hake (EC, 2019). In the Ex-ante evaluation of renewal scenarios, when considering a future

protocol, it is suggested a cautious approach which takes into account the situation of full exploitation of black hake in Mauritania as well as regionally (EC, 2019).

1.4 Identity of Fishery

The current SFPA agreement covers the period from 2015 to 2019 and allows for several fleets and target shrimp, demersal fish, tuna and small pelagic fish up to a total of 287,050 tons a year (FarFish, 2019h). The species are specified under different categories in Table 2. This SFPA is the most expensive EU protocol where the EU financial contribution exceeds the EUR 59 million per year and shipowners paid feeds around EUR 60 million (Paz, 2018). From the EU contribution, more than EUR 4 million support the development of the Mauritanian fishery sector. Over the last three years, the value at first sale of these catches taken under the current protocol is estimated at EUR 166 million per year on average, including 59 % by pelagic trawlers and 13 % by shrimp trawlers in category 1 of the Protocol (EC, 2019).

Black hake is the target species in *category 2* and *2bis*, but may also be taken as bycatch in especially the category 3 demersal trawl, category 6 pelagic trawl for small pelagics and category 7 small pelagic (fresh), but there has been no fishery in category 7 in recent years.

The fishery under SFPA *category 2* fresh trawlers and *2bis* freezer trawlers, allow for capture of black hake quota amounting to 6,000 tons under *category 2* for up to 6 vessels and 3,500 tons under *category 2bis* for up to 6 vessels (Bouzouma *et al.*, 2018). The fishing possibilities were revised upwards in 2017, adding 3,500 tonnes of black hake to EU freezer trawlers under *category 2bis* of the SFPA (Paz, 2018: 29). These fisheries are also allocated 25% of bycatch quotas, but bycatch of cephalopods and crustaceans is prohibited. Category 3 vessels are allowed to catch 10 % bycatch, while category 6 and 7 vessels are allowed to catch 3%, where crustaceans or cephalopods are not authorized, except squid.

The black hake quota includes two different species, i.e. tropical African hake (*Merluccius polli*) and Senegalese hake (*Merluccius senegalensis*) which have been denominated under the generic name of black hake for more than 60 years (FAO, 2018). The species are mixed in catches, are commonly marketed as *Merluccius spp* (FAO, 2016) and reported together as black hake in catch statistics. Neither in the SFPA agreement, nor in the stock assessment by CECAF is it discriminated between the two species, even though they have different biological characteristics and should therefore preferably be managed separately (Fernández-Paralta *et al.*, 2017).

Table 2: Fishing opportunities by categories, allowed catch, gear and utilisation percentage in 2017. Source: Bouzouma et al., 2018

No	EU categories	Species	Allowed catch	Gear	Utilization 2017
1	MRT_CRU	Crustaceans, shrimp ⁶¹	5,000 t	Bottom trawl	27%
2	MRT_HKM	Black hake	6,000 t	Bottom trawl (fresh)	103%
2bis ⁶²	MRT_HKM_TOF	Black hake Squid Cuttlefish	3,500 t 1,450 t 600 t	Bottom trawl (freeze)	97%
3	MRT_NTO_DEM	Demersal other than black hake	3,000 t	Longline, gillnet, handline, creels, seine for fishing live bait	86%
4	MRT_SP	Tuna	12,500 t	Seiners	110%
5	MRT_LP	Tuna	7,500 t	Pole & line, surface longline	67%
6	MRT_PEL_frozen	Small pelagics	225,000 t	Pelagic trawl (freeze)	37%
7	MRT_PEL_fresh	Small pelagics	15,000 t	Pelagic trawler and industrial purse seine (fresh)	0%
8	MRT_CEPH	Cephalopods	-	Trawling, no fishing opportunities	-

Note: low utilization rates of fishing opportunities in some categories have been associated to problems with technical measures, high fees and the issue of boarding of vessels (Paz, 2018).

⁶¹ Crustaceans, except spiny lobster and crabs.

⁶² New fishing category from March 2017

2 Fishery overview

The fishing opportunities accessed by the EU fleet under *Category 2* and *2Bis* accounted for 77.6 and 58.2% of the total demersal catch under SFPA agreement in 2016 and 2017 respectively (Bouzouma et al., 2018, IEO conversion factor, Table 2.1.4). Catch in *Category 2* and *2Bis* accounted for approximately 42.6% of the total catch of hake in Mauritanian waters in 2016 and 2017 on average (Table 2). A considerable amount of black hake is taken as bycatch in non-hake fisheries, where the offshore pelagic vessels have been increasing the last years up to 66% of total bycatch taken by other demersal and pelagic fleet (Table 2 based on numbers from Bouzouma et al., 2018). In 2017, the bycatch of black hake by the EU fleet accounted for 700 tonnes out of a total of 4,646 tonnes.

Black hake is targeted by bottom trawlers from several countries, but Spain is allocated the entire allowed catch of demersal fish under the SFPA protocol, including the black hake quota. The Spanish trawlers generally operate in the deepest stratum and specific areas in the north between 19°N and 17°N (Figure , From Bouzouma et al., 2018 and Fernández-Peralta et al., 2017). The fresh trawler fleet operates along the coast of Mauritania from the border with Senegal (16°N) to the border with Morocco (21°N), from north to south according to VMS positions (Bouzouma et al., 2018). More coastal species are usually targeted at depths < 500m in the area from Cape Timiris and the latitude of Nouakchott, while black hake more frequently targeted at fishing area with depths between 500 and 700 m.

Figure 3: Left Panel: Fishing area for Spanish flag vessels targeting black hake in categories 2 and 2bis in the Mauritanian EEZ in the period from July to December 2017. Source: (Bouzouma et al., 2018). Middle panel and right panel show presence of *M. Polli* (orange circles) (middle panel) or *M. senegalensis* (green circles) (right panel) and absence (red crosses) catches at four surveys in the period 2007-2010 in late autumn (Fernández-Peralta et al., 2017).

2.1 Recent trends- EU catch statistics and EU fleet

The utilization rate of the annual fishing opportunities for the categories targeting black hake have been very close to 100% per year in 2016 and 2017, in term of authorized catch tonnages (Table 2), (based on numbers from Bouzouma et al., 2018). The EU vessels targeting black hakes has slightly (category 2) or largely (category 2bis) exceeded the catch limits authorised by the protocol (according to data from the EC-DG MARE) (EC, 2019). EU vessels fishing under *category 2bis* captured 215% of the adjusted TAC in 2018 (7,511 tons), while captures under *category 2* were close to 100% (EC, 2019).

Between 2-5 Spanish vessels have been fishing under *Category 2* in the last decade (FarFish, 2019h) and six Spanish vessels in under the new *Category 2bis* in 2018. Four trawlers from OPROMAR were actively operating under *Category 2* (fresh) and six trawlers under *Category 2bis* (frozen) in 2018. The fresh trawlers land fish on weekly basis in the port of Nouadhibou, while catches from freezer trawlers are transported to Las Palmas (Canary Island, Outermost Region –Ors-EU) after landing in Mauritania) (Bouzouma et al., 2018, FarFish, 2019h).

In 2016, catches of black hake under *category 2* were at the highest level since 2008 (Figure 4), but the total catch in 2017 by both *category 2* and the new *category 2bis* was 8,060 t, approaching the limit of fishing opportunities allocated in *category 2* and *2bis* (total of 9,500 t) in the protocol. For European freezer vessels, the utilization was 97% in 2017, in terms of catches made in just five and a half months (Bouzouma et al., 2018).

Table 3: Landings of Black hake by EU hake vessels, Mauritania, other and bycatch in non-hake fisheries in the period from 2008 to 2017. Source: Bouzouma et al., (2018)⁶³.

Fleet	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
EU trawl Fresh (Cat.2)	5,727	5,429	3,847	3,273	3,135	3,992	2,609	135	5,833	5,082
EU trawl Frozen (Cat.2bis)										2,978
EU fresh longline	169									
Mauritania trawl frozen									n.d	n.d
Other trawlers	25			12						
Demersal and pelagic trawl	817	1,652	1,487	3,578	3,060	484	3,029	3,568	7,076	4,646
Total	6,738	7,081	5,334	6,863	6,195	4,476	5,638	3,703	12,909	12,706

⁶³ Based on data from Secretaría General de Pesca (SGP) - Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO) for Spanish flag vessels; Mauritanian Institute for Oceanographic Research and Fisheries (IMROP) for other vessels; 2014 and 2015 are years of partial activity, 2016 and 2017 are underestimated. n.d.: not available

Figure 4: Landings (t) of black hake (*Merluccius polli* and *M. senegalensis*) by fleets operating in Mauritania's fishing zone for the period 2008-2017 (Black line: Total, red line Spanish demersal category 2 (fresh), blue line: Bycatch in other demersal and pelagic trawls, green line: frozen category 2bis. Source: Bouzouma et al., 2018)

The main bycatch species in black hake fisheries under *category 2* and *2bis* were estimated at 11% for 2016 and 2017, which is well below the accepted 25% value set in the agreement. The most frequent bycatch species families are: Zeidae, Sparidae, Scorpaeniformes, Lophidae, Ophidiidae and some different species of elasmobranchs (Bouzouma et al., 2018). The most frequent bycatch species are John dory *Zeus Faber* (23%), Silvery John Dory *Zenopsis conchifer* (21.6%) and Anglerfish *Lophius Sp.* For 2bis, the reported bycatch accounts for 10% of the total catch. This bycatch is largely dominated by horse mackerel (EC, 2019).

2.2 Stock status of target species

The black hake is a shared resource in the subregion between Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal and Gambia; the two species *M. polli* and *M. senegalensis* are generally assessed as one *Merluccius spp.* The stock is considered fully exploited (although not overfished, $B_{cur} > B_{0.1}$) by the FAO/CECAF Working group on the Assessment of Demersal Resources Subgroup North in 2017, as shown in (Table 4, FAO, 2018a). The catch level the last years at approximately 17,000 t in the whole subregion, where the potential is estimated to 10,900, is not considered sustainable in the short term (FAO, 2018b).

Table 4: Summary of stock assessment of black hake stocks in CECAF North area in 2017 and management recommendations. Source: FAO (2018b)

	Catches (tonnes) 2016 [Average 2012-2016]	Bcur/B0.1	Fcur/F0.1
Sub-regional stock of black hake: <i>Merluccius polli</i> and <i>M. senegalensis</i>	16,972 [9,668]	115%	137%
Evaluation	Fully exploited - The catch level of the last year is not sustainable in the short term. This stock has also been evaluated by other models (Bayesian and CMSY which give the same situation as Biodyn ⁶⁴)		
Management Recommendations	Given the relatively low level of effort targeting black hake and the bycatch of these species in 2016 (7,076 tons), the Working Group recommends that the necessary steps be taken to reduce bycatch at the average of the 2014-2015 period (3,300 tons)		

The last IMROP calculation Group (2014) estimated the catch potential in Mauritanian EEZ at 11,700 tons per year, while total catch has been close to 13,000 tons in 2016 and 2017 (Table 3) and is probably an underestimate as the catch data from the Mauritanian trawl fleet chartered by Namibia is missing. The CSC does not consider the catch level in 2017 sustainable and concluded that an increase in effort and catches cannot currently be introduced in the Mauritanian black hake fisheries (Table 3, Bouzouma et al., 2018).

Catches of black hake in Mauritania constitutes for a large proportion of the total catch of the two species in the sub-region of Mauritania, Senegal, Morocco and Gambia. The total catch in the sub-region increased from approximately 9,000 tons in 2006 to 16,000 in 2016 and exceed the catches of white hake (*Merluccius Merluccius*) in the northern CECAF zone (Figure 5, FAO, 2018b). About 13,000 tons, which is possibly an underestimation, were taken in Mauritanian waters by all fleets combined the same years (EC, 2019).

Due to an increased fishing mortality exceeding F0.1 (137%), there is considered a risk of overexploitation of the stock in short-term if the current catch levels are maintained (FAO, 2018b). The catch levels during the last years have been at approximately 17,000 t in the whole sub-region, which is well above MSY that is estimated to be 10,900 tons (FAO 2018b). CECAF recommend that steps should be taken to reduce the bycatch of black hake in non-hake fisheries to the 2014-2015 levels i.e. 3,300 tons (FAO, 2018a).

⁶⁴ Biodyn: Assessment tool, spreadsheet approach assists understanding of models and allows for adaptation, here for Schaefer surplus model. Bayesian refers to statistical method applied.

Figure 5: Capture of hake in northern zone of CECAF (1990-2016). Source: FAO/CECAF (2018b)

2.3 Specific challenges in CS related to black hake

The following challenges have been identified during the development of this MR, several of them taken from the CSC report of 2018 (FarFish, 2019a, D3.3, D3.4):

2.3.1 Lack of level playing field where all operators oblige to the same rules

The European Union has also established a system concerning fishing activities of Union fishing vessels fishing outside Union waters under SFPA agreements and on the high seas⁶⁵; the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) requires SFPAs to be limited to surplus catches and to provide a comprehensive report of all catches and by catches via the electronic logbook / ERS.

Furthermore, the CFP stresses the need to promote the objectives of CFP internationally, ensuring that Union-fishing activities outside Union waters area based on the same principles and standards as those applicable under Union law, while promoting a level playing field for Union operators and third-country operators.

The EU vessels report on their position (VMS) and catch (e-logbook) both to the control authorities of their flag states and to the authorities of Mauritania (via paper logbook) on a daily/weekly basis. Through this system, it is possible to perform a real time monitoring of the quota consumption under the reference tonnage allocated under each of the categories.

However, for the non-EU fleets operating under private / chartering agreements charter in Mauritania, there is little knowledge on the vessels catching black hake and the categories and quota allocation for

⁶⁵ REGULATION (EU) 2017/2403 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 12 December 2017 on the sustainable management of external fishing fleets, and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008

each of them and which have incidence in the sustainability of the stock. As a result, there are no official statistics available from the Coastal State and they are also not included for the estimation of the surplus in the scientific assessments.

Furthermore, the ex-ante and ex post evaluations of the SFPA agreement are helpful to understand what the main problems are, and recommendations made by the governing bodies, including the Scientific Committee and the Mixed Committee dealing with management.

In view of the above, it is clear that there is a lack of level playing field between EU and non-EU operators in terms of catch reporting and use of these data for stock assessments. However, it is worthwhile to note that Mauritania has joined the Fisheries Transparency Initiative (FiTI) which will develop a report with information in relation to improve information on fishing activity of all fleets within the Mauritanian EEZ and governance structures through annual country reports.

2.3.2 Divergent conversion factors used in logbooks to obtain live weight

The estimation of conversion factor applied by IEO and IMROP for black hake is currently using different criteria, so it creates misunderstanding and loss of value for operators. This issue was addressed at the last CSC meeting and the CSC recommends application of 1.51 (IEO) which is based on recent IEO study.

2.3.3 Data limitation for sustainable conservation and separate stock assessment of black hake

Due to their morphological resemblance and overlapping occurrence at certain depths, both species are mixed in catches and are commonly marketed as *Merluccius* spp (FAO, 2016). Neither in the SFPA agreement, nor in the stock assessment by CECAF it is discriminated between the two species, even though they have different biological characteristics and should therefore preferably be managed separately (Fernández-Paralta et al., 2017). The two species are reported together as black hake in catch statistics by CECAF/FAO and in STECF annual reports.

2.3.4 High bycatch of black hake in non-hake fisheries

Black hake occurs frequently as bycatch in other non-hake fisheries, especially in the pelagic fishery. Both the CSC and the demersal working group in CECAF raise the concern of this bycatch and the management recommendation from CECAF is that the necessary steps must be taken to reduce bycatch at the average of the 2014-2015 period (3,300 tons).

2.3.5 Bycatch in black hake fisheries

The main activity related to bycatch reporting is being made by operators and onboard scientific observers, but those observers are not providing to the operators the observers report or any

feedback, thus encouraging lack of transparency and no incentives for them to cooperate. There is a need to improve communication between authorities and operators to exchange experiences and views on fisheries data reporting and exchange of data, identifying gaps and trying to promote research initiatives such as industry-science partnerships.

2.3.6 Insufficient monitoring of the consumption of TAC

According to Article 2 in the Protocol, the EU and Mauritania shall ensure joint monitoring of catches and when the catches within a category reaches 80% of the annual TAC, the catches should be monitored monthly. The establishment of ERS will improve the monitoring of TAC consumption. Mauritania is in the process of setting up an alert mechanism to track TAC consumption in the GCM system (EC, 2019).

3 Outcome targets and indicators

This chapter identifies the outcome targets and associated indicators established to provide measurable performance goals for the EU DWF fishery under the SFPA agreement between Mauritania and the EU. The OTs may address different dimensions (Ecological, Governance and Socioeconomic) of the fishery in question and are classified as obligatory or recommended, with a certain degree of flexibility to adapt to the realities and the evolution of the defined CS throughout the lifetime of the project. Only obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version of the MR, as they are considered important to reach the main objectives of the MR for this CS. The obligatory OTs for the Mauritanian CS relate to the fishery of black hake, small pelagics and shrimp as listed in the MR Invitation D3.2 (FarFish, 2019a).

An OT is usually a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B'), but it can also be a statement of presence or absence of some entity, in which a statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time. The indicator is a variable, pointer or an index related to a criterion. Its position and trend in relation to reference points (if available) or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. The indicators that relate to the OTs should commonly be SMART, namely Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timely. An example of a biological/ecological indicator could be the fishing mortality (F); an example of economic indicator could be the EBITDA (Earnings before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization); and a social indicator could be the number of jobs created.

The suggested indicators in FarFish are set to measure the degree of adherence to the OTs Table 5 and are classified according to their level of measurability. The most detailed indicator category A, is where the level of achievement of OT is quantitative, measured in percentage. Indicator category B is qualitative, where the level of OT achievement is considered to be high level (score level 4), moderate level (score 3), fair level (score 2), low level (score 1) or not present (score 0). The last indicator category is binomial, measured to have only two outcomes such as yes (score 1) or no (Score 0), true or false, success or failure.

Table 5: FarFish indicator categories (A- quantitative, B- qualitative C-binomial) and the level of OT achievement

Indicator category	Level of OT achievement				
A	100%	75 %	50 %	25 %	0 %
B	High level (HL) 4	Moderate level (ML) 3	Fair Level (FL) 2	Low Level (LL) 1	Not present (NP) 0
C	Yes (true/success) 1				No (False/Failure) 0

3.1 Obligatory OTs and associated indicators

WP3 defined the OTs listed in the MR Invitation D3.2 (FarFish, 2019a) based on the “pre-invitation dialogues” and the MR kick-off meeting in Vigo (Spain, June 2018). The obligatory OTs related to the black hake fishery were given priority in this first loop of MR for Mauritania, where a consensus has been reached between authorities and operators. The development of management recommendations and OTs related to the fishery of the small pelagics requires a differentiated strategy that needs to be further reinforced into the second loop.

3.1.1 Estimate the proportion of the two species of black hake in the catch composition (OT 5.1)

This OT is classified with an ecological dimension as reflects the knowledge strengthening of the black hake fishery, being in line with both MFMP first goal and the recommendation by CSC "Development and implementation of a sampling protocol allowing catches of the two species of black hake to be differentiated, to provide a separate assessment for each of the two stocks".

There is a strong indication of dominance of *M. Polli* in previous studies (Fernández-Peralta et al., 2017), both by surveys and visual identification on board by trained observers and/or skippers and fishermen. With the introduction of the new fishing *Category 2bis* in 2017, targeting deeper fishing areas, it is important to gain knowledge on the proportion of the two species in this fishery. It is also important to follow up on previous studies, to support comparison of historical catch composition of the two black hake species, as the proportion of *M. senegalensis* has been increasing the last years (2016 and 2017) reported in the CSS report of (2018). Hence, the following OT was proposed in the MR Invitation (FarFish, D3.2):

OT 5.1 Enhance data collection to enable for an accurate estimation of the proportion of *Merluccius polli* and *Merluccius senegalensis* in the total black hake catch composition. **(Obligatory OT).**

To make the OT more in line with the RFMS approach, it has been rephrased to, with the approval of the authority (WP3) to:

OT 5.1 Estimate the proportion of *M. polli* and *M. senegalensis* into the catch composition. **(Obligatory OT).**

In order to measure the performance of OT 5.1, the following indicators are suggested (Table 6):

- **I_1_CS5:** Visual identification of black hake species from subsamples
- **I_2_CS5:** Collection fin samples for molecular analysis
- **I_3_CS5:** Preliminary molecular analysis study to verify visual identification of black hake

Comments from operators:

OPROMAR represents trawlers who are already doing some on board identification and separate storage, as both species have different FAO identification codes *M. Polli* (HKB) and *M. Senegalensis* (HKH). The Spanish Scientific Institute (IEO) has been training observers for visual identification of both hake species and provided guides to skippers and crews; thus, anglers could be able to identify each species. Opromar were not completely against visual ID of black hake, but stress that such identification could contain mistakes or inaccuracies as it is done very fast during the fishing operations due to logistic issues. The operators propose to proceed with the identification of species on the port after landing, as it is more efficient in terms of logistic operations.

3.1.2 Collecting data on black hake occurring as bycatch in non-hake fisheries (OT 5.2)

The CSC notes the importance of the accessory catches of black hake, seemingly by the pelagic vessels. It recommends that the data of this pelagic fishery and the rest of the fleets catching black hake as bycatch are clarified on the databases and followed (observations at sea and sampling done at landings) with the aim of clarify their impacts on the black hake stocks (Bouzouma et al., 2018).

This OT is classified with an ecological dimension as reflects the knowledge strengthening of the black hake fishery, to provide a separate assessment for each of the two species following the same arguments as for OT 5.1. There is to our knowledge, no information on the proportion of the two black hake species reported bycatch. Given the quantity this bycatch, it is considered important that these vessels collect data, identify and report the proportion of the two black hake species in their catch, in line what is requested for the fleet targeting black hake. Hence, the following OT was proposed in the MR Invitation D3.2 (FarFish, 2019a):

OT 5.2 Improved data collection and reporting from all operators fishing black hake in Mauritanian waters where data on catches and landings of all species are reported via electronic reporting system (ERS). **(Obligatory OT).**

During the development of this MR1 this OT has been revised and rephrased (with the approval of the authority (WP3) to:

OT 5.2 Collecting data of the black hake as bycatch by all operators in Mauritanian waters. **(Obligatory OT).**

In order to measure the performance of OT 5.2, the following indicators are suggested (Table 6):

- **I_4_CS5:** Training of skippers and crews in visual species identification of black hake.
- **I_5_CS5:** Visual species identification from subsamples of black hake as bycatch species.
- **I_2_CS5:** Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis.
- **I_3_CS5:** Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake species.

Table 6: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome Targets and suggested indicators

Management goal	Management objectives	Outcome Target (OT)	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries (SFPA), Improved knowledge of fisheries resources (MFMP), Conserve and Sustainable use of the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development (SDG 14)	Improve the quality of the current stock assessment for the species included in the agreement	OT 5.1 Estimate the proportion of <i>M. polli</i> and <i>M. senegalensis</i> into the catch composition OT Dimension: Ecological	I_1_CS5: Visual identification of subsamples black hake species by vessels targeting black hake
			I_2_CS5: Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis
			I_3_CS5: Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake species
		OT 5.2 Collecting data of the black hake bycatch by all operators in Mauritanian waters OT Dimension: Ecological	I_4_CS5: Training of skippers and crews in visual species identification from subsamples of black hake
			I_5_CS5: Visual species identification from subsamples of black hake
			I_2_CS5: Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis
			I_3_CS5: Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake species

Table 7: Indicators related to obligatory OTs in MR1

Outcome target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator scoring	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 5.1	I_1_CS5: Visual identification of black hake species by vessels targeting black hake	B	1	Operators
OT 5.1/OT 5.2	I_2_CS5: Collection of fin samples from visually identified black hakes for molecular analysis	C	0	Operators / Authority
OT 5.1/OT 5.2	I_3_CS5: Preliminary molecular analysis to verify visual identification of black hake	A	0%	Authority
OT 5.2	I_4_CS5: Training of skippers and crews in visual species identification from subsamples of black hake	C	0	Operators/Authority
OT 5.2	I_5_CS5: Visual species identification from subsamples of black hake as bycatch species	B	0	Operators

3.1.3 Obligatory OTs related to small pelagics (OT 5.5 and OT 5.6)

As mentioned above, the development of MRs and OTs related to the fishery of small pelagic requires a differentiated strategy that needs to be further reinforced into the second loop of the project. The following obligatory OTs have been identified for the small pelagics fishery.

OT 5.5 Improved data collection and reporting from all operators fishing for small pelagics in Mauritanian waters where data on landings and catches of all species are reported via electronic reporting (E logbook should include target species, bycatch species and discard where applicable) **(Obligatory OT)**

OT 5.6 Full on-board observer coverage on all high-capacity pelagic vessels **(Obligatory OT)**.

3.1.4 Obligatory OT related to the shrimp fishery (OT 5.4)

The MR invitation (FarFish D3.2) included one obligatory OT for the shrimp fishery, but it was also acknowledged that there would probably be little interest among operators to enter RFMS for the fishery due to declining catches and increased efforts after important fishing grounds were closed off for the EU fleet. The OT as identified in the MR invitation was as follows:

OT 5.4: Registration and reporting of all catches in the shrimp fishery, including bycatches. **(Obligatory)**.

This OT was however slightly rephrased and changed in priority from obligatory to recommended at the CS/WP meeting in Mindelo (Cape Verde, Nov 2018). The OT is now as follows:

OT 5.4 Increase knowledge and data collection of all catches in the shrimp fishery, including by-catches. **(Recommended OT)**.

3.2 Recommended OTs

The recommended OTs, which will strengthen the MR are listed below. Strategies to achieve the recommended OTs will be developed in the second version of the MR (MR2). The following recommended OTs were proposed in the MR Invitation D3.2 (FarFish, 2019a):

OT 5.3: Improved data collection and reporting from all operators fishing for small pelagics, in Mauritanian waters where data on landings and catches of all species are reported via electronic reporting (E logbook, target, bycatch and discard where applicable) (**Recommended OT**).

OT 5.7: Increase knowledge and data collection of all fleets fishing for small pelagics on trade flows. (**Recommended OT**).

Also, as previously mentioned, OT 5.4 changed priority from obligatory to recommended after meeting in Mindelo (Cape Verde, Nov. 2018):

3.3 Other potential actions as supplement to the MR

Apart from the OTs identified for the EU fleet operating in Mauritania, a number of action points have been identified that could strongly support the case study objectives identified in the MPO. These action points have not been included in the list of OTs as they cannot be solely operationalised by the operators, as they require input/action from other relevant parties (authorities, scientific institutions, other international fleets, etc.). These are:

- Improved quality of current stock assessments for **black hake**, with separate stock assessments for the two species. FarFish will aim to contribute to this with collection of new data that enables separation between the two species. FarFish will as well attempt to build competences amongst relevant stakeholders to separate between the two species.
- Knowledge gap analysis is needed, in order to identify key knowledge and data gaps, for **small pelagics**. The responsibility for this cannot realistically be placed on the operators alone. This is at least partly to be addressed within the FarFish project.
- Effort should be put into increasing local demands and local markets for **black hake**, including those in other African countries e.g. Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire and Cameroon. Analysis of the Mauritanian black hake value chains will be a part the FarFish project, which will potentially contribute to this.
- Socio-economic effects and conditions linked to **small pelagics** need to be analysed in more detail than has been done until now i.e. employment, human consumption and value. This will to a point be addressed in FarFish.
- Develop user friendly, **digital maps** (VMS/AIS based) with the intention of: a) demonstrating the EU fleet's good compliance in reporting of activities and avoidance of identified VMEs (thus creating pressure on other international fleets to do the same), b) mapping fishing activities of other distant water fleets operating in Mauritanian waters, and c) visualise the frequency of VMS/AIS gaps.

4 Management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning

This section outlines and describes the strategies and key measures by which the authorities/operators plan to achieve the obligatory OT 5.1 and OT 5.2. Potential risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving the OTs are mentioned.

4.1 Strategies and risk for achieving OT 5.1

A guide to visual identification of the two species of black hake in catch composition has been developed by Fernández-Peralta et al (2018) and some skippers and crew at vessels targeting black hake, in addition to IEO observers, have been trained to do such identification. This visual identification should be implemented at all vessels targeting black hake, both freezer trawlers (*Category 2bis*) and fresh trawlers (*Category 2*) either by skippers and crews or by scientific observers. Further, the method of visual identification of black hake species should be verified by molecular analysis. If the fleet succeed in visual identification of black hake species, the next step would be to standardize catch report templates to include separate reporting for the two species, a strategy for such standardization will be explored in the next loop of the MR.

FarFish has already started the progress to facilitate this action by approaching operators to ask for their cooperation. FarFish will encourage operators to visually identify the black hake species *M.polli* and *M.senegalensis* following the guidelines provided by Fernández-Peralta et al (2018) from subsamples of black hake catches and to collect fins samples for molecular analysis from the identified fish. As vessels represented by FarFish partner OPROMAR fishing under *Category 2* and *2Bis* already do some onboard identification and storage, and IEO has developed an identification guide (Fall et al., 2018, Appendix 5), fishermen should be able to identify the fish by species. However, all the current vessels who have agreed to participate are freshfish trawlers. FarFish will strive to get identification by species from subsamples and collection of samples for molecular analysis also from the freezer trawlers who fish under *Category 2bis*.

A sampling protocol for the collection and preservation of samples for molecular analysis by the operators has been developed and will be updated if necessary. For the preliminary molecular study, samples of 20-30 fish from 10 - 20 hauls will be collected. These samples will be taken fresh onboard the fishing vessels and stored in small tubes of ethanol. For preliminary molecular analysis, WP2, by CS leader CCMAR will lead this work and has already established contact with the University of Oviedo in Spain to perform the molecular analysis.

Main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this OT would be (1) if the skipper or crew are not qualified or for other reasons not able to identify the black hake species visually, FarFish suggest two approaches do deal with this potential situation: (a) FarFish create training materials in accordance to the IEO identification guide or (b) Trained scientific observers can do the identification and collection of fin samples. Another risk related to the molecular analysis (2) where contamination of samples can occur and (3) risk of damage to samples during logistic procedures between vessels and laboratory. In order to minimize the risks related to failure in sampling and storage of samples for molecular analysis, a comprehensive protocol, potentially with video clips illustrating the sampling procedure, will be produced lead by WP2 leader CCMAR in collaboration with other task contributors. The risk of failure in laboratory analysis is reduced by following procedures for such analysis.

4.2 Strategies and risk for achieving OT 5.2

A similar approach as for OT 5.1 should be applied to identify black hake species and collect samples for molecular analysis should be applied for non-hake fleets catching black hake as bycatch. However, training materials in accordance to the IEO identification guide must be provided as this fleet has not been doing any species identification of black hake before. This is in line with the CSC recommendation that data from the accessory catches of the pelagic fishery and the rest of the fleet that fish black hake as bycatch are clarified in the databases and followed (observations at sea and sampling done at landings) with the aim to clarify their impacts on the black hake stocks. If the fleet succeed in visual identification of black hake species, the next step would be to standardize catch report templates to include separate reporting for the two species. A strategy for such standardization will be explored in the next loop of the MR.

Two approaches can be applied (1) Encourage the fleet to participate in a self-sampling program to identify the species and collect samples for molecular analysis or (2) Encourage authorities to train scientific observers to identify black hake species visually and to collect samples for molecular analysis to verify the visual identification.

FarFish will facilitate this by approaching the FarFish Reference Group member, Pelagic Freezer-trawler Association (PFA) and ask for their participation for visual identification of subsamples, collection and preservation of fin samples for molecular analysis. To our knowledge, there has been no species identification of black hakes when it occurs as bycatch.

4.3 Internal monitoring

In FarFish, the internal monitoring of development of OT 5.1 and OT 5.2 will be to follow up on the data collection and analysis. The operators representing vessels in *category 2* is responsible for visual identification and collection of samples for molecular analysis, assisted by WP2 leader CCMAR. If

possible, the same approach will be followed by vessels under *category 2bis* and for pelagic vessels represented by PFA. However, if training materials and guidelines is required, authority by task leader 3.3, MATIS, is responsible for providing this in collaboration with WP7, UNUFTP. WP2 leader, CCMAR, is responsible for the collection and all logistics related to molecular analysis.

4.4 FarFish recommendations aiming to achieve OT 5.1 and OT 5.2 summarized:

- (1) FarFish supports the recommendation by CSC to
- (2) Visual identification of black hake species by all fleets
- (3) Visual identification should be verified by molecular analysis
- (4) In the future, FarFish suggest that all operators and/or scientific observers shall be trained in visual identification of black hake onboard and be able to quantify the proportion of the two black hake species in their catch.
- (5) FarFish suggest that all fleets participate in self sampling by collection of fin samples for molecular analysis in a project to verify visual identification and to follow up on potential distribution changes due to environmental changes.
- (6) FarFish will create training materials in accordance with IEO guidelines, if requested by operators

4.5 Adaptive planning

Adaptive planning is shall admit for immediate adaptation within the planning period to support proper management of fisheries in case of abrupt changes occurs, for example political, distribution of fish stocks etc. This MR relies on data collection for the fishing fleet, which can be exposed to abrupt changes that would require adaptive planning due to for example changes in species distribution (area and/or depth). However, since the aim is to improve the knowledge of catch composition of the two species of black hake, subsamples will reflect what is actually caught and has an impact on the fishing mortality of the species.

5 Monitoring, compliance and sanctions

The obligatory OTs related to species identification of black hake, both as target and as bycatch species, entail that the participation in data collection by operators is crucial. An incentive for such data collection by operators can be rewarded by increased quota, or prioritized access to fishing areas for those who provide data and cooperate with self-sampling initiatives. The FMC of the fishing vessels should be responsible for the monitoring of the data collection by their fleet as part of the catch reporting system, once the templates include the possibility to report the two black hake species separately.

Nevertheless, requirements from other players than operators are required since operators have limited control over the overall process of analysis of the collected data and molecular analysis. The Scientific institution in charge of analysing the molecular samples should take the responsibility of facilitating all templates and provide all necessary equipment to collect samples. The same institution must take the responsibility of logistics for transportation of samples from the vessels to the laboratory. FarFish is not in the position to issue potential sanctions to operators not providing data collection.

6 Documentation

FarFish partner CCMAR has provided a sampling protocol (Annex 1) and will provide all necessary equipment and templates for collection fin samples for molecular analysis. FarFish partner MATIS and UNUFTP will provide the necessary training material and guidelines for visual identification if this is required.

Table 8: Documentation required for FarFish actions related to OTs

OT	Documentation	Responsible	Availability for auditor
OT 5.1 /OT 5.2	Template for sampling sheet.	Authority: CCMAR	Internal FarFish report available at the FarFish internal webpage
	Sampling protocol for collection of samples for molecular analysis.	Authority: CCMAR	
	Record for haul location, date, time and location.	Operators: (OPROMAR)	
	Record for visual species identification.	Operators: (OPROMAR)	
	Training materials and guidelines for visual identification.	Authority: MATIS and UNUFTP	

7 General considerations

The participation in data collection is crucial for improved stock assessment and sustainable management of black hake, but it must be emphasized that black hake is considered a shared stock between several coastal states. Therefore, all operators targeting black hake in the CECAF subregion Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal and The Gambia should carry out self-sampling to improve knowledge of the proportion of the two species of black hake in catch, including when black hake is captured as bycatch in pelagic or demersal trawl. A regional approach should follow up the previous work by Fernandez-Peralta and the actions FarFish will explore in this research project.

The scientific body responsible for data collection in each of the countries in the sub region where the black hake species in question are targeted, namely Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal and Gambia should be made responsible for initiating and monitoring of self-sampling, logistics and analysis. The results of the analysis should thereafter be reported to the working group of CECAF Demersal North adding valuable information on the stocks and future separate stock assessment.

8 Auditor

FarFish partner Syntesa will audit the RFMS process and implementation process and has agreed to this at the initial stage of FarFish. It is however possible to seek different auditors if necessary.

9 Planning process

The development of MRs depend on input from other Work packages and this first version is supported by the Case study characterization (FarFish 2017), First MR invitations (FarFish, 2019a), Draft 1 General Guidelines for making MRs (FarFish, 2019b), Management Plan Zero (FarFish, 2018a), Report from MR Kick-off meeting (FarFish, 2019c), Evaluation of governance structures of the cases (FarFish, 2019d), Developments needed to produce relevant management tools (FarFish, 2019e), Stakeholders hub (FarFish 2019f), Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB pilot version 1 (FarFish, 2018b), Visualization materials and tools for MR1 (FarFish, 2019g) and Description of CS value chains (FarFish, 2019h). WP5 will provide their audit of the MR1 in FarFish deliverable D5.2, which will be published in the autumn of 2019.

Tentative planning process

FarFish has approached OPROMAR and they have ensured the participation of three freshfish trawlers for data collection related to OT 5.1. FarFish partner CCMAR will explore the potential of data collection also by freezer trawlers represented by OPROMAR. A detailed plan for the data collection, sampling and molecular analysis will be ready by September 1st 2019.

FarFish has also approached PFA and asked for their participation in data collection for black hake. If they approve to participate, FarFish will provide a detailed plan for the data collection and training materials. If PFA vessels are unavailable to participate, FarFish will explore the second approach involving scientific observers for visual identification and collection of samples for molecular analysis.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Self-Sampling protocol

	Action	Scheme	Responsible to provide template
1	Record haul location, date, time and depth	CS4_1_vessel	CCMAR
2	For each fish: d) Assign a unique identifier and link to record haul location (code/number) e) Identify the species by morphological method f) Record total length and sex	CS4_2_Fish	CCMAR
3	Procedure for collection of samples g) Prepare tubes with ethanol h) Cut a small piece of fin (1 cm ²) and i) Put the small piece of the fin in tube with ethanol j) Label the tube with the unique identifier k) Clean/disinfect the scissors with ethanol before taking the next sample l) Store the tubes in a cool place	CS4_3_Procedure	CCMAR
5	Logistics Send the tubes with the sampling sheet containing the unique identifier, haul location, date, time, depth, species sex and total length data.	Address to analysing lab will be provided	CCMAR

Appendix 2. SFPA Fishing log

1.12.2015

EN

Official Journal of the European Union

Appendix 4

FISHING LOG

ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF MAURITANIA FISHING LOG		Name of vessel (1)		Left (4)		Date (6)		Time												
Call sign (2)		Name of master (3)		Returned (5)		Date (6)		Year												
Fishing gear (7)		Gear code (8)		Mesh size (9)		Gear measurements (10)		Month												
ITEM No 1		SECTION No 2		SECTION No 3		SECTION No 4		Day												
Date (12)	Statistical sector (13)	Number of fishing operations (14)	Duration of fishing (hours) (15)	HEADING No 3: Delete list A or B (whichever is unused) Estimate of quantities caught per species (in kg) (16) (or comments if fishing is interrupted)				Total catch weight (kg) (17)	Total weight of fish (kg) (18)	Total weight of fish meal (kg) (19)										
				Horse mackerel A	Sardines	Sardinellas	American plaice	Mackerel	Scabbard fish	Tunas	Hake	Red bream	Squid	Cuttlefishes	Shrimps	Octopus	Spiny lobster	Other fish		
				Spiny lobster B	Deep water shrimp	Deep water rose shrimp	Blue and red shrimp	Other shrimp	Albacore	Pink spiny lobster	Rough ray	Rough ray	Hake	Misc. cephalopods	Misc. shellfish	Misc. cephalopods	Misc. shellfish			

A. List

1. Horse mackerel
2. Sardines
3. Sardinellas
4. American plaice
5. Mackerel
6. Scabbard fish
7. Tunas
8. Hake
9. Read Bream
10. Squid
11. Octopus
12. Shrimps
13. Spiny lobster
14. Other fish

B. List

1. Spiny lobster
2. Deep water shrimp
3. Deep water rose shrimp
4. Other shrimp
5. Albacore
6. Pink spiny lobster
7. Other crustaceans
8. Rough ray
9. Hake
10. Other fish
11. Misc. cephalopods
12. Misc. shellfish

Appendix 3. SFPA Protocol Datasheets for Fishing Category 2

FISHING CATEGORY 2:

BLACK HAKE (NON-FREEZER) TRAWLERS AND BOTTOM LONGLINERS

1. Fishing zone

(a) North of latitude 19° 15' 60" N, west of the line joining the following points:

20° 46' 30" N	17° 03' 00" W
20° 36' 00" N	17° 11' 00" W
20° 36' 00" N	17° 36' 00" W
20° 03' 00" N	17° 36' 00" W
19° 45' 70" N	17° 03' 00" W
19° 29' 00" N	16° 51' 50" W
19° 15' 60" N	16° 51' 50" W
19° 15' 60" N	16° 49' 60" W

(b) South of latitude 19° 15' 60" N as far as latitude 17° 50' N, west of the 18-nautical mile line from the low-water mark.

(c) South of latitude 17° 50' N: west of the 12-nautical mile line from the low-water mark.

In the case of areas calculated on the basis of the low-water mark, the Joint Committee may replace the lines for delimiting zones with a series of geographical coordinates.

2. Authorised gear

- Bottom-set longline.
 - Bottom trawl for hake
 - Doubling of the cod-end is prohibited.
 - Doubling of the twine forming the cod-end is prohibited.
-

3. Minimum authorised mesh

70 mm (trawl)

4. Minimum Size

For fish, the minimum size is to be measured from the tip of the snout to the end of the caudal fin (total length) (see Appendix 7).

5. By-catches

Authorised	Not authorised
Trawlers: 25 % fish Longliners: 50 % fish	Cephalopods and crustaceans

The Joint Committee may determine by-catch rates for species not listed above.

The Joint Committee may determine by-catch rates for species not listed above.

6. Fishing opportunities/fees

Period	Year
Total allowable catch (tonnes):	6 000
Fee	90 EUR/t

The fee shall be calculated at the end of each period of three months in which the vessel is authorised to fish, taking into account the catches made during that period.

The licence shall be granted on advance payment of EUR 1 000 per vessel, to be deducted from the total amount of the fee. The advance payment shall be made at the beginning of each three-month period in which the vessel is authorised to fish.

The number of vessels authorised at the same time shall not exceed 6.

7. Biological rest periods

Where appropriate, the Joint Committee shall determine a biological recovery period based on the scientific opinion of the Joint Scientific Committee.

8. Comments

The fees are fixed for the entire period of application of the Protocol.

Appendix 4. Fishing category 6 Pelagic freezer trawlers (SFPA Protocol, Annex 1, Appendix 1, Datasheets)

FISHING CATEGORY 6:
PELAGIC FREEZER TRAWLERS

1. Fishing zone

Fishing is authorised to the west of a line defined as follows:

(a) North of latitude 19° 00' 00" N, the line joining the following points:

20° 46' 30" N	17° 03' 00" W
20° 36' 00" N	17° 11' 00" W
20° 36' 00" N	17° 30' 00" W
20° 21' 50" N	17° 30' 00" W
20° 10' 00" N	17° 35' 00" W
20° 00' 00" N	17° 30' 00" W
19° 45' 00" N	17° 05' 00" W
19° 00' 00" N	16° 34' 50" W
19° 00' 00" N	16° 39' 50" W

In the case of areas calculated on the basis of the low-water mark, the Joint Committee may replace the lines for delimiting zones with a series of geographical coordinates.

2. Authorised gear

Pelagic trawl

The bag of the trawl may be strengthened with a piece of netting with a minimum mesh size of 400 mm of stretched mesh and by straps placed at least 1,5 metres apart, except for the strap at the back of the trawl which may not be placed less than 2 metres from the window in the bag. Strengthening or doubling the bag by any other means is prohibited and the trawl may in no case target species other than the small pelagic species authorised.

3. Minimum authorised mesh

40 mm

4. Minimum Size

For fish, the minimum size is to be measured from the tip of the snout to the end of the caudal fin (total length) (see Appendix 7).

The Joint Committee may determine the minimum size for species not listed above.

5. By-catches

Authorised	Not authorised
3 % of the total for the authorised target species or group of species (live weight)	Crustaceans or cephalopods except squid

The Joint Committee may determine by-catch rates for species not listed in Appendix 7.

6. Fishing opportunities/fees

Period	Year
Total allowable catch (tonnes):	225 000 tonnes, which may be exceeded by a margin of 10 % without any impact on the financial contribution paid by the European Union for access
Fee	123 EUR/t

<p>The fee shall be calculated at the end of each period of three months in which the vessel is authorised to fish, taking into account the catches made during that period.</p> <p>The licence shall be granted on advance payment of EUR 5 000 per vessel, to be deducted from the total amount of the fee. The advance payment shall be made at the beginning of each three-month period in which the vessel is authorised to fish.</p> <p>The number of vessels authorised at the same time shall not exceed 19.</p>
--

7. Biological rest periods

A biological recovery period may be agreed by the Parties within the Joint Committee on the basis of the scientific advice of the Joint Scientific Committee.

8. Comments

The fees are fixed for the entire period of application of the Protocol.

The conversion factors for small pelagic species are specified in Appendix 8.

Unused category 8 fishing opportunities may be used at a rate of a maximum of 2 licences per month.

Appendix 5. Self-Sampling protocol in Spanish

Protocolo de muestreo merluza negra para análisis de DNA.

1. Registre la ubicación, fecha, hora y profundidad de cada lance en la hoja de muestreo
2. Para cada lance, seleccione entre 30-40 merluzas, al azar de entre toda la captura): asigne un identificador único (código / número), identifique la especie por el método morfológico (visual) y registre la longitud total y el sexo.
3. Corte un trozo pequeño de aleta (aprox.1 cm²), a poder ser de la parte terminal de la aleta la cual contiene rayos más delgados y más tejido. Para la correcta preservación del ADN, es necesario que el tejido no represente más de aproximadamente 1/4 del volumen total (1/4 tejido y 3/4 de etanol).
Coloque el tejido en un microtubo con tapón a rosca (de al menos 2ml, ejemplo: <https://www.zelian.com.ar/microtubo-a-rosca-esteril-con-tapon-de-2-ml-con-faldon-marca-deltalab-modelo-409115-6--det--PLA-00730>) conteniendo etanol absoluto (o etanol 96%). Previamente, colocar etiqueta con el identificador único dentro cada tubo. Es importante que la etiqueta no se borre con el alcohol. En muchos casos, utilizamos etiquetas impresas con impresoras laser/toner. Cada caja de almacenamiento de tubos (para 81 tubos, ver detalle abajo) será previamente rotulada con el rango de identificador único de los tubos que contiene, para facilitar su manejo durante el muestreo. Con el fin de evitar mezcla de muestras entre lances contiguos, se puede dejar una muestra vacía (sin muestra) entre lances.
4. Limpie / desinfecte las tijeras con etanol antes de tomar la siguiente muestra. Secar con un papel y verificar que no hay restos de tejido para evitar contaminaciones.
5. Guarde los tubos en un lugar fresco (e.g. nevera). Para almacenar los tubos, generalmente utilizamos cajas plásticas de 81 cavidades (ejemplo: <https://es.vwr.com/store/product/10637188/cajas-de-almacenamiento-para-viales-o-frascos-de-muestras>)
6. Envíe los tubos con la hoja de muestreo que contiene el identificador único, ubicación fecha, hora, profundidad, especie, sexo y datos de longitud total a CETMAR cuando los barcos regresen a Vigo.
7. Si transcurre mucho tiempo (semanas) entre la llegada a CETMAR y la extracción de ADN en Oviedo, es conveniente cambiar el etanol de cada tubo por etanol nuevo.
Si no transcurre mucho tiempo, esta tarea se hará en la Universidad de Oviedo.

SEYCHELLES CASE STUDY

Deliverable No. 4.3

Project acronym:

FarFish

Project title:

Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

Grant agreement No: **727891**

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme

Start date of project: **1st June 2017**

Duration: **48 months**

Due date of deliverable:	31/01/2019
Submission date:	23/09/2019
File Name:	FarFish D4.3_MR1 Seychelles
Revision number:	02
Document status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public

Role	Name	Organisation	Date	File suffix
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Deliverable D4.3

Management Recommendation 1

Seychelles

23/09/2020

Executive Summary

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) for the tuna fishery under the Fisheries Partnership Agreement (FPA) between the Seychelles and EU. The EU fleet targeting Yellowfin tuna (*Thunnus albacares*), Bigeye tuna (*Thunnus obesus*), and Skipjack tuna (*Katsuwonus pelamis*) are from Spain, France and Italy. The tuna species in Seychellois waters are managed by the framework of the Regional Fisheries Management Organisation (RFMO), The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC), while the Seychelles Fishing Authority (SFA) is the executive arm of government for fisheries within the Seychelles EEZ.

The Seychelles Fisheries Authority (SFA) and the Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE) are considered the competent authorities in this FarFish case study, but FarFish Work Package 3 (WP3) acts as the leading authority in the process of developing the MRs, considering input from the authorities and other stakeholders. The operators are represented by the Long Distance Advisory Council (LDAC), the Organisation of Associated Producers of Large Tuna Freezer Vessels in Spain (OPAGAC) and the National Association of Fish and Seafood Canning Manufactures- National Technical Centre for the preservation of Fish Products in Spain (ANFACO-CECOPECA), assisted by FarFish Work Package 1 and 4 (WP1 and WP4).

This MR1 is developed following the “draft General Guidelines for making MRs” presented in FarFish ([D3.1](#)) and is based on the Management Recommendation Invitation ([D3.2](#)), where the outcome targets (OTs) are proposed. Only the obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version of the MR. The proposed OTs area based on input from Management Plan Zero ([D4.1](#)), input from operators at the MR Kick-off meeting ([D4.2](#)) and additional stakeholder meetings facilitated by FarFish stakeholder interaction (WP1), and input from FarFish Work package (WP)/Case study (CS) leader meeting in Mindelo (Cape Verde, Nov. 2018). The recommended OTs will be address in the second version of the MR.

The aim of this MR is to improve data collection to promote sustainable fisheries and to improve monitoring, control and surveillance (MCS). The subsequent OTs are related to improved data standardization of fisheries information system, improved data collection on non-target species and improved MCS tools and compliance. The OTs are classified to ecological and governance dimension and we acknowledge that the operators cannot be solely made responsible for achieving the OTs. It must therefore be a joint effort between authorities and operators to make progress in this MR. Indicators are suggested to measure the performance of the OTs, and the strategy for achieving OTs is outlined. The strategies do not affect any of the current management conservation measures by IOTC, EU or the Seychelles.

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Abbreviations

AIS	Automatic Identification System
ANABAC	National Association of Tuna Freezer Vessel Shipowners (Spain)
AMSSI	Association of Members of the Seychelles Sea Cucumber Industry (Seychelles)
ANFACO-CECOPESCA	National Association of Fish and Seafood Canning Manufactures (Spain)
Bmsy	Maximum Sustainable Yield Biomass
BSFC	British/Seychelles Fisheries Commission
BSP	Bayesian Surplus Production model
CCMAR	Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal)
CETMAR	Centro Tecnológico del Mar - Fundación (CETMAR) (Spain)
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CMM	Conservation and management measures
COMESA	Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa
CPC	Contracting Party and Non-Contracting Party (IOTC)
CPUE	Catch per Unit Effort
CS	Case Study
CSC	Joint Scientific Committee
CSIC	Spanish National Research Council (Spain)
DFAD	Drifting Fish aggregating devices
DG MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (EU)
DWF	Distant Water Fleet
EC	European commission
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EFCA	European Fisheries Control Agency
EPA	Economic Partnership Agreement
ERS	Electronic Recording Systems
FAD	Fish Aggregation Device
FarFish RG	FarFish Reference Group
FBOA	Fishing Boat Owners Association
FIP	Fishery Improvement Program
FIS	Fisheries Information System
FITI	Fisheries Transparency Initiative
FMC	Fisheries Monitoring Centre
FOB	Floating Objects (including FADs)
FPA	Fisheries Partnership Agreement
FPAOI	The Federation of Artisanal Fishers of the Indian Ocean, Seychelles
GFE	Global Fishing Watch
ICMAN-CSIC	Institute for Marine Sciences of Andalucía (ICMAN)-Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) (Spain)
IMO	International Maritime Organization
INPESCA	Cía Internacional de Pesca y Derivados, S.A. (Seychelles)

IO	Indian Ocean
IOC	Indian Ocean Commission
IOT	Indian Ocean Tuna, a branch of Union Thai
IOTC	The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
IUU	Illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing
JDP	Joint Deployment Plans
LDAC	EU Long Distance Fleet Advisory Council
LL	Longline
MATIS OHF	Icelandic Food and Biotech R & D Institute (Iceland)
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance
MEECC	The Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MR	Management Recommendation
MSC	Marine Stewardship Council
MSY	Maximum Sustainable Yield
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NOFIMA	The Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture research (Norway)
OPAGAC	Organisation of Associated Producers of Large Tuna Freezer Vessels (Spain)
ORTHONGEL	Organisation of producers of frozen and deep-frozen tropical tuna (France)
OT	Outcome Target
PS	Purse Seine
RBM	Results-Based Management
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organization
RFMS	Responsible Fisheries Management System
SADC	South African Development Committee
SAMPER	Société Anonyme de Pêche Malgache et Réunionnais S.A. (France)
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SFA	Seychelles Fisheries Authority
SFPA	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements
SIDS	Small island developing state
SIOFA	South Indian Ocean Fisheries Agreement
SIOTI	The Sustainable Indian Ocean Tuna Initiative
SMSP	Seychelles Marine Spatial Planning (Seychelles)
SOLAS	Safety Of Life At Sea
SOTN	Seychelles Ocean Temperature Network
SYN	SP/F SYNTESA (Faroe Islands)
TAC	Total Allowable Catch
TNC	The Nature Conservancy
TRP	Target Reference Point

UIT	The Arctic University of Norway (Norway)
VME	Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems
VMS	Vessel Monitoring System
WIO	Western Indian Ocean
WWF	Worldwide fund for nature

Concepts/definitions

Indicator	A variable, pointer or index related to a criterion. Indicators are selected such that their variations reflect variations in key elements of the fishery resource, the social and economic well-being of the sector and the sustainability of the ecosystem. The position and trend of an indicator in relation to reference points or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. Indicators provide a bridge between objectives and actions (source: FAO 1999).
Management goals	The higher-order objective to which a management intervention is intended to contribute (OECD 2011). A management goal is derived from a management principle (constitutional-order) and is specified into a set of more operational management objectives (collective-order).
Management intervention	Strategies or instruments aimed to impact the state of a fishery with reference to authorized objectives. Examples are input and output controls and economic measures.
Management measures	Can be technical (e.g. gear selectivity etc.), input (effort)/output (catch) control, right based.
Management objectives	Fisheries management objectives are typically framed within the overall concept of sustainable development, and may reflect one or more of the various dimensions and criteria that relate to it (FAO 1999). Operators through setting and implementing management measures control OTs.
Management Plan (MP)	A fisheries management plan is a formal arrangement between a fishery management authority and interested parties which identifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, details the agreed objectives for the fishery and specifies the management rules and regulations which apply to it and provides other details about the fishery which are relevant to the task of the management authority (Source: FAO 2002).
Management Recommendation (MR)	In RFMS, the management recommendation (MR) is a formal arrangement between a management authority and operators that specifies the partners in the fishery and their respective roles, the agreed objectives for the fishery, the management rules and regulations that apply, and provides other relevant details about the fishery. In RFMS, the formal responsibility for developing the management plan is delegated to an operator.
Management strategies	In FarFish context, it means the strategies applied to achieve OTs
Outcome Target (OT)	Outcome targets (OTs) are specific and measurable requirements that are set by an authority to make management goals operational. An OT is a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B') or a statement of presence or absence of some entity. On the basis of relevant information, this statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time ⁵⁴ . For instance, the management objective that "the fishery should be biologically sustainable" could be expressed in terms of one or more OTs such as 'Catch < 20 000t; 'bycatch < 20%'; SSB > 30 000t; 'a catch reporting system is present', etc.
Reference point	A classification device, defined in relation to the measure of an indicator, for distinguishing different management relevant states of the system under management. A Biological Reference Point is a metric of stock status. A Target Reference Point indicates a state of a system which is considered desirable and at which management action should aim. A Limit Reference Point indicates a state of a system, which is considered to be undesirable, that one therefore should seek to avoid through relevant management action.
RFMS	Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) is a fisheries management approach developed within the FP7 project EcoFishMan . The RFMS is an adaptive management approach that is results-based and ecosystem-based. The RFMS attempts to reduce micromanagement by involving stakeholders and increase the degree of co-management by delegating management responsibilities to resource users.

1 Introduction

This document serves as the first proposal for a management recommendation (MR1) from European operators active in the Seychelles tuna fishery under the current Fisheries Partnership Agreement (FPA) which has a six-year duration 2014-2020. The MR1 is founded on Results-Based Management (RBM) principles and based on the Responsive Fisheries Management System (RFMS) approach (Figure 1), which was developed in the FP7 project EcoFishMan (Silva et al., 2014, Santiago et al., 2015, Nielsen et al., 2017). Basically, the MR is an agreement between competent authorities, relevant operators and potentially other stakeholders. In the MR, strategies are defined to achieve outcome targets (OTs) which are established by authorities in the MR invitation ([D3.2](#)) to support sustainable fisheries (FarFish, 2018a), while following the draft General Guidelines for making MRs ([D3.1](#)) developed in the FarFish project (FarFish, 2018b). Figure 1 shows the key steps in the RFMS process, from the initial planning to implementation and monitoring of success.

Figure 1: The RFMS process. The responsibilities of each of the three entities are demonstrated with different colours. Authority: red/Operators: blue/ Auditors: yellow (FarFish, 2018b).

The partners in the fishery and their respective roles and responsibilities are identified in the MR, which also provides a detailed overview of the fishery and the geographical boundaries for the MR, which were outlined in the Management Plan zero (MP0) in [D4.1](#) (FarFish, 2018c). The authority is the organizational entity acting in pursuit of the management objectives decided for a fishery (e.g. a coastal state or the European Commission). They oversee the RFMS process and issue the “MR invitation”, which includes a clear specification of measurable OTs, set in order to operationalize the goals of existing policies and the local management objectives.

The operator is defined as an organized group of resource users, e.g. an association of fishermen or stakeholders with rights in a given fishery. It is the organizational unit with delegated authority to develop MRs based on the OTs set by the authority and oversee or conduct fishing operations within the standards decided by a management authority. In line with the RFMS approach, the engagement of stakeholders is highly prioritized in FarFish. At the MR kick-off meeting in Vigo (Spain, June 2018),

operators representing the distant water fleet (DWF) from the European Union expressed their interests and needs (D4.2) (FarFish, 2018d), which were relevant for the development of the MR Invitation and defining the OTs, in which this MR1 will address.

1.1 Partners involved in MR1

The leader of Task 3.3 (Authority role within RFMS) in FarFish, MATIS, acts as the leading authority within the project, whilst considering input from relevant authorities e.g. Seychelles Fishing Authority (SFA) and the Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE). The European operator qualified to respond to the MR Invitation for Seychelles are the Long-Distance Advisory Council⁶⁶ (LDAC) represented by its Executive Secretary Alexandre Rodríguez, ANFACO-CECOPECA⁶⁷ and the Organisation of Associated Producers of Large Tuna Freezer Vessels⁶⁸ (OPAGAC). Three members form OPAGAC have participated in the MR1 meetings.

Table 1 shows the main parties involved in the development of the MR1, identifies the target species and gives other background data relevant for the RFMS process.

Table 1: MR1 Seychelles partners involved, geographical range, target species, main aims and planning period

MR basis	MR1 Seychelles		
Partners involved	Authorities: WP3, DG Mare, SFA		
	Operators: WP4, LDAC, OPAGAC, ANFACO-CECOPECA		
	Auditor: WP5, SYNTESA		
Target species	Common name	Scientific name	FAO code
	Yellowfin tuna	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	YFT
	Bigeye tuna	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	BET
	Skipjack tuna	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	SKJ
Geographical range	The Seychelles EEZ covers an area of 1,374,000 km ² of which only 50,000 km ² is a shelf area.		
Fleets	EU fleet: Spain, France, Italy, Portugal (last not active since 2016-2017) Tuna purse seiners, surface longline.		
Main aims of MR	The main aims this MR1 is to improve the scientific knowledge base for the fisheries management and support MCS activities and thereby enhance a level playing field for operators.		
MR planning period	Lifetime of the FarFish project (2017-2021).		

LDAC has a nominal composition of 60% of fishing sector organizations (including catching, processing and marketing sectors, and trade unions). The remaining 40% is represented by other groups of interests (mainly environmental and development NGOs). OPAGAC is one of the two main Spanish tuna fishing organizations representing the purse seine fleet. OPAGAC signed a Memorandum of

⁶⁶ <http://ldac.eu/>

⁶⁷ www.anfaco.es

⁶⁸ <http://opagac.org/>

Understanding⁶⁹ with the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) for the implementation of a Fishery Improvement Programme (FIP), intended to facilitate Certification of the OPAGAC Fishery with the Marine Stewardship Council (MSC), by or before the year 2021. ANFACO_CECOPECA is the National Association of Fish and Seafood Canning Manufactures- National Technical Centre for the preservation of Fish Products in Spain, representing the interests of more than 240 associate members from a multi-sectorial cluster linked to seafood producers and the industrial processing sector. The leader for work package 4 (WP4) in FarFish, UiT - The Arctic University of Norway, assists the representatives for operators in the development of the MR1.

1.2 Aims of MR1 for the Seychelles

This MR1 applies to the EU Fishery for tuna within the Seychelles EEZ (Figure 2) and aims to enhance the sustainability of the fishery by i) improving the scientific knowledge base for the fisheries management, ii) supporting the fight against IUU fisheries by utilizing the latest available satellite system and tool and iii) enhance a level playing field where all fleets comply by the commitment to honour Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).

1.3 Current Management Plan in Seychelles, CFP and relevant IOTC Recommendations

Fishing activities within the Seychelles are primarily governed by the Seychelles Fisheries Act of 2014 and the accompanying Fisheries Regulations of 1987 (FarFish, 2019 – [D3.3](#)). The Fisheries Act and associated Regulations specifies provisions for management measures, licensing requirements, enforcement measures, and sanctions. The Ministry of Fisheries and Agriculture has the overall mandate for policy and legislation in the area of fisheries and agriculture, while the Seychelles Fishing Authority (SFA), and is the executive arm of government for fisheries.

The SFA coordinates fisheries Monitoring Control and surveillance (MCS) through a specific section comprising the Monitoring and Control Unit and the Enforcement Unit (Goulding et al., 2019). The MCU hosts the Fisheries Monitoring Centre (FMC) which issues fishing authorisations and monitors compliance of all fishing vessels with lawful conditions applied. This includes the operations of satellite Vessel Monitoring System (VMS), the validation of statistical documents for ICCAT, IOTC, EU and Non-EU, including for the catch certificates (Goulding et al., 2019).

⁶⁹ https://fisheryprogress.org/system/files/documents_mou/MOU%20FIP%20OPAGAC-WWF%202016_0.pdf

Figure 2: Seychelles have the largest EEZ in the West Indian Ocean, covering almost 1.4 million km². Source: "Search for oil to begin in Seychelles-Mauritius managed area" The Seychelles News Agency 03 October 2018

The Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC), is leading the process for the development of the Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan (SMSP)⁷⁰ initiative, aiming to address climate change adaptation, marine protection and support the Blue Economy and other national strategies.

The Nature Conservancy (TNC) is a powerful NGOs which promotes conservation of oceans and development of a coherent network of Marine Protected Areas (MPA). They have funded the Seychelles administration with "Blue Bonds", which are a loan for signing off public debt in Exchange of adoption of conservation measures to achieve environmental targets (e.g. 30% of MPAs within Seychelles EEZ) in a given timeframe. An ecosystem-based approach is applied to review Gazetted coordinates for marine protected areas in conjunction with improved management for uses and activities within the Seychelles EEZ, as the area is a global biodiversity hotspot with two UNESCO World Heritage Sites. The designated zones will be implemented in 2021, on the completion of the marine spatial plan.

The Overall Policy Objective of the Government of Seychelles for the fishing industry is the "promotion of sustainable & responsible fisheries plus the development and optimization of the benefits from this sector for present and future generations". It is anticipated that this will be achieved via the:

⁷⁰ <https://seymsp.com/>

- Conservation & management of marine resources in order to ensure the sustainability and long-term viability of the industry
- Maximum generation of employment
- Maximization of revenue from fisheries & other related activities
- Promotion of an integrated economy
- Food supply and food security enhancement
- Promotion of safety at sea

The tuna and highly migratory species in Seychelles waters are managed by the framework of the Regional Fisheries Management Organization (RFMO) The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC)⁷¹ and Seychelles has been a member of IOTC since 1995. IOTC has the mandate to adopt conservation and management measures for tuna and billfish species in the Indian Ocean and a compendium of the active Conservation and Management Measures is published (IOTC, 2018a). These decisions are passed in the form of either Resolutions or Recommendations and the measures are legally binding to contracting parties, including the Seychelles and EU.

The European Union has also established a system concerning fishing activities of Union fishing vessels fishing outside Union waters under FPA/SFPA agreements⁷² and on the high seas. The Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) also requires SFPAs to be limited to surplus catches. EU has reformed the CFP, which came into effect in January 2014, stating that all EU fishing activities, inside and outside EU waters, are subject to the same environmental and other standards (EU, 2017). Thus, the EU must conduct its external fleet in accordance with the objectives and principles set out in Articles 2 and 3 of the CFP. According to Article 2, those objectives include the application and promotion of the precautionary approach to ensure that the stocks targeted are higher levels that deliver Maximum Sustainable Yield (MSY) by 2020 at the latest, the application of the ecosystem principle, the promotion of the collection of scientific data and the gradual elimination of discards.

The main objective of the CFP is to ensure that fishing activities are environmentally, economically and socially sustainable and are managed consistently with the objectives of achieving economic, social and employment benefits, and of restoring and maintaining fish stocks above levels which can produce maximum sustainable yield and that they are contributing to the availability of food supplies. Additionally, the union has committed itself to Sustainable Development Goal 14⁷³ (SDG 14) and Sustainable Development Goal 12⁷⁴ (SDG 12). EU vessels operating under the FPA agreement shall

⁷¹ www.iotc.org

⁷² REGULATION (EU) 2017/2403 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 12 December 2017 on the sustainable management of external fishing fleets, and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1006/2008

⁷³ SDG14: conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

⁷⁴ SDG12: ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns and their targets

comply with all technical conservation measures as set out in the FPA protocol Annex Chapter 1 (EC, 2014), including templates for fishing logbooks ([Appendix 1](#), [Appendix 2](#)).

The CFP stresses the need to promote the objectives of CFP internationally, ensuring that Union-fishing activities outside Union waters area based on the same principles and standards as those applicable under Union law, while promoting a level playing field for Union operators and third-country operators.

1.4 Identity of Fishery

Seychelles has the largest EEZ in the West Indian Ocean and majority of the fishery is conducted by international fleet consisting of purse seiners and industrial longline. The purse seine fishery targets mostly surface-swimming tuna (skipjack and yellowfin), while the longline fishery targets deep-swimming bigeye and yellowfin tuna (FarFish, 2019 - [D3.4](#)).

The current EU-Seychelles Fisheries Partnership Agreement (FPA) covers the period from 2014 to 2020 and allows for 40 tuna seiners and 6 surface longliners from Spain, France and Italy to target tuna and tuna-like species within Seychelles EEZ (Table 2). Portugal is also allowed to employ two surface longliners in Seychelles waters, but have not been active in recent years.

Table 2. Allocation of fishing opportunities in the Seychelles EEZ (Source: Goulding et al., 2019)

	Spain	France	Italy	Portugal	Total
Tuna seiners	22	16	2	-	40
Surface longliners	2	2	-	2	6

A total reference catch of 50 thousand tonnes per year is allowed during the current agreement period from 2014-2020 (Goulding et al., 2019). The purse seiner vessels mostly target skipjack and yellowfin tuna, while the surface longliners (very few currently active) mainly target bigeye and yellowfin tuna. The turnover of EU purse seiners under the current Protocol was approximately EUR 70 million per year on average over the 2014-2018 period, varying between EUR 39.2 million in 2015 and EUR 83.0 million in 2017 (Goulding et al., 2019).

OPAGAC, ANABAC and ORTHONGEL are the three main EU tuna purse seine operators within the Seychelles EEZ and the EU flag vessels operate under the public agreements (FPA) in force signed with the EU, but there are also Seychelles flagged boats owned by these companies. These agreements are published and it is known the money paid for access to fishing and sectoral support; as well as volume of annual catches by species and national fleets in tones; there are also specific provisions on control at sea and at ports, landing of fish for processing and composition/hiring of local crew.

2 Fishery overview

Fishing activity in the Seychelles can be divided according to three categories; artisanal, semi-industrial and industrial fisheries. Artisanal fisheries target coastal, inshore resources while semi-industrial fisheries target large pelagics such as tunas and swordfish. These two types of fisheries are carried out by boats that are locally owned and operated.

The main focus of FarFish is however industrial fisheries, using purse seine (PS) and longline (LL) gears in the Seychelles. This includes about 45-50 national and foreign PS vessels that operate under various agreements, but it is important to note that these operate both inside the Seychelles EEZ and outside in the Indian Ocean (IO). There are currently 12-13 large purse seiners operating under the Seychelles flag, most of which are under Spanish beneficial ownership (Goulding et al., 2019). Up to 5 PS vessels from Mauritius can fish under a Seychelles-Mauritius fisheries agreement, but only about two have operated in recent years, and an additional five Korean PS vessels have operated in the Seychelles EEZ (SFA 2016).

An average of 27 EU tuna purse seiners have drawn fishing authorisations in the period 2014-2018, which represents almost all EU tuna purse seiners active in the Indian Ocean, but only one longline vessel made use of fishing possibilities in 2016 and 2017 (none in 2018) (Goulding et al., 2019).

2.1 Processing sector and value chain

The information in this subchapter is extracted from training assessment needs report (FarFish, 2018f). The Seychelles is highly dependent on processing catch landed and supplied from the foreign fleets, notably Spanish purse seiners and, to a less extent, French. They have taken notorious steps to improve value addition in the country, but with limited success in practice. From a scientific point of view, they rely heavily on external consultants (mainly of French nationality and paid through the SFPA sectoral support) and there is little capacity to carry out a full analytical assessment of the commercial stocks through a peer reviewed robust advisory process within the current SFA staff. There is a lab operated by SFA which aims to experiment of value addition potential of underutilized species, however it has been so far underutilized.

There is at least one Seychellois processing facility that is dedicated exclusively to bycatch. The volume of raw material they are getting seems to be high enough to be profitable, and of good quality, but the facilities are not fit for purpose with structural defaults (no temperature or cold cameras insulation, lack of electricity power to run processing machine) and they do not fulfil the technical, health and sanitary requirements to qualify for processing and exporting transformed, processed and/or elaborated products for export to the EU market. Up to now, it is used to grade the fish, do the repackaging, and send it to Sri Lanka.

2.2 Recent trends- EU catch statistics and EU fleet

Catches of the EU PS fleet in the Seychelles EEZ have been on average 48,000 tonnes in the period 2014-2018 (Table 3). In 2017, total catches of the EU fleet amounted to 49,378 tonnes, mostly split between French and Spanish fleets, with Italy only taking around 3 thousand tonnes. Following the introduction by the IOTC of the full landing obligation from 2018, all bycatch is also landed to the Seychelles (Goulding et al., 2019). There are differences between EU fleet catches in the Seychelles EEZ in 2017, compared to their catches in the whole Indian Ocean. France (and one PS vessel from Italy) take about 37% of their catches inside the Seychelles EEZ, while Spain takes only about 16%.

Table 4 shows a breakdown of ‘Other species’ group, which can be considered bycatch of the EU PS fleet. An important component is albacore tuna, but these are small quantities as the main fishing grounds are further south in the IO. Bycatches are generally minor and include undetermined species (e.g. billfish and tunas). Note that certain species such as Dolphinfinch, Frigate tuna, and Wahoo are not assessed due to data limitations. On the other hand, albacore tuna and Kawakawa have been assessed and are considered to be exploited sustainably by the IOTC.

Another important component is the industrial longline fleets in the Seychelles fishing zone. This consists of fleets under the Seychelles flag as well as a number of other countries. The number of vessels with licenses have varied greatly, but this was 158 vessels in 2015, including 45 under the Seychelles flag, 85 Taiwanese, and 19 from China, as well as a few other vessels from other countries such as Oman, Philippines, Tanzania and Thailand (SFA 2016). Most are reported to be still operating (Goulding et al., 2019).

Table 3: Total EU tuna catches (tonnes) in the Seychelles EEZ. A breakdown of EU catches is also given on PS catches inside the Seychelles EEZ and in the whole Indian Ocean. (Unit: tonnes) (Source: DGMARE & Goulding et al., 2019)

Entity	Species	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	Avg
EU	Yellowfin tuna	23,384	17,205	30,095	24,579	16,610	22,375
	Skipjack tuna	15,160	12,656	28,206	19,971	33,457	21,890
	Bigeye tuna	3,416	2,075	3,452	4,062	5,249	3,651
	Other species	56	49	179	121	39	89
	Total	42,016	31,985	61,932	48,733	55,355	48,004
EU breakdown							
Spain	Whole IO	133,720	120,890	136,147	151,392		135,537
	Seychelles	20,179	16,791	30,631	23,914		22,879
	% Seychelles	15%	14%	22%	16%		17%
France & Italy	Whole IO	58,339	54,390	68,250	66,934		61,978
	Seychelles	21,837	15,194	31,301	24,818		23,288
	% Seychelles	37%	28%	46%	37%		38%

Table 4: Breakdown of bycatch species (other species) in EU catches (tonnes) (Source: DGMARE)

Code	Species	2014	2015	2016	2017
ALB	Albacore	56.4	49.3	95.7	111.9
BIL	Billfish			1.8	
BLM	Black Marlin			0.6	1.8
DOL	Dolphinfish			1.0	0.4
FRI	Frigate tuna			3.0	3.3
LTA*	Kawakawa				3.1
TUN	Tuna nei			76.2	
WAH	Wahoo			0.8	0.2
		56.4	49.3	179.1	120.8

Note*: This is presumably *Euthynnus affinis* so this is a misidentification and the code should be KAW

As in the case of the purse seiners, these longline vessels operate both within and outside the Seychelles EEZ. A reported total of 59 longline vessels are registered under the Seychelles flag in 2019, but some do not operate within the EEZ at all and have until now not been required to draw a licence for this activity (Goulding et al., 2019). All of these vessels are owned and operated by Chinese operators and the main target is bigeye tuna for the sashimi market (Goulding et al., 2019).

The available data for 2014 and 2015 indicate total LL catches of 18,000 and 14,200 tonnes, respectively (Table 5). Note that these are the LL vessels licensed to fish in the Seychelles, not the whole LL fleet operating in the Western Indian Ocean (WIO). The catch estimates are presumably underestimated by about 10%, since the data is based on the return of logbooks, which was about 90% (SFA, 2016). The proportion of the catches taken inside the Seychelles EEZ varies from about 30 to 55 %. According SFA, the Seychelles fleet of 13 PS vessels caught a total of 88,740 tonnes of tunas in 2015, of which 11,650 tonnes were taken inside the Seychelles EEZ (13%). This is similar to the Spanish PS fleet and as explained before, most of these vessels are under Spanish beneficial ownership, thus operating with the same fishing strategy.

Table 5: Total catches (tonnes) by the longline fleets under license to fish in the Seychelles EEZ. This is presented separately for vessels under the Seychelles flag and all fleets together, indicating how much of the catches are taken inside and outside the Seychelles (Source: SFA 2016)

Fleet	Year	SYC EEZ	Catch	Percentage species composition					
				Yellowfin	Bigeye	Swordfish	Marlin	Shark	Other
Seychelles	2014	WIO	10,689	15	49	9	6	5	15
		SYC EEZ	3,031	21	61	6	5	4	2
Seychelles	%		28%						
	2015	WIO	12,255	18	46	13	10	3	9
		SYC EEZ	3,205	30	50	9	7	3	1
	%		26%						
All	2014	WIO	18,000	19	51	8	7	6	10
		SYC EEZ	9,927	23	55	7	6	7	3
	%		55%						
All	2015	WIO	14,243	19	47	12	10	4	8
		SYC EEZ	5,054	28	49	8	8	4	2
	%		35%						

(Source: SFA 2016)

The above data confirms that bigeye tuna is main target of these LL vessels with substantial catches of yellowfin tuna and swordfish as well (Table 5). The other species can be considered bycatches, including unspecified marlin and shark. Blue shark is presumed to be the dominant species caught as bycatch. As presented in the beginning of this section, there are concerns about the status of the yellowfin and several billfish stocks, which imply that LL fisheries are also subject to measures such as the rebuilding of the yellowfin tuna stock and limitations on capacity.

2.3 Stock status of target species

Stock assessments are carried out regularly by specific Working Parties that then report to the IOTC Scientific Committee. It is however important to bear in mind that the models used for stock assessment depend on the available data, and in some cases, it is not considered possible to carry out a full formal assessment such as in the cases of various neritic tuna species and other bycatch species. Various indicators are used instead (e.g. catch, CPUE, size, etc.), when the data does not provide for a formal assessment.

Tropical tunas such as yellowfin, skipjack and bigeye tuna are the main targets of the industrial purse seine (PS) fishery and are of particular importance to the EU PS fleet. Bigeye and skipjack tunas are being fished sustainably, but the stock of yellowfin tuna is considered to be overfished as well as being subject to overfishing, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Stock status of species under management by the IOTC. The term sustainable is used to indicate that the stock is not overfished (biomass at safe level) and not subject to overfishing (fishing mortality at acceptable level). See notes below for exact meaning of these terms

Species	Total IO Catch in 2017 (unit: tons)	MSY estimate (80% CI) (unit: 1000 tons)	Kobe colour codes	Stock Status	Year of full assessment
Tropical tunas					
Bigeye tuna (<i>Thunnus obesus</i>)	90,050	104 (87-121)		Sustainable	2016
Skipjack tuna (<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>)	524,282	≈ 510.1 (455.9-618.8)		Sustainable	2017
Yellowfin tuna (<i>Thunnus albacares</i>)	409,567	403 (339-436)		Overfished & subject to overfishing	2018
Billfish					
Swordfish (<i>Xiphias gladius</i>)	34,782	31.59 (26.30-45.50)		Sustainable	2017
Black marlin (<i>Makaira indica</i>)	21,250	12.93 (9.44-18.20)		Probably sustainable, but uncertain	2018
Blue marlin (<i>Makaira nigricans</i>)	12,155	11.93 (9.23-16.15)		Not overfished but subject to overfishing	2016
Striped marlin (<i>Tetrapturus audax</i>)	3,082	4.73 (4.27-5.18)		Overfished & subject to overfishing	2018
Indo-Pacific sailfish (<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>)	33,280	25.0 (16.18-35.17)		Not overfished but subject to overfishing	2015
Sharks					
Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>)	≈52,000	33.1 (29.5-36.6)		Sustainable	2017

**Note: Stock status definitions and colour code

Biomass (B) Fishing Mortality (F)	Overfished (B _{year} /BMSY < 1)	Not overfished (B _{year} /BMSY ≥ 1)
Subject to overfishing (F _{year} /FMSY > 1)		
Not subject to overfishing (F _{year} /FMSY ≤ 1)		
Not assessed / Uncertain		

IOTC has adopted various measures such as a rebuilding plan for yellowfin tuna (Resolution 18/01) (IOTC, 2018b), limitations on fishing capacity (Resolution 15/10) (IOTC, 2015d), and the development of an allocation system (Quota) for tropical tunas stocks (Resolution 14/02) (IOTC, 2014), bearing in mind that these and other measures have a potential effect on the exploitation of tropical tunas in general.

Species such as swordfish and Blue shark are important target species of the EU and the Seychellois longline fleet. These two species are being fished sustainably according to IOTC, but it should be noted that the EU fleet takes most of its catches in the southern IO, not making use of fishing possibilities in the Seychelles EEZ. The other billfish species are included for the sake of completeness, as these may be taken as bycatches in longline fleets.

2.4 Specific challenges in CS

Although the Seychelles institution and legal framework is well established, the ongoing reorganization of the SFA may affect the MCS of the EU fishing fleet. Also, challenges were raised during the stakeholder interaction in FarFish. The following challenges form the basis for the OTs described in chapter 3 and are based on output from the stakeholder interaction in FarFish, where the operators, the CS leader and the IOTC has contributed. In addition, some challenges are based on the most recent Evaluation of the agreement between the Seychelles and EU (Goulding et al., 2019).

2.4.1 Gazette Marine zones

A central pillar for the sustainability of the blue growth policy is the implementation of the Seychelles Marine Spatial Planning process (SMSP). This includes the designation of two extended Marine Protected Areas covering at this stage 15% of the EEZ (with a further 15% foreseen in the future). The proposed regulatory restrictions will impact on EU tuna operators (who were consulted extensively on the SMSP process) (Goulding et al., 2019).

The Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC) in Seychelles signed and thereby legally designated the marine boundaries for the expansion of the marine protected areas around

Seychelles' Aldabra group (Zone 1) and Amirantes to Fortune Bank (Zone 2) on April 12th 2019 (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan, Gazetted Marine Zones 15 April 2019 (Source: <https://seymssp.com>)⁷⁵

Zone 1 includes an UNESCO world heritage site, which is home to the dugong, the most threatened animal in the western Indian Ocean, and 100,000 giant tortoises. The second zone includes important areas for tourism and fisheries. The zones will be implemented in 2021, on the completion of the SMSP. This is expected to impact on some 4,000 to 5,000 tonnes of catch by the EU vessels fishing under the Agreement, although the fishing effort associated with this catch is expected to be re-directed to other zones, within or outside the Seychelles EEZ (Goulding et al., 2019).

2.4.2 Lack of data to undertake stock assessment of bycatch species

Most IOTC Contracting Party and Non-Contracting Party (CPC) have systematically failed to provide the IOTC Secretariat with estimates of total bycatch; or observer reports from which bycatch levels can be assessed (IOTC 2017-WPEB13-07). There is limited or complete lack of data and stock assessments of non-target species that are regularly caught as bycatch in the tuna fishery and included in the recent

⁷⁵[https://seymssp.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/SEYMSP Milestone 2 Gazetted Marine Zones 25April2019.pdf](https://seymssp.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/SEYMSP_Milestone_2_Gazetted_Marine_Zones_25April2019.pdf)

discard ban (17/04)⁷⁶. Operator OPAGAC is already addressing some actions identified in the FIP Action Plan, with a focus on bycatch and endangered, threatened and protected species in the Indian Ocean (IOTC, 2018c). The IOTC, as a member of the FarFish RG, suggested the issue the assessment of the sustainability of non-target species included in the recent discard ban as worth examining in FarFish, especially for dolphinfish, wahoo, barracuda and rainbow runners.

2.4.3 Insufficient monitoring and control in the Seychelles EEZ

During the scoping process while developing this MR1, the IOTC reported that any initiative that will contribute to improved compliance is welcomed. Monitoring of transshipment and landings has been difficult for the distant water industrial longliners as they do not land in Port Victoria. This makes it difficult to obtain good logbook coverage of this part of the fishery (FarFish, 2019 - [D3.3](#)). SFA interacts with other countries in the fight against IUU-fishing and is a leading partner in a project called FishGuard⁷⁷, where fishing activities will be surveilled by drones.

2.4.3.1 Satellite monitoring system (VMS)

VMS is used as a monitoring tool for ensuring compliance to restricted zones (see chapter 2.4.1), such as closure for shallow water to industrial vessels (DG Mare, 2013; IOTC, 2017a). When VMS data is used along with electronic logbook, misreporting at the point of harvest can be reduced and thereby support the fight against IUU fisheries. Representatives for EU Operators in FarFish stress the need to combat IUU fisheries, as such practices create uneven playing field which responsible operators cannot compete with.

The IOTC Resolution 15/03 (IOTC, 2017a, Appendix 3) state that all Contracting Party and Non-Contracting Party (CPC) shall adopt a VMS for all vessels flying its flag 24 meters in length overall or above or in case of vessels less than 24 meters, those operating in waters outside the EEZ of the Flag state fishing for species covered by the IOTC Agreement within the IOTC area of competence (IOTC Resolution 15/03). All Seychelles flagged industrial vessels (71 at present according to Goulding et al., 2019) and foreign vessels operating within the EEZ are required to operate satellite VMS systems, but this is currently not mandatory for local vessels (FarFish, 2019 - [D3.3](#)).

There is a very large variability in the way Resolution 15/03 is implemented by the CPCs and although there are some areas of consistency, there are widely different standards that apply to most aspects of the system (IOTC, 2019). Some CPCs have not yet implemented the national VMS framework and according to the recommendations provided in IOTC VMS study (2019), it is suggested that IOTC should consider direct support for implementation of obligation in the design of any ABNJ follow-on project.

⁷⁶ https://www.iotc.org/sites/default/files/documents/compliance/cmm/iotc_cmm_1704.pdf

⁷⁷ <http://www.grida.no/activities/275>

There are some technical challenges at SFA related to monitoring of the VMS data received. There are also problems with Internet connection for long periods of time (sometimes more than a week) so they cannot perform their work adequately (FarFish, 2018i). According to Goulding et al (2019), the VMS system (installed by French contractor CLS) will be upgraded in 2019 with a back-up system, incorporation of Automatic Identification System (AIS), satellite data and installation of the Electronic Recording System (ERS) for automatic recording of catch data for the Seychelles flagged vessels.

2.4.3.2 Automatic Identification System (AIS)

Another compulsory monitoring system for vessels over 300 gross tons (GT) engaged on international voyages is the Automatic Identification System (AIS) which is shared real-time information of ship traffic. The AIS was intended to increase security at sea and support ship to ship collision avoidance, but as AIS transposes dynamic information such as ships position, course, speed, type of ship, navigational status in addition to International Maritime Organization (IMO) number, and the processed AIS data can provide insights and information for regulatory bodies and researchers.

Tracking AIS signals may aid monitoring and conservation of marine ecosystems. The IMO Convention for the Safety Of Life At Sea (SOLAS) Regulation V/19.2 requires vessels to operate AIS Class A on-board at all times, unless there are valid security reasons to turn it off, temporarily. In 2014, the European Commission required the entire fishery fleet >15 m to install AIS Class A transmitters (Shelmerdine, 2015). Nevertheless, as AIS is an open source information system, the EU operators transmitting AIS are continuously monitored by their competitors and in the Indian Ocean, and potentially also by pirates.

Somali piracy has been a problem in the region since the 1990's, with serious impacts for the Seychelles. This also limits the ability of the SFA to monitor its fishery as the national resources tend to become dedicated to combating piracy (FarFish, 2019 - [D3.3](#)). This can affect the security of the EU fleet and give their competitors indications, based on their interpretation of the AIS positions over time, of where their fishing activity might take place and thereby experience a public exposure of their fishing activity. If non-EU fleets do not comply by the same rules, the level playing field is undermined.

2.4.3.3 Observers

There are very limited independent observer coverage; data on catches by the industrial sector provided by the SFA is reliant on reports sent by the fishing vessels (FarFish, 2019 - [D3.3](#)). The international Seafood Sustainability Foundation (ISSF) Conservation Measure 4.3(a) relates to observer coverage for large-scale purse seine initiating a 100% observer coverage (human or electronic if proven to be effective) (ISSF, 2019) and has also provided a survey report on human observer programs for

Purse Seine and a set of Best Practices⁷⁸. For surface longline, the coverage is variable and generally lower than the stipulated target at 5% (FarFish, 2019 - [D2.4](#)). There is a request from operators to set conditions for a better coordination of the observer programme with respect to content (protocols, criteria), schedules, processes and sharing of information.

At the MR Kick-off meeting in Vigo (June 2018, Spain), OPAGAC pointed out that there are difficulties caused by the fact that observers are usually required to be national. This means that vessels have to go ashore and replace the observers every time they cross an EEZ. This could be addressed by having an international pool of observers. Another challenge is the associated costs for the vessels. OPAGAC is doing a regional strategy for improving training, aiming for regional training of observers, and it was suggested that FarFish may take input from this program.

2.4.3.4 Catch data reporting

The SFA routinely collects catch and effort data from logbooks (Appendix 4, Appendix 5) of the EU purse seine vessels in compliance with IOTC mandatory requirements (IOTC, 2015a, 2015b, 2017b, Appendix 6). They also collect length-frequency data for yellowfin, bigeye and skipjack tuna through port sampling, and supplies data to the IOTC sampling programs. After many years of effort, the Electronic Recording System (ERS) for automatic recording of catch reports from EU vessels continue to experience technical problems, where vessels are submitting data which is received with missing data fields, and the system cannot yet therefore be relied upon (Goulding et al. 2019). Also, submissions of ERS, made obligatory since 2012 by the Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009, represent the captain's estimates only. SFA experts also told the FarFish team visiting Seychelles, that monitoring of the yellowfin catches near real time is extremely difficult and require additional human resource capacity (FarFish, 2018i).

2.4.4 Lack of transparency

There are other non-EU fleets operating under private agreements, particularly Asian longline fleets such as the ones from Taiwan. There is a general lack of transparency of the content of the agreements between Seychelles and Asian countries as well as the nature and dynamics of their fishing activities. Due to little data available it is not possible to ensure level playing field amongst fishing operators. Nevertheless, the Seychelles was one of the first countries to support the Fisheries Transparency Initiative (FiTI). FiTI is a global initiative which seeks to establish a global level playing field among fisheries countries and supports Sustainable Development Goal 14⁷⁹. In May 2019, the International Secretariat was opened in Victoria, Seychelles. FarFish will follow the progress made by FiTI.

⁷⁸ <https://iss-foundation.org/downloads/16786/>

⁷⁹ SDG 14 "conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development"

2.4.5 Limited knowledge of ecological and economic effects of drifting FADs

Fishing Aggregated Devices (FADs) may cause environmental problems, such as ghost fishing and marine pollution, as about 30% of FADs are lost or stolen at sea and may end up stranded at beaches, reefs or even at the seafloor. The FAD owners from the EU fishing industry can locate the FADs as they are equipped with geo location devices that transmit their position. However, as a vessel may have many FADs deployed drifting in the sea its FADs may disperse over a large area and then escape the radius of control by the vessel. The ecological impact of FADs is important and is addressed by the IOTC ad hoc Working Group on FADs (IOTC, 2017c). An- Inter RFMO Working Group coordinated by ICCAT on improving knowledge on the composition, types, tracking and use of FADs as well as projects such as FAD-Watch funded by OPAGAC and developed by AZTI which are also doing research on tracking and retrieval of FADs. There is also an ongoing experimental project on Biodegradable FADs running, described in IOTC Res 18/04 (IOTC, 2018b)

In addition to environmental and sustainability aspects, FADs could be explored from an economic perspective, but this is very complex as many factors are involved in business strategy decisions relating to the number and use age of FADs. In some cases, FADs may be used by other vessels. Operators and suppliers of FAD equipment may have detailed information on FADs, but this may be difficult to access as it will likely be regarded confidential business information. Operators claim that there are wealthy datasets on use of FADs in Seychelles by the EU purse seine fleet.

3 Outcome targets and indicators

This chapter identifies the OTs and associated indicators established to provide measurable performance goals for the EU DWF fishery under the FPA agreement between Seychelles and the EU. The OTs may address different dimensions (Ecological, Governance and Socioeconomic) of the fishery in question and are classified as obligatory or recommended, with a certain degree of flexibility to adapt to the realities and the evolution of the defined CS throughout the lifetime of the project. Only obligatory OTs are addressed in this first version of the MR. The recommended OTs will be addressed in the next version of the MR, namely MR2.

An OT is usually a statement of the condition of an indicator relative to a reference point, often in the form of an inequality ('A>B'), but can also be a statement of presence or absence of some entity, in which a statement can be assessed to be either true or false at a given point of time. The indicator is a variable, pointer or an index related to a criterion. Its position and trend in relation to reference points (if available) or values indicate the present state and dynamics of the system. The indicators that relate to OTs should commonly be SMART, namely Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Timely. An example of a biological/ecological indicator could be the fishing mortality (F); an example of economic indicator could be the EBITDA (Earnings before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation and Amortization); and a social indicator could be the number of jobs created.

The suggested indicators in FarFish are set to measure the degree of achievement of the OT (Table 7) and are classified according to their level of measurability. The most detailed indicator category A, is where the level of achievement of the OT is quantitative e.g. measured in percentage. Indicator category B is qualitative, where the level of OT achievement is considered to be high level (score level 4), moderate level (score 3), fair level (score 2), low level (score 1) or not present (score 0). The last indicator category is binomial, measured to have only two outcomes such as yes (score 1) or no (Score 0), true or false, success or failure.

Table 7: FarFish Indicator categories (A- quantitative, B - qualitative and c-binomial) and the level of OT achievement

Indicator category	Level of OT achievement				
	100%	75 %	50 %	25 %	0 %
A	100%	75 %	50 %	25 %	0 %
B	High level (HL) 4	Moderate level (ML) 3	Fair Level (FL) 2	Low Level (LL) 1	Not present (NP) 0
C	Yes (true/success) 1				No (False/Failure) 0

3.1 Obligatory OTs and their indicators

WP3 defined the OTs listed in the MR Invitation [D3.2](#) based on the “pre-invitation dialogues”, CS/WP leader meeting in Faro (Portugal, Nov 2017) the MR kick-off meeting in Vigo (Spain, June 2018). The obligatory OTs for the Seychelles CS address the challenges identified by stakeholders, authorities and RFMOs during the development of the MR1. Four OTs were prioritized and classified as obligatory. The development of MRs and OTs related to socio economic challenges require a differentiated approach that needs to be further reinforced in the second loop (MR2).

3.1.1 *Mandatory e-logbooks for scientific and research purposes (OT6.1)*

This OT is classified as an ecological dimension, as it supports improved knowledge base for stock assessment and sustainable fisheries management. All vessels fishing in the IOTC are obliged to report their catches according to IOTC Resolution 15/01 and 15/02 (IOTC 2015a, IOTC 2015b).

According to IOTC resolution 15/01 on the recording of catch and effort data by fishing vessels in the IOTC area of competence, each flag CPC shall ensure that all PS, LL, gillnet, pole and line, handline and trawling fishing vessels flying its flag and authorized to fish species managed by IOTC be subject to a data recording system. All vessels shall keep a bound paper or electronic logbook to record data that includes, as a minimum requirement, the information and data in the logbook set forth in Annex I, II and III in Resolution 15/01. The logbook shall be completed by the Master of the fishing vessel and submitted to the flag state administration, as well as to the coastal State administration (here Seychelles) where the vessel has fished in that state’s EEZ.

E-logbook contribute to better monitoring, as these systems can collect and transmit some data automatically at set time intervals or in near real time. When used along with vessel tracking tools, e-logbooks can help reduce misreporting at the point of harvest (Lewis and Boyle, 2017) and thereby support SDG 14, target 14.2 to fight IUU fisheries. Also, the requirement in the UN Fish Stocks Agreement (UNFSA) to ensure the “timely collection, compilation and analysis of data” for effective fisheries conservation and management underscores the need to explore the implementation of e-logbooks. The EU vessels are obliged under the CFP, Control Regulation 1224/2009 to submit catch data to their flag state by e-logbook. The reason for including this OT is to put increased pressure on other fleets to do the same. The following OT was proposed in the MR Invitation:

OT 6.1 Mandatory e-logbooks and provision of data to be used for scientific and research purposes.

However, as the comprehensive work made by IOTC on management measures does not include mandatory ERS at the moment and the fact that there are still technical issues related the ERS submission by the EU fleet to SFA, it has during the development of the MR1 been suggested by representatives for Operators to rephrase this OT. There is a need for better integration of related datasets which would improve both fisheries science knowledge and increase transparency in the control of fishing operations. Operators provide a wealth of data by different channels or tools, including VMS, ERS, observer reports from scientific surveys, fishing trip voluntary reports, etc. However, data are not processed or dealt with in a consistent manner depending on who the end receiver is, e.g. for Seychelles CS, Spain as flag state, SFA as coastal state authority, IOTC as competent authority for tuna and tuna like stocks, and feedback to operators in the fishing ground (e.g. OPAGAC). The rephrased OT is:

OT 6.1 Standardization of a fisheries information system (including data provision, handling, processing and analysis) to be used for scientific and research purposes. **Obligatory OT.**

In order to measure the performance of OT 6.1, the following indicators are suggested:

- **I_1_CS6:** Report on all relevant data protocols for EU fleet fishing under the FPA agreement between EU and the Seychelles.
- **I_2_CS6:** Standardized fisheries information system.

3.1.2 Protocol for registration of catches of non-target species in e-logbooks (OT 6.2)

This OT is classified as an ecological dimension, as it supports improved knowledge base for stock assessment and sustainable fisheries management. There is a need to improve the knowledge base for these species where there is limited or complete lack of data for stock assessment. The following OT was proposed in the MR Invitation based on the suggestion from IOTC to address the non-target species included in the recent discard ban (17/04) that are not currently assessed (e.g. Dolphinfish, triggerfish, billfish, wahoo, barracuda, rainbow runners):

OT 6.2 Development of a protocol for registration of catches of non-target species in e-logbooks.

In order to measure the performance of OT 6.2, the following indicators are suggested:

- **I_3_CS6:** Template for catch protocol for non-target species to be implemented in e-logbooks.

Comments from operators:

Most of the catches of non-target species (definitely all that are landed) are being currently duly recorded. For logistic and operational reasons, it is not possible to record the total catches, despite there is an electronic observer (CCTV) software operative in the OPAGAC fleet 365/24 for the 100% of

its EU and Seychelles flag fleet. Operators suggest to go beyond the registration and think of predictive models that can provide estimations of potential by-catch species both in terms of volume and types of species.

3.1.3 Commitment to transmit VMS (OT 6.5)

This OT is classified to Governance dimension. Information about vessels that has engagement in IUU fishing activities within the IOTC Area can be obtained from VMS or AIS data, and CPCs shall submit VMS information to the IOTC annually in the IOTC Reporting Form for Illegal Activity. In order to ensure compliance and improve monitoring of all fleets fishing in the Seychelles EEZ it is important that all vessels transmit VMS or AIS signals. As the EU DWF is committed to transmit both VMS and AIS data, the reason for including this OT is to put increased pressure on other international fleets operating in the area to commit to VMS or AIS transmission as well, initiating a level playing field, which has been requested by operators during the progress of developing this MR. The suggested OT as listed in the MR Invitation;

OT 6.5 Transmission of VMS/AIS signals. **Obligatory OT.**

Taking into account feedback from operators, OT 6.5 was changed to:

OT 6.5 Transmission of VMS or AIS signals. **Obligatory OT.**

Comments from operators:

Regarding AIS reporting, the operators were reluctant to the requirement of compulsory AIS reporting as the AIS is an open code information system giving public to exposure of fishing activities in terms of where they occur in real-time. This is particularly problematic within the EEZ of Seychelles, as there are security problems related to piracy and therefore poses a risk on skippers and crews operating in the area. ***The priority of this OT is changed from obligatory to recommended, as it needs further exploration, access to VMS data and associated strategy will be developed in MR2.***

3.1.4 Compliance to honour MPAs and no-take zones as identified in SMSP (OT 6.6)

This OT is classified to ecological and governance dimension as it relates to the management goal for sustainable ecosystem and compliance of conservation management measures for gazetted areas according to the SMSP. The proposed regulatory restrictions will impact on EU tuna operators, but the EU fleet respect MPAs. In order to enhance compliance for according to the gazetted areas in SMSP, the following OT was proposed in the MR Invitation:

OT 6.6 Commitment to honour MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP. **Obligatory OT.**

In order to measure the performance of OT 6.6, the following indicators are suggested:

I_6_CS6: Operator compliance verified by analysis of VMS or AIS data.

Comments from operators:

The project should follow closely the ongoing process of designating MPAs and no take zones in Seychelles and ask SFA to regularly report on this in order to use it as applied knowledge for the project. It is suggested to put more effort on the consultation process than on the compliance.

Table 8 summarises the management goals, management objectives, OTs and associated indicators for the obligatory OTs discussed above. Table 9 then provides a summary of the indicators, their scoring, baseline and identifies who is the responsible entities are.

Table 8: Management goals, Management objectives, Outcome targets (OT) and indicators

Management goal (CFP (SFPA) PGRM, SDG 14, IOTC)	Management objectives	Outcome Target	Indicator
Sustainable fisheries based on the best scientific advice	Improved quality of the current stock assessment for the species included in the agreement	OT 6.1 Standardization of a fisheries information system (including data provision, handling, processing and analysis) to be used for scientific and research purposes	I_1_CS6: Report on all relevant data protocols for EU fleet fishing under the FPA agreement between EU and the Seychelles Indicator score: C
	Improve knowledge base for stock assessment on non-target species currently not assessed due to data limitations	OT 6.2 Development of a protocol for registration of catches of non-target species in e-logbooks	I_2_CS6: Standardized fisheries information system Indicator score: B
Sustainable ecosystem	Protection of Marine Protected Areas	OT 6.6 Commitment to honour MPAs and no-take zones identified in the SMSP	I_3_CS6: Template for catch protocol for non-target species to be implemented in e-logbooks Indicator score: C
			I_6_CS6: Operator compliance Indicator score: C

Table 9: Summary of indicators, their scoring, baseline and entity responsible

Outcome target	FarFish Indicator	Indicator scoring	Indicator baseline	Responsible entity
OT 6.1	I_1_CS6: Report on all relevant data protocols for EU fleet fishing under the FPA agreement between EU and the Seychelles	C	0	Authority, WP2
	I_2_CS6: Standardized fisheries information system	B	0	Authority by IOTC/Operators
OT 6.2	I_3_CS6: Template for catch protocol for non-target species to be implemented in e-logbooks	C	0	Authority, WP2
OT 6.6	I_6_CS6: Operator compliance	C	n.a	Authority, SFA

3.2 Recommended OTs

The recommended OTs are not to be addressed in this first version of the MR, but they are based on important interests and needs reported through stakeholder interaction, both from authorities and operators. Strategies to achieve the recommended OTs will be developed in the second version of the MR (MR2), but some ideas and comments are drafted below each recommended OT. The following recommended OTs were proposed in the MR Invitation ([D3.2](#)):

OT 6.3: Setting of conditions for a better coordination of observer programme: content (protocol criteria) schedules, processes, sharing information. **(Recommended OT)**

Based on discussion at the Vigo meeting (June, 2018), it was suggested that observers could receive common training and that a standardized approach to observation could be deployed. Accordingly, the situation could be reviewed in FarFish, and the development of a protocol for a shared pool of observers could be defined as an OT.

One of the measures proposed is the setting up of a mixed/combined system comparing information compiled by (physical or human) observer sampling on board with information originated by EMS installed on these boats. The cross-check and interaction between both data would be a good source to detect errors, make verifications and guarantee a higher level of accuracy while minimizing risks of subjective assessments. This combined system could also serve to help achieving OT 6.2, as it might assist to quantify the by-catch data. Reference material:

<http://www.franciscoblaha.info/blog/2016/3/23/cud5ifuynu0cuwxk3wa9v0s1lz3ch>

This is an OT that will have to be worked on in collaboration between operators and authorities as it includes harmonisation of Seychelles, EU and IOTC protocols on on-board observers and will be

approach in MR2 where FarFish shall consider and potentially integrate ongoing actions to create regional observer programme. The LDAC and OPAGAC will keep informed the PMA of the Project and Seychelles CS leader on this.

Comments from operators:

OPAGAC has already signed an agreement with SFA in 2016 to develop a pilot programme for electronic observers on board fishing vessels (EMS) within the “Common Oceans” initiative under ABNJ project run by FAO and co-financed by GEF (Global Environment Facility) and OPAGAC. More information (in Spanish): <http://opagac.org/opagac-firma-un-acuerdo-con-la-autoridad-de-seychelles-para-el-desarrollo-de-un-programa-piloto-de-observadores-electronicos-a-bordo/>

OT 6.4: Provision of data on the use of FADs within Seychelles EEZ. This includes catch data, operating costs and other data relevant for estimating the socio-economic impact of using FADs (particularly drifting FADs) (**Recommended OT**)

Both the CS leader and IOTC, as a member of the FarFish Reference Group (FarFish RG), reported FAD issue as worth examining during the development of the FarFish MRs. IOTC specifically encouraged a study of the economic and social impacts of the discard ban (17/04).

According to operators, there are wealthy datasets on use of FADs in Seychelles by the EU purse seine fleet. The problem here is to use these data to assess socio-economic impact, as it is difficult to know in depth the running and exploitation costs and disaggregate them in terms of FAD use.

During the development of MR2, FarFish shall follow closely the IOTC and Inter-RFMO work on FADs to have a better understanding of the types, number and use of FADs in the Convention Areas and make assumptions/extrapolations to the Seychelles EEZ if possible. The operators suggest looking at the preliminary outcomes and findings of the FAD-Watch Project with the view of:

- Extending this Initiative to other purse seine fleets (and scientific institutes?) so they can collaborate in this project and increase the coverage of FADs deployed and used in the Seychelles EEZ.
- Defining buffer zones to preserve sensitive habitats and protected features (such as coral reefs) with high risk to attract or gather drifting or lost/abandoned/stolen FADs.
- Developing a framework including those involved interested parties for detection of other sensitive areas to protect in Seychelles and with a broader view looking for a coherent network also outside.

- Modifying gradually the FAD design in the short/medium term, to go from non-entangling to biodegradable FADs as ultimate goal.
- Performing a cost-benefit analysis of eliminating one FAD in terms of marine pollution, tourism / eco-tourism, ship cruising and safety at sea, protection and conservation of wild marine life including species and ecosystems.

Information on FAD Watch Project:

Presentation by Dr Jose Santiago at LDAC Working Group 1 (Tuna and Highly Migratory Stocks):

<http://ldac.ldac.eu/attachment/d5edb7eb-6601-4008-a42d-06062b6da6f8>

<http://opagac.org/opagac-pone-en-marcha-el-proyecto-fad-watch-en-las-seychelles-para-localizar-y-retirar-fad-a-la-deriva-o-varados/>

Given the lack of knowledge within the value chain of tuna products and what markets these products enter, the final OT was suggested in the MR Invitation [D3.2](#):

OT 6.7: Mandatory provision of sales invoices (sales certificates) in order to verify the markets tuna derived from Seychelles EEZ ends up in (i.e. canning or others). **(Recommended OT)**

Comments from operators:

This OT 6.7 is considered not acceptable by the operators, as it implies to disclose commercially highly sensitive information which might have a strong impact on prices and generate unfair competition practices between operators. It would also go against WTO and EU competition law rules. The only information it could be provided would be on overall catches but no information on final destination or markets could be provided. Furthermore, it is extremely difficult in practice to disaggregate in the reporting those catches done within the EEZ and outside, as they are all stored on deck together. Operators suggest removing this OT.

After a thorough discussion between task 4.3 contributors and stakeholders, operators suggestion to remove this OT was supported by the second FarFish annual meeting and it will not be addressed in MR2 (will not be included in MR2 invitation).

3.3 Other potential actions as supplement to the MR

Apart from the OTs identified for the EU fleet operating in Seychelles, a number of action points have been identified that could strongly support the case study objectives identified in the MPO (FarFish, 2018c). These action points have not been included in the list of OTs as they cannot be solely operationalized by the operators, as they require input/action from other relevant parties (authorities, scientific institutions, other international fleets, etc.). These are:

A6.1: Investigation (including trade-off analysis) of the economic impacts of using drifting FADs in Seychelles waters, and estimate the economic consequences of reducing the number of allowable FADs. This could lead to a conclusion on the optimal number and spatial distribution of drifting FADs.

A6.2: Analysis of the economic impacts of the discard ban (IOTC resolution 17/04, 2017)

The analysis of the distant water fleet might include some of the following variables that are used to measure the economic performance of the EU fleet by STECF at their annual economic reports (AER), they are called data requirements:

- Capacity: Number of vessels, Gross Tonnage and KWs
- Effort: Days at sea, fishing days, and energy consumption
- Employment: FTE
- Income: Value of landings
- Cost: Gross Profit GVA, and, where possible, Net Profit
- Landing: weight of landing per species, and value per species
- Capital and Investment: Value Recovery Price

4 Management strategies, management measures and adaptive planning

This section outlines and describes the strategies and key measures by which the authorities/operators plan to achieve the obligatory OTs (OT 6.1, OT 6.2 and OT 6.6). Potential risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving the OTs are identified. The chapter does as well include a section identifying internal (FarFish partner) responsibilities for achieving the OTs.

4.1 Strategies and risk for achieving OT 6.1

A Fisheries Information System (FIS) could be developed based on the experience of the EC working with EU MCS. The strategy is to develop a harmonized data protocol and methodology to ensure that data flows are implemented in a consistent manner by all relevant actors including policy makers (EU/DG MARE administrators and coastal states control authorities), scientific institutes and stakeholders (i.e. fishing operators).

This FIS would aim to agree a data reporting protocol based on the EU one including standards, indicators and requirements for this system should be jointly develop by both authorities and operators, including non-EU fleets as well insofar as possible to ensure the level-playing-field.

FarFish will facilitate this by (1) analysing catch (and effort if possible) data protocols (e-logbooks mainly) and look at the structure of data flows and communications between authorities and operators. (2) Initiate a joint work between the operator OPAGAC and SFA on the identification of the standards and indicators necessary to generate protocols for increasing reliability and accuracy of data as well as transparency in the level of use and treatment of the information presented and (3) explore the needs for technical assistance and capacity building of the human resources at SFA. This last point aligns with the intention of WP 7 to develop and deliver Tutor Web/Education in a suitcase. A travel to explore the specific input to the tutor web program is already planned.

Main risk and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this OT would be lack of templates for current data flows and failure of stakeholder involvement.

FarFish recommendations

- (1) Standardized Fisheries Information System

4.2 Management strategy and risk for OT 6.2

A template for providing data collection for non-target species in e-logbook should be explored. This work should also be reinforced with scientific observers on board in terms of pilot initiatives of sampling.

To facilitate this, FarFish will approach IOTC and ask which data they wish operators could collect and provide in the e-logbook for the non-target species for Wahoo, dolphinfish, rainbow runners and barracuda. The template will also take into consideration data for the Data Limited Method (DLM) tool developed in FarFish WP6 for the data-limited non target species in question.

FarFish recommendations:

- (1) Review data gaps for the non-target species
- (2) Explore these non-target species in the data limited model (DLM) developed by FarFish partner CSIC in Working group 6 (WP6). Will be explored in MR2.
- (3) When stock assessment is available, identify relevant conservation management measures in collaboration with the IOTC Working Party on Data Collection and Statistics for improvement of the scientific knowledge base of the species mentioned in Res 17/04 but not assessed due to data limitations.

4.3 Management strategy and risk for OT 6.6

To achieve this OT, increased monitoring in MPAs by analysing VMA or AIS data, could be a useful tool, taking into account technical and/or security issues related to the transmission of signals.

FarFish will support the progress of achieving this OT by exploring ideas on monitoring of fisheries in MPAs applying new methods and tools.

Main risks and uncertainties that may jeopardize the process of achieving this obligatory OT would be related to adaptive planning and to data treatment.

4.4 Internal monitoring of performance towards achieving OTs

The internal monitoring of the development of the OTs in this case study will be to follow up on the progress, but simulation studies are not within the scope of this case study. The following institutions are suggested to take the responsibility for the FarFish actions related to the OTs:

- OT 6.1 FarFish partner CCMAR is suggested to take the responsibility for analysing the different fishing logbooks (electronic ideally) and how is reported in the existing protocols, while LDAC will explore the data flows and reporting between authorities and operators

- OT 6.1 FarFish partner LDAC is will take the responsibility for initiate a joint work between the operator OPAGAC and SFA on the identification of the standards and indicators necessary to generate protocols.
- OT 6.2 FarFish partner CCMAR is suggested to take the responsibility to review data gaps for the non-target species and develop a template for collection of data which can be performed by operators and reported in the electronic logbook.
- OT 6.5 SFA is suggested to take the responsibility for achieving OT 6.5.
- OT 6.6 SFA is suggested to take the responsibility of monitoring the compliance for the MPAs when the new areas are implemented as part of the SMSP in 2021.

4.5 Adaptive planning

Adaptive planning shall admit for immediate adaptation within the planning period to support proper management of fisheries in case of abrupt changes occurs, for example political, distribution of fish stocks etc. The nature of the obligatory OTs in this MR does not rely on any data collection which can be exposed to abrupt changes that would require adaptive planning.

5 Monitoring, compliance and sanctions

As the IOTC is responsible for the management of the species under the EU- Seychelles agreement, they have a comprehensive list of management measures available at their homepage www.iotc.org. Compliance of management measures of the CPC is partly monitored by the FMC in flag states and the coastal state when the fishery takes place within a country's EEZ, as for the Seychelles CS. The sanctions system, including the public IUU vessel list is also available at IOTC homepage.

6 Documentation

A documentation system will be developed, describing how reliable and accurate information will be collected and provided to the auditor.

Suggested documentation:

- Fishing logbook templates (EU, IOTC, SFA), provided by WP2
- LDAC will assist the operator OPAGAC with providing the templates for data collection from the different channels or tools, including VMS, ERS, observer reports from scientific surveys, fishing trip voluntary reports, etc.
- IOTC Resolutions, recommendations and other relevant documents will be collected and provided to the internal FarFish web page by WP4 leader, UiT.
- Report on bycatch reporting systems required by the EU fleet (CCMAR)
- Template for catch protocol for non-target species (CCMAR)
- Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan Milestone 2 Gazetted Marine Zones 15 April 2019, provided to the internal FarFish web page by WP4 leader, UiT.
- Seychelles Marine Spatial Plan Proposed MSP Zone Categories, Zoning Design, provided to the internal FarFish web page by WP4 leader, UiT.

7 General considerations

In the second version of the MR for Seychelles, WP7 will explore the needs for capacity building and/or training based on the drafted version of the FIS. Some potentials remain for setting more socio-economic OTs related to landing, processing and marketing of bycatches, which often are valuable species. At the moment, it is premature to set such OTs, as some research should take place prior to that.

8 Auditor

FarFish partner Synthesis will audit the RFMS process and implementation process and has agreed to this at the initial stage of FarFish. Other auditors can however be chosen if necessary.

9 Planning process

Tentative plan:

- Report on all relevant fishing logbooks for EU fleet fishing under the FPA agreement between EU and the Seychelles, due by November 2019.
- Review data gaps for non-target species and draft for implementation of data collection in electronic logbook for EU fleet, due by January 2020
- Identification of standards and indicators necessary to generate non-target protocols, due by January 2020
- Travel to Seychelles to explore the needs for capacity building related to OT 6.1 completed by fall 2019

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Appendix 3: IOTC Resolution 15/03 VMS

RESOLUTION 15/03 ON THE VESSEL MONITORING SYSTEM (VMS) PROGRAMME

Keywords: Vessel Monitoring System (VMS).

The Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC),

TAKING NOTE of the results of the Intersessional Meeting on an Integrated Control and inspection scheme, held in Yaizu, Japan, from 27 to 29 March, 2001;

RECOGNISING the value of satellite-based Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS) for the Commission's conservation and management programmes, including compliance;

RECOGNISING IOTC Resolution 02/02 [superseded by Resolution 06/03 and subsequently by Resolution 15/03] which called for the adoption of a pilot satellite-based vessel monitoring system (VMS) by 1st January 2004;

TAKING NOTE that the Resolution 02/02 [superseded by Resolution 06/03 and subsequently by Resolution 15/03] has allowed the progressive incorporation of these systems to accommodate Contracting Parties that lack sufficient capacity for immediate implementation at a national level;

RECOGNISING that this Resolution 02/02 [superseded by Resolution 06/03 and subsequently by Resolution 15/03] provides a process for developing States of the region to build the capacity to implement this Resolution;

AWARE that many Parties have established VMS systems and programmes for their fleets and that their experience may be very helpful in supporting the conservation and management programmes of the Commission;

ADOPTS in accordance with the provisions of Article IX paragraph 1 of the IOTC Agreement, that:

1. Each Contracting Party and Cooperating Non-Contracting Party (CPC) shall adopt a satellite-based vessel monitoring system (VMS) for all vessels flying its flag 24 metres in length overall or above or in case of vessels less than 24 metres, those operating in waters outside the Economic Exclusive Zone of the Flag State fishing for species covered by the IOTC Agreement within the IOTC area of competence.
2. Those CPCs currently without a VMS for any additional vessel now meeting the criteria for inclusion in the VMS obligation since Resolution 06/03 was superseded, as defined in paragraph 1 above, shall submit an implementation plan to the Compliance Committee in April 2016 that sets out a phased approach to full implementation of their national VMS obligation within a maximum of 3 years, i.e. by April 2019, with at least 50% of all qualifying vessels compliant by September 2017.
3. Any CPC with vessels not yet equipped with VMS as already required under Resolution 06/03 (or any subsequent superseding Resolution, superseded by Resolution 15/03) shall be required to fully implement its national VMS obligation within a maximum of 1 year, i.e. by April 2016 in respect of those vessels.
4. The Commission may establish guidelines for the registration, implementation and operation of VMS in the IOTC area of competence with a view to standardising VMS adopted by CPCs.
5. Information collected shall include:
 - a) the vessel identification;
 - b) the current geographical position of the vessel (longitude, latitude) with a position error which shall be less than 500 metres, at a confidence level of 99%; and
 - c) the date and time (expressed in UTC) of the fixing of the said position of the vessel.
6. Each CPC shall take the necessary measures to ensure that their land-based national Fisheries Monitoring Center (FMC) receives through the VMS the information required in paragraph 5, and that the FMC is

- equipped with computer hardware and software enabling automatic data processing and electronic data transmission. Each CPC shall provide for backup and recovery procedures in case of system failures.
7. Each CPC shall ensure that the information in paragraph 5 is transmitted to the FMC at least once every 4 hours. Each CPC shall ensure the masters of fishing vessels flying its flag ensure that the satellite tracking device(s) are at all times fully operational.
 8. Each CPC as a Flag State shall ensure that the vessel monitoring device(s) on board its vessels are tamper resistant, that is, are of a type and configuration that prevent the input or output of false positions, and that they are not capable of being over-ridden, whether manually, electronically or otherwise. To this end, the on-board satellite monitoring device must:
 - a) be located within a sealed unit; and
 - b) be protected by official seals (or mechanisms) of a type that will indicate whether the unit has been accessed or tampered with.
 9. The responsibilities concerning the satellite-tracking devices and requirements in case of technical failure or non-functioning of the satellite-tracking devices are established in **Annex I**.
 10. Fishing vessels referred to in paragraph 1 which are not yet equipped with VMS shall report to their FMC at least daily by email, facsimile, telex, telephone message or radio. Such reports must include, inter alia, information required in paragraph 5 when transmitting the report, to their competent authorities, as well as:
 - a) the geographic position at the beginning of the fishing operation;
 - b) the geographic position at the end of the fishing operation.
 11. CPCs that cannot fulfil the obligations as outlined in this Resolution shall report to the IOTC Secretariat (i) the systems and infrastructure and capabilities existing with respect to the implementation this Resolution, and (ii) the hindrances for implementation of such a system and (iii) requirements for implementation.
 12. Each CPC shall provide to the IOTC Secretariat, by 30 June each year, a report on the progress and implementation of its VMS programme in accordance with this Resolution. The IOTC Secretariat shall compile reports prior to the annual Session of the Commission and present a report to the IOTC Compliance Committee. Based on these reports, the Commission will discuss how best to proceed with future consideration of VMS to support its Conservation and Management Measures.
 13. CPCs are encouraged to extend the application of this Resolution to their fishing vessels not provided for in paragraph 1 if they consider this to be appropriate to ensure the effectiveness of IOTC Conservation and Management Measures.
 14. Resolution 06/03 *On establishing a Vessel Monitoring System Programme* is superseded by this Resolution.

Conservation and Management Measures linked to [Resolution 15/03](#) or return to the [Table of Contents](#)

Links from within [Resolution 15/03](#)

Links from other CMMs

nil

[Resolution 15/07](#)

[Resolution 15/08](#)

ANNEX I

RESPONSIBILITIES CONCERNING THE SATELLITE-TRACKING DEVICES AND REQUIREMENTS IN CASE OF TECHNICAL FAILURE OR NON-FUNCTIONING OF THE SATELLITE-TRACKING DEVICES

- A) In the event that a CPC has information to suspect that on-board vessel monitoring device(s) do not meet the requirements of paragraph 4, or have been tampered with, it shall immediately notify the IOTC Executive Secretary and the vessel's Flag State.
- B) Masters and owners/licenseses of fishing vessels subject to VMS shall ensure that the vessel monitoring device(s) on board their vessels within the IOTC area of competence are at all times fully operational. Masters and owners/licenseses shall in particular ensure that:
- VMS reports and messages are not altered in any way,
 - the antennae connected to the satellite monitoring device(s) are not obstructed in any way,
 - the power supply of the satellite monitoring device(s) is not interrupted in any way, and
 - the vessel monitoring device(s) are not removed from the vessel.
- C) A vessel monitoring device shall be active within the IOTC area of competence. It may, however, be switched off when the fishing vessel is in port for a period of more than one week, subject to prior notification to, and approval of, the Flag State, and if the Flag State so desires also to the IOTC Secretariat, provided that the first position report generated following the re-powering (activating) shows that the fishing vessel has not changed position compared to the last report.
- D) In the event of a technical failure or non-operation of the satellite tracking device fitted on board a fishing vessel, the device shall be repaired or replaced within one month. After this period, the master of a fishing vessel is not authorised to commence a fishing trip with a defective satellite tracking device. Furthermore, when a device stops functioning or has a technical failure during a fishing trip lasting more than one month, the repair or the replacement has to take place as soon as the vessel enters a port; the fishing vessel shall not be authorised to commence a fishing trip without the satellite tracking device having been repaired or replaced.
- E) In the event of a technical failure or non-functioning of the vessel monitoring device on board the fishing vessel, the master or the owner of the vessel, or their representative, shall communicate immediately to the FMC of the Flag State, and if the Flag State so desires also to the IOTC Secretariat, stating the time that the failure or the non-functioning was detected or notified in accordance with paragraph F of this Annex. In the event of a technical failure or non-functioning of the vessel monitoring device on board the fishing vessel, the master or the owner of the vessel, or their representative, shall also communicate to the FMC of the Flag State the information required in paragraph 5 of the Resolution every four hours, by email, facsimile, telex, telephone message or radio.
- F) When the Flag State has not received for 12 hours data transmissions referred to in paragraphs 7 of the Resolution and E of this Annex, or has reasons to doubt the correctness of the data transmissions under paragraphs 7 of the Resolution and E of this Annex, it shall as soon as possible notify the master or the owner or the representative thereof. If this situation occurs more than two times within a period of one year in respect of a particular vessel, the Flag State of the vessel shall investigate the matter, including having an authorised official check the device in question, in order to establish whether the equipment has been tampered with. The outcome of this investigation shall be forwarded to the IOTC Secretariat within 30 days of its completion.
- G) With regard to paragraphs E and F of this Annex, each CPC shall, as soon as possible but no later than two working days following detection or notification of technical failure or non-functioning of the vessel monitoring device on board the fishing vessel, forward the geographical positions of the vessel to the IOTC Secretariat, or shall ensure that these positions are forwarded to the IOTC Secretariat by the master or the owner of the vessel, or their representative.

Appendix 6: Resolution 15-01 ITOC, Species listed in Annex II for longline and purse seine

Vessel category	FAO code	Other species	Optional species to be recorded
LL	SSP	Shortbill spearfish (<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>)	
LL	BSH	Blue shark (<i>Prionace glauca</i>)	
LL	MAK	Mako sharks (<i>Isurus</i> spp.)	
LL	POR	Porbeagle shark (<i>Lamna nasus</i>)	
LL	SPN	Hammerhead sharks (<i>Sphyrna</i> spp.)	
LL, PS	FAL	Silky shark (<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>)	
LL	MZZ	Other bony fishes	PS
LL	SKH	Other sharks	PS
LL		Seabirds (in number) ⁸⁰	
LL, PS	MAM	Marine Mammals (in number)	
LL, PS	TTX	Marine turtles (in number)	
LL, PS	THR	Thresher sharks (<i>Alopias</i> spp.)	
LL, PS	OCS	Oceanic whitetip shark (<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>)	
PS	RHN	Whale sharks (<i>Rhincodon typus</i>) (in number)	
LL	TIG	Tiger shark (<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>)	LL
LL	PSK	Crocodile shark (<i>Pseudocarcharias kamoharai</i>)	LL
LL	WSH	Great white shark (<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>)	LL
LL, PS	MAN	Mantas and devil rays (<i>Mobulidae</i>)	LL, PS
LL	PLS	Pelagic stingray (<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>)	
LL, PS		Other rays	LL, PS

⁸⁰ When a CPC is fully implementing the observer program the provision of seabird data is optional